

Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 10

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The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16282>

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16653>

This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

*This work brings **magic, semi-magic and pandiagonal** magic squares of order 10 for **reduced entries**. By **reduced or less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less numbers. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These **entries** are **non-sequential positive and negative numbers**. Sometimes, we call these kind of magic squares as **self-made**. It means that these are complete in themselves. Just put the values of entries and choose the sum, we get a magic square. In some cases, there maybe **decimal or fractional** values of entries depending on the types of magic squares. Different kind of magic squares are used to bring these self-made magic squares. These are of type, **cornered, single-digit bordered and double-digit bordered**, etc. Most of the results are with **magic rectangles**. In each case, these are considered with **equal width and length**. There are total 58 results. Out of them, 15 are of magic squares, 14 are of semi-magic squares and 29 are of **pandiagonal** magic squares. For the previous work readers are suggested to see author's work [30]-[41].*

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1 Introduction

This work brings **self-made algebraic pandiagonal** magic squares of order 10. By **self-made** or **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less numbers of entries, where the magic square is complete in itself. Putting any integer values for the less entries, we shall get always a magic square. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more **sequential** numbers. These entries are **non-sequential positive** and/or **negative** numbers. In some cases, these may be **decimal** or **fractional** values depending on the way of choosing the entries. Sometime to avoid **decimal** or **fractional** entries we apply certain conditions. These conditions depends on the types of magic squares. The name **self-made** is not known in the literature of magic squares. It is being introduced for first time. The work is based on different types of magic squares, such as, **pandiagonal, block-wise, cornered, single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered**, etc. It is not necessary, but we worked with **magic rectangles** with equal width and length for the same category within a magic square. If we relax this condition, i.e., by considering only equality of width, still we have good results. For more details refer author's previous works. Previously, the author brought similar kind of work for the orders 3 to 12, specially for representing the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few entries and the **days** are the magic sums.

In this work, we brought 58 magic squares, out of them 15 are just magic squares, 14 are **semi-magic** and 29 are **pandiagonal** magic squares. This work is also online available at the following links: The table below give the number of **self-made algebraic** magic squares of order 10. For more details refer author's work [36]-citeta41.

Order	Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Pandiagonal Magic Squares	Total
10	15	14	29	58

The author [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35] also worked on similar kind of idea but from different point of view. This work is for the magic squares of orders 3 to 12 for the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few entries and **days** are the sums of the magic squares.

2 Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are three examples of magic squares of order 10.

Example 2.1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 10*

mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/										505
69	87	8	27	10	99	72	95	25	13	505	
14	32	93	74	91	2	29	6	88	76	505	
85	16	49	60	61	38	33	62	24	77	505	
84	17	68	59	47	35	52	42	18	83	505	
90	11	65	41	34	63	64	36	3	98	505	
23	78	39	53	43	54	48	66	96	5	505	
12	89	45	46	67	55	50	40	71	30	505	
79	22	37	44	51	58	56	57	4	97	505	
21	73	75	86	70	1	9	81	82	7	505	
28	80	26	15	31	100	92	20	94	19	505	
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

It is a double digits bordered magic squares where the magic rectangles of order 2×4 are of equal sums.

Example 2.2. *Let's consider a magic square of order 10*

mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/										505
49	54	43	56	61	40	31	70	18	83	505	
44	55	50	53	41	60	19	82	5	96	505	
58	45	52	47	59	42	72	29	94	7	505	
51	48	57	46	67	34	27	74	99	2	505	
36	35	62	68	38	64	25	76	95	6	505	
65	66	39	33	37	63	71	30	10	91	505	
28	26	80	69	24	79	78	20	88	13	505	
73	75	21	32	77	22	81	23	8	93	505	
15	84	12	90	9	98	97	85	1	14	505	
86	17	89	11	92	3	4	16	87	100	505	
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

It is a cornered magic squares, where in each case the magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 , 2×8 are of equal sums. It contains magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8. In the left upper corner there is a magic square of order 4.

Example 2.3. Let's consider a magic square of order 10

mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/									505
91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92	505
13	26	20	80	82	69	31	71	25	88	505
89	23	64	62	35	68	36	38	78	12	505
11	24	34	49	54	43	56	67	77	90	505
96	29	40	44	55	50	53	61	72	5	505
1	79	42	58	45	52	47	59	22	100	505
93	74	60	51	48	57	46	41	27	8	505
7	73	63	39	66	33	65	37	28	94	505
95	76	81	21	19	32	70	30	75	6	505
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

It is a well known *single digits bordered* magic square. It also contains magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8.

For more details on these kind of magic squares refer author's work [25, 26, 27, 28].

3 Self-Made Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are 6 results for reduced entries magic squares of order 10 based on the Examples 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3.

Result 3.1. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$2*(T-S)/2-A35-A20-A41$	$2*A41+A35+A34+A20-A21-2*A28-3*T/2+5*S/2-A27$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$3*(T-S)/2-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19$	A19	$A21+2*A28-A20+A27-A41-A34$	A20
A27	A28	$(T-S)/2-A15$	$(T-S)/2-A16$	$(T-S)/2-A17$	$(T-S)/2-A18$	$A15+A16+A17+A18+A19-2*(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A19$	$3*S/2-A21-T/2-A27-A28$	A21
$3*(T-S)/2-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$A22+A23+A24+A25+A26-2*(T-S)/2$	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	S-M-A10	A10	$(T-S)/2-A29$	A29
A22	$(T-S)/2-A22$	A6	A4	A5	$M-A4-A5-A6$	$A10+A11+A12-S+M$	$2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12$	$(T-S)/2-A30$	A30
A23	$(T-S)/2-A23$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	S-M-A11	A11	$A29+A30+A31+A32+A33-T+S$	$3*(T-S)/2-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33$
A24	$(T-S)/2-A24$	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	$(T-S)/2-A31$	A31
A25	$(T-S)/2-A25$	S-M-A8	$2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M$	$2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S$	S-M-A9	$(1/2)*(S-M)$	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A32$	A32
A26	$(T-S)/2-A26$	A8	$A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S$	$3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M$	A9	$(5*M-3*S)*(1/2)$	$(S-M)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A33$	A33
$5*S/2-3*T/2+A35+A20-A27$	$3*T/2-5*S/2-A20+A27+A28-A41+A21$	$(T-S)/2-A36$	$A36+A37+A38+A39+A40-T+S$	$(T-S)/2-A37$	$(T-S)/2-A38$	$(T-S)/2-A39$	$(T-S)/2-A40$	$A41+A20-A28$	$3*S/2-A35-T/2-A20-A21$
A41	$3*S/2-T/2-A41-A35-A34$	A36	$3*(T-S)/2-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A37	A38	A39	A40	A34	A35

Details:

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 embedded with **cornered** magic square of order 6 having magic square of order 4 at the left upper corner. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×4 are of equal width and length. Also the four magic rectangles of orders 2×6 are of equal width and length. The letters M, S and L represents the magic squares of orders 4, 8 and 10 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums M, S and L should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd** numbers.

Example 3.1. Let's consider following two examples:

1a	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										200	1a	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										221
	-76	152	25	26	27	28	-60	29	19	30	200		-56	123	25	26	27	28	-30	29	19	30	221		
	37	38	0	-1	-2	-3	85	-4	19	31	200		37	38	10	9	8	7	65	6	10	31	221		
	-95	120	11	77	-11	13	40	20	-14	39	200		-65	100	11	78	-11	13	40	20	-4	39	221		
	32	-7	16	14	15	45	3	57	-15	40	200		32	3	16	14	15	46	3	57	-5	40	221		
	33	-8	9	8	53	20	39	21	155	-130	200		33	2	9	8	54	20	39	21	135	-100	221		
	34	-9	54	-9	33	12	38	22	-16	41	200		34	1	55	-9	33	12	38	22	-6	41	221		
	35	-10	42	56	-19	41	30	0	-17	42	200		35	0	42	57	-20	41	30	1	-7	42	221		
	36	-11	18	4	79	19	0	30	-18	43	200		36	-1	18	3	80	19	1	30	-8	43	221		
	113	-50	-21	190	-22	-23	-24	-25	43	19	200		84	-21	-11	170	-12	-13	-14	-15	43	10	221		
	51	-15	46	-165	47	48	49	50	44	45	200		51	-24	46	-135	47	48	49	50	44	45	221		
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 90$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 150$$

$$L_{12 \times 12} := 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 91$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 151$$

$$L_{12 \times 12} := 221$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 60 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 25 \times 75$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 60 \times 120$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 35 \times 105$$

Result 3.2. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

A18	A19	$2*(T-S)/2-A15-A16-A17$	A15	A16	A17	$2*S-T+A18-A19+A23$	$2*(T-S)/2-A23-2*A18$	L-T-A28	A28
$2*A13+A24+A14+2*A18-2*(T-S)/2-A19$	$2*(T-S)/2-2*A18-A13$	$A15+A16+A17-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A15$	$(T-S)/2-A16$	$(T-S)/2-A17$	$2*(T-S)/2-A23-A13-A24-A18+A19$	$2*S-T+A18+A23-A14$	L-T-A29	A29
$2*(T-S)/2-A7-A8-A9$	$A7+A8+A9-(T-S)/2$	A1	$A4+S-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$A10+A11+A12-(T-S)/2$	$2*(T-S)/2-A10-A11-A12$	$A28+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+3*T-3*L$	$4*L-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-4*T$
A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A6	A4	A5	$S-A4-A5-A6$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	A10	L-T-A30	A30
A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$S-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A11	L-T-A31	A31
A9	$(T-S)/2-A9$	$S-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	$(T-S)/2-A12$	A12	L-T-A32	A32
$T-2*A13-A14+A19-3*A18-A23-A24$	$A23+3*A18+A24-A19+A13-2*(T-S)/2$	$A20+A21+A22-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A20$	$(T-S)/2-A21$	$(T-S)/2-A22$	A13	A14	L-T-A33	A33
A23	$T-A23-A18-2*(T-S)/2-A24$	$2*(T-S)/2-A20-A21-A22$	A20	A21	A22	A24	A18	L-T-A34	A34
L-T-A35	$T-A1+A29-A28+A11+A21+A22+2*A20-6*(T-S)/2-A35+2*A10+A12-3*A4$	$T+A1-A29+A28-A11-A21-A22-2*A20+6*(T-S)/2+2*A35-2*A10-A12-2*L+3*A4+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40$	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	$(L-T)/2$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
A35	$A1-A29+A28-A11-A21-A22-2*A20+6*(T-S)/2+A35-2*T-2*A10-A12+L+3*A4$	$3*L-2*T-A1+A29-A28+A11+A21+A22+2*A20-6*(T-S)/2-2*A35+2*A10+A12-3*A4-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	$(L-T)/2$

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 10 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 8 with magic square of order 4 in the middle. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×4 are of equal width and length. Also the two magic rectangles of orders 2×8 are of equal width and length. The letters M, T and L represents the magic squares of orders 4, 8 and 10 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums M, T and L should be of same type, i.e., either *even* or *odd*.

Example 3.2. Let's consider following two examples:

2a	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										220	2b	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										251
	45	47	-63	39	41	43	103	-85	-15	65	220		45	47	-63	39	41	43	118	-85	1	65	251		
	147	-65	93	-9	-11	-13	-85	113	-17	67	220		147	-65	93	-9	-11	-13	-85	128	-1	67	251		
	-15	45	11	95	-11	15	63	-33	347	-297	220		-15	45	11	110	-11	15	63	-33	299	-233	251		
	23	7	21	17	19	53	1	29	-19	69	220		23	7	21	17	19	68	1	29	-3	69	251		
	25	5	7	5	69	29	-1	31	-21	71	220		25	5	7	5	84	29	-1	31	-5	71	251		
	27	3	71	-7	33	13	-3	33	-23	73	220		27	3	86	-7	33	13	-3	33	-7	73	251		
	-137	175	123	-19	-21	-23	35	37	-25	75	220		-122	175	123	-19	-21	-23	35	37	-9	75	251		
	55	-47	-93	49	51	53	57	45	-27	77	220		55	-32	-93	49	51	53	57	45	-11	77	251		
	-29	175	229	-31	-33	-35	-37	-39	25	-5	220		-13	190	182	-15	-17	-19	-21	-23	33	-46	251		
	79	-125	-179	81	83	85	87	89	-5	25	220		79	-124	-116	81	83	85	87	89	-46	33	251		
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220		251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 100$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 170$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 220$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 125$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 185$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 251$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 50 \times 200$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 66 \times 264$$

Result 3.3. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	a18	T-S-A18	L-T-A30	A30
A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	S-M-A11	A11	a19	T-S-A19	L-T-A31	A31
A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	M- S+A10+A11+A1 2	2*(S-M)-A10-A11-A12	A20	T-S-A20	L-T-A32	A32
M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5- A6	A2	S-M-A12	A12	3*(T-S)-A18- A19-A20-A21- A22	2*(S-T)+A18+ A19+A20+A21 +A22	L-T-A33	A33
2*S-3*M+A1-A8+3*A4- A11+A10	S-M-A8	3*M-2*S-A1+2*A8- 3*A4+A11-A10+A9	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	(5*M-3*S)/2	A21	T-S-A21	3*(T-L)+A30+A31 +A32+A33+A34+ A35+A36	4*(L-T)-A30-A31- A32-A33-A34- A35-A36
2*M-S-A1+A8- 3*A4+A11-A10	A8	3*S-4*M+A1-2*A8 +3*A4-A11+A10-A9	A9	(5*M-3*S)/2	(S-M)/2	A22	T-S-A22	L-T-A34	A34
A14	2*A11-T-5*S-A1 +2*A9+2*A8+2*A12+ A14-3*A4+A18- A19+8*M	A15	4*T+2*S-2*A14+A1- 2*A11-2*A9-2*A8- 2*A12+3*A4-A18+A19- 8*M-A15-A16-A17	A16	A17	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2	L-T-A35	A35
T-S-A14	2*T+4*S+A1-2*A11- 2*A9-2*A8-2*A12- A14+3*A4-A18+A19- 8*M	T-S-A15	2*A14-3*S-3*T- A1+2*A11+2*A9+2*A8+2 *A12-3*A4+A18- A19+8*M+A15+A16+A17	T-S-A16	T-S-A17	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2	L-T-A36	A36
2*L+6*T-6*S-2*A20- A16-2*A15-2*A11-2*A9- A17-2*A8-A22-2*A12- A21-2*A14 +3*A4- 2*A18+A1-A24+A30- A31-3*M	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	6*S-4*L-4*T+2*A20 +A29+A27+A16+2*A15+ 2*A11+2*A9+A17+2*A8+ A25+A28+A22+A26- A1+2*A12+A21+2*A14- 3*A4+2*A18+2*A24- A30+A31+3*M	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	(L-T)/2	(9*T-7*L)/2
6*S-L-7*T+2*A20 +A16+2*A15+2*A11 +2*A9+A17+2*A8+A22 +2*A12+A21+2*A14- 3*A4+2*A18-A1 +A24- A30+A31+3*M	A24	A25	A26	A27	5*L+3*T-6*S-2*A20-A29- A27-A16-2*A15-2*A11-2*A9- A17-2*A8-A25-A28-A22- A26+A1-2*A12-A21-2*A14 +3*A4-2*A18-2*A24+A30- A31-3*M	A28	A29	(9*T-7*L)/2	(L-T)/2

Details:

It is a *cornered* magic square of order 10 having the magic squares of orders 6 and 8 also *cornered* magic squares. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 and 2×8 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T and L represents the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums M, S, T and L should be of same type, i.e., either *even* or *odd* numbers.

Example 3.3. Let's consider following two examples:

3a	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										222	3b	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										301
	21	67	-21	23	0	30	25	37	-3	43	222		21	68	-21	23	10	30	23	37	67	43	301		
	26	24	25	15	63	-33	52	10	-4	44	222		26	24	25	16	53	-13	19	41	66	44	301		
	19	18	23	30	-1	31	40	22	202	-162	222		19	18	24	30	9	31	75	-15	-8	118	301		
	24	-19	63	22	-2	32	24	38	-5	45	222		25	-19	63	22	8	32	22	38	65	45	301		
	2	-94	151	1	15	45	23	39	-6	46	222		12	-73	130	11	20	31	21	39	64	46	301		
	28	124	-121	29	45	15	22	40	-7	47	222		28	113	-90	29	31	20	20	40	63	47	301		
	38	160	-93	28	27	26	31	-35	-8	48	222		66	181	-142	26	25	24	30	-19	62	48	301		
	24	-98	155	34	35	36	-35	31	-9	49	222		-6	-121	202	34	35	36	-19	30	61	49	301		
	166	-10	69	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	20	42	222		275	60	-180	59	58	57	56	55	55	-194	301		
	-126	50	-29	51	52	53	54	55	42	20	222		-165	50	290	51	52	53	54	55	-194	55	301		
	222	222	222	222	222	222	222	222	222	222	222		301	301	301	301	301	301	301	301	301	301	301	301	

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 90$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 120$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 182$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 222$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 91$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 131$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 191$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 301$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 62 \times 186$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 40 \times 160$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{8 \times 6} := 60 \times 180$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 110 \times 440$$

Result 3.4. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$4*S-6*M+A_{12}$	$S+2*A_{13}+2*A_{14}-4*A_{12}-M$	$2*A_{12}+9*M-6*S-A_{13}-A_{14}$	$S-A_{13}-M$	$S-A_{14}-M$	A_{12}	$T-S-A_{16}$	A_{16}	$L-T-A_{25}$	A_{25}
$4*M-3*S+A_9+A_{10}+A_{11}$	A_1	$A_4+M-A_6-A_1$	$A_6-A_3-A_4$	A_3	$4*S-A_9-A_{10}-A_{11}-5*M$	$T-S-A_{16}-A_1-A_{13}-A_9-A_{14}+2*A_{12}-7*S-3*A_4+10*M$	$A_{16}+A_1+A_{13}+A_9+A_{14}-2*A_{12}+7*S+3*A_4-10*M$	$3*T-3*L+A_{25}+A_{26}+A_{27}+A_{28}+A_{29}+A_{30}+A_{31}$	$4*L-4*T-A_{25}-A_{26}-A_{27}-A_{28}-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}$
$S-A_9-M$	A_6	A_4	A_5	$M-A_4-A_5-A_6$	A_9	$2*A_{16}+A_{18}+A_{19}+A_1-2*T+9*S+A_{13}+A_9+A_{14}-2*A_{12}+3*A_4+10*M+A_{17}$	$3*T-10*S-A_{18}-A_{19}-2*A_{16}-A_1-A_{13}-A_9-A_{14}+2*A_{12}-3*A_4+10*M-A_{17}$	$L-T-A_{26}$	A_{26}
$S-A_{10}-M$	$A_2+A_3-A_6$	$A_1+A_2-A_5$	$M-A_1-A_2-A_4$	$A_4+A_5+A_6-A_2-A_3$	A_{10}	$T-S-A_{17}$	A_{17}	$L-T-A_{27}$	A_{27}
$S-A_{11}-M$	$M-A_1-A_2-A_3$	$A_5-A_2-2*A_4+A_6$	$A_1+A_2+A_3+2*A_4-A_5-A_6$	A_2	A_{11}	$T-S-A_{18}$	A_{18}	$L-T-A_{28}$	A_{28}
$5*M-A_{12}-3*S$	$4*A_{12}-2*A_{13}-2*A_{14}$	$7*S+A_{13}+A_{14}-2*A_{12}-10*M$	A_{13}	A_{14}	$5*M-A_{12}-3*S$	$T-S-A_{19}$	A_{19}	$L-T-A_{29}$	A_{29}
$T-S+A_{13}+A_9+A_{14}-2*A_{12}+2*A_1+7*S+6*A_4-11*M$	$8*S+A_{13}+A_9+A_{14}-2*A_{12}+2*A_1+6*A_4-11*M$	$A_{21}+A_{20}+A_{22}-T-2*A_{13}-2*A_9-2*A_{14}+4*A_{12}-4*A_1-14*S-12*A_4+22*M$	$T-S-A_{20}$	$T-S-A_{21}$	$T-S-A_{22}$	$(T-S)/2$	$(7*S-5*T)/2$	$L-T-A_{30}$	A_{30}
$11*M-A_{13}-A_9-A_{14}+2*A_{12}-2*A_1-7*S-6*A_4$	$T-9*S-A_{13}-A_9-A_{14}+2*A_{12}-2*A_1-6*A_4+11*M$	$2*T+13*S+2*A_{13}+2*A_9+2*A_{14}-4*A_{12}+4*A_1+12*A_4-22*M-A_{21}-A_{20}-A_{22}$	A_{20}	A_{21}	A_{22}	$(7*S-5*T)/2$	$(T-S)/2$	$L-T-A_{31}$	A_{31}
$L-T-A_{32}$	$4*L+2*A_{17}+A_{19}+A_{18}+2*A_{16}+12*M-9*A_4+2*A_{12}-3*A_1-S-A_{13}-A_9-2*A_{14}-A_{11}+A_{21}+2*A_{20}+A_{22}-A_{32}-10*T-2*A_{25}-A_{26}-A_{27}-A_{28}-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}$	$2*A_{32}+12*T+2*A_{25}+A_{26}+A_{27}+A_{28}+A_{29}+A_{30}+A_{31}-6*L+A_{37}+A_{36}+A_{35}+A_{34}+A_{33}-2*A_{17}-A_{19}-A_{18}-2*A_{16}-12*M+9*A_4-2*A_{12}+3*A_1+S+A_{13}+A_9+2*A_{14}+A_{11}-A_{21}-2*A_{20}-A_{22}$	$L-T-A_{33}$	$L-T-A_{34}$	$L-T-A_{35}$	$L-T-A_{36}$	$L-T-A_{37}$	$(L-T)/2$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
A_{32}	$A_{32}+9*T+2*A_{25}+A_{26}+A_{27}+A_{28}+A_{29}+A_{30}+A_{31}-3*L-2*A_{17}-A_{19}-A_{18}-2*A_{16}-12*M+9*A_4-2*A_{12}+3*A_1+S+A_{13}+A_9+2*A_{14}+A_{11}-A_{21}-2*A_{20}-A_{22}$	$2*A_{17}+A_{19}+A_{18}+2*A_{16}+12*M-9*A_4+2*A_{12}-3*A_1-S-A_{13}-A_9-2*A_{14}-A_{11}+A_{21}+2*A_{20}+A_{22}-2*A_{32}-13*T-2*A_{25}-A_{26}-A_{27}-A_{28}-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}+7*L-A_{37}-A_{36}-A_{35}-A_{34}-A_{33}$	A_{33}	A_{34}	A_{35}	A_{36}	A_{37}	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	$(L-T)/2$

Details:

It is also a *cornered* magic square of order 10 with *single-digit bordered* magic square of order 6 at the upper left corner containing magic square of order 4. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×8 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T and L represents the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums M, S, T and L should be of same type, i.e., either *even* or *odd* numbers.

Example 3.4. Let's consider following two examples:

4a	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										250	4b	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										333
	84	68	-69	3	0	44	4	56	-23	83	250		128	99	-135	34	31	44	-6	56	-1	83	333		
	44	11	63	-11	17	6	-221	281	464	-404	250		-9	11	103	-11	17	90	-328	378	398	-316	333		
	15	26	20	23	11	35	403	-343	-26	86	250		46	26	20	23	51	35	520	-470	-4	86	333		
	12	5	2	35	38	38	1	59	-29	89	250		43	5	2	75	38	38	-9	59	-7	89	333		
	9	38	-5	33	14	41	-2	62	-32	92	250		40	78	-5	33	14	41	-12	62	-10	92	333		
	-34	-18	119	47	50	-34	-5	65	-35	95	250		-47	-18	216	47	50	-47	-15	65	-13	95	333		
	276	346	-409	-8	-11	-14	30	-20	-38	98	250		323	474	-584	-18	-21	-24	25	76	-16	98	333		
	-216	-286	469	68	71	74	-20	30	-41	101	250		-273	-424	634	68	71	74	76	25	-19	101	333		
	-44	-611	1160	-47	-50	-53	-56	-59	30	-20	250		-22	-480	985	-25	-28	-31	-34	-37	41	-36	333		
	104	671	-1100	107	110	113	116	119	-20	30	250		104	562	-903	107	110	113	116	119	-36	41	333		
	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250		333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 80$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 130$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 190$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 250$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 120$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 201$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 251$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 333$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 60 \times 180$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 60 \times 240$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 50 \times 150$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 82 \times 328$$

Result 3.5. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

T-S-A17	$2*T+3*S+A19-A14-A20$	T-S-A14	$A18+2*A17-7*T+2*S+A16+A15+2*A14+A21+A22+A24+2*A20+A23$	T-S-A15	T-S-A16	T-S-A18	T-A21-A22-A24-A20-A23-A17-A19	A32	L-T-A32
T-S-A20	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	A20	A33	L-T-A33
T-S-A21	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10+A11+A12-S+M	$2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12$	A21	A34	L-T-A34
T-S-A22	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	S-M-A11	A11	A22	A35	L-T-A35
T-S-A23	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	A23	$4*L-4*T-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38$	$3*(T-L)+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38$
T-S-A24	S-M-A8	$2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M$	$2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S$	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	A24	A36	L-T-A36
T-S-A19	A8	$A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S$	$3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M$	A9	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	(S-M)/2	A19	A37	L-T-A37
$A17+A19+7*S+A21+A22+A24+A20+A23-6*T$	$A14+A20-T-A19-4*S$	A14	$8*T-A18-2*A17-3*S-A16-A15-2*A14-A21-A22-A24-2*A20-A23$	A15	A16	A18	A17	A38	L-T-A38
$5*S-2*A12-4*M+A21-3*A4-2*A10+A33-2*T-A1+A26-2*A8-2*A9-A32+L+A14$	A26	A27	A28	$3*L-2*T+2*A12-5*S+4*M-A21+3*A4+2*A10-A33+A1-2*A26+2*A8+2*A9+A32-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A14$	A29	A30	A31	(L-T)/2	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
$T+2*A12-5*S+4*M-A21+3*A4+2*A10-A33+A1-A26+2*A8+2*A9+A32-A14$	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	L-T-A28	$T-2*L-2*A12+5*S-4*M+A21-3*A4-2*A10+A33-A1+2*A26-2*A8-2*A9-A32+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31+A14$	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	(L-T)/2

Details:

It is also a **cornered** magic square of order 10 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 8 at the upper left corner. The inner part is again a **cornered** magic square of order 6 embedded with magic square of order 4. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×8 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T and L represents the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums pairs (M, S) and (T, L) should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd** numbers.

Example 3.5. Let's consider following two examples:

5a	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										236	5b	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										285
	-3	701	3	-271	1	-1	-5	-245	-27	83	236		8	723	14	-348	12	10	6	-234	11	83	285		
	-9	21	85	-21	25	-19	39	59	-29	85	236		2	21	85	-21	25	-19	39	59	9	85	285		
	-11	31	27	29	23	103	-83	61	455	-399	236		0	31	27	29	23	103	-83	61	341	-247	285		
	-13	17	15	39	39	-21	41	63	-31	87	236		-2	17	15	39	39	-21	41	63	7	87	285		
	-15	41	-17	63	23	-23	43	65	-33	89	236		-4	41	-17	63	23	-23	43	65	5	89	285		
	-17	-15	17	55	-17	10	80	67	-35	91	236		-6	-15	17	55	-17	10	80	67	3	91	285		
	-7	35	3	-35	37	80	10	57	-37	93	236		4	35	3	-35	37	80	10	57	1	93	285		
	255	-651	47	321	49	51	55	53	-39	95	236		189	-662	47	409	49	51	55	53	-1	95	285		
	-67	-15	411	-17	-19	-21	-23	-25	28	-16	236		-2	23	270	21	19	17	15	13	47	-138	285		
	123	71	-355	73	75	77	79	81	-16	28	236		96	71	-176	73	75	77	79	81	-138	47	285		
	236	236	236	236	236	236	236	236	236	236	236		285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285	285		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 110$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 130$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 180$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 236$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 110$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 130$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 191$$

$$R_{12 \times 12} := 285$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 20 \times 40$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 56 \times 224$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 20 \times 40$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 94 \times 376$$

Result 3.6. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

	$2*T+3*S+A16-2*A13-A22-2*A12-2*A8-5*M-3*A4-A17-2*A14$	T-S-A22	$A26+2*A25+2*A13-7*T+2*S+A24+A23+2*A22+2*A12+2*A8+5*M+3*A4+A18+A19+A21+2*A17+2*A14+A20$	T-S-A23	T-S-A24	T-S-A26	T-A18-A19-A21-A17-A20-A25-A16	L-T-A29	A29
T-S-A17	S-M-A14	S-A12-M	$2*A11-3*A4-A12-A8+A9+M$	$3*A4-3*S+2*A12+A13+2*A8+A9-A10+2*A14+2*M$	S-A13-M	S-A8-A9-A10-A11-A14	A17	L-T-A30	A30
T-S-A18	S-M-A9	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	A9	A18	$A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+3*T-3*L$	$4*L-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-4*T$
T-S-A19	S-M-A10	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10	A19	L-T-A31	A31
T-S-A20	S-M-A11	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	A11	A20	L-T-A32	A32
T-S-A21	S-M-A8	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	A8	A21	L-T-A33	A33
T-S-A16	$A8-4*S+A9+A10+A11+A14+5*M$	A12	$S-2*A11+3*A4+A12+A8-A9-2*M$	$4*S+A11-3*A4-2*A12-A13-2*A8-A10-2*A14-3*M$	A13	A14	A16	L-T-A34	A34
$A25+A16+7*S+A18+A19+A21+A17+A20-6*T$	$A22+2*A12+2*A8+5*M+3*A4+A17+2*A14-T-A16+2*A13-4*S$	A22	$8*T-A26-2*A25-2*A13-3*S-A24-A23-2*A22-2*A12-2*A8-5*M-3*A4-A18-A19-A21-2*A17-2*A14-A20$	A23	A24	A26	A25	L-T-A35	A35
L-T-A36	$A30-A29-A18-A36+T-A12-A22+2*A11+A9-S-A8-6*A4+2*M-A1-A10$	$A29-A30+A18+A38+A37+A40+2*A36+T+A12+A22-2*A11+A39-A9-2*L+S+A8+6*A4-2*M+A1+A10+A41$	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	L-T-A41	(L-T)/2	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
A36	$A29-A30+A18+A36-2*T+A12+A22-2*A11-A9+L+S+A8+6*A4-2*M+A1+A10$	$A30-A29-A18-A38-A37-A40-2*A36-2*T-A12-A22+2*A11-A39+A9+3*L-S-A8-6*A4+2*M-A1-A10-A41$	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	(L-T)/2

Details:

It is also a *cornered* magic square of order 10 with *single-digit bordered* magic square of order 8 at the upper left corner. The inner part is magic square of order 4. The magic rectangles of order 2×8 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T and L represents the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums pairs (T, L) should be of same type, i.e., either *even* or *odd* numbers.

Example 3.6. Let's consider following two examples:

6a	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										320
	35	291	38	-265	37	36	34	64	11	39	320	
	43	56	58	99	-168	57	98	27	10	40	320	
	42	61	11	107	-11	13	19	28	144	-94	320	
	41	60	16	14	15	75	20	29	9	41	320	
	40	59	9	8	83	20	21	30	8	42	320	
	39	62	84	-9	33	12	18	31	7	43	320	
	44	-98	22	-19	248	23	24	26	6	44	320	
	-14	-221	32	335	33	34	36	35	5	45	320	
	4	111	80	3	2	1	0	-1	25	95	320	
	46	-61	-30	47	48	49	50	51	95	25	320	
	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	

6b	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										351
	36	293	39	-272	38	37	35	65	41	39	351	
	44	56	58	99	-168	57	98	27	40	40	351	
	43	61	11	107	-11	13	19	28	54	26	351	
	42	60	16	14	15	75	20	29	39	41	351	
	41	59	9	8	83	20	21	30	38	42	351	
	40	62	84	-9	33	12	18	31	37	43	351	
	45	-98	22	-19	248	23	24	26	36	44	351	
	-20	-222	32	343	33	34	36	35	35	45	351	
	34	112	19	33	32	31	30	29	40	-9	351	
	46	-32	61	47	48	49	50	51	-9	40	351	
	351	351	351	351	351	351	351	351	351	351	351	

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 120$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 200$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 270$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 320$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 120$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 200$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 271$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 351$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 50 \times 200$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 80 \times 320$$

Result 3.7. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}-A_4-A_7-A_{11}-A_{15}$	A4	A7	A11	A15	$S-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}$	T-S-A29	A29	L-T-A41	A41
$S-A_{12}-A_5-A_8-A_{16}-A_{19}$	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	T-S-A30	A30	L-T-A42	A42
$A_4+A_7+A_{11}+A_{15}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_1-A_2-A_3+A_5+A_8+A_{12}+A_{16}$	$S-A_4-A_5-A_{12}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}-A_{17}-A_7-A_8-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{13}-A_9-A_{11}+A_1+A_2+A_3$	A9	A13	A17	A20	T-S-A31	A31	L-T-A43	A43
A1	$S+A_{16}+A_{13}+A_6-A_{19}+A_3-A_{18}-A_{14}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{20}$	$A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}+A_{20}-A_{16}-A_{13}-A_6+A_{19}-A_3$	A14	A18	A21	T-S-A32	A32	L-T-A44	A44
A2	A6	$S+A_{16}+A_{13}-A_9+A_6-A_{19}+A_3-A_{10}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{20}-A_7-A_8$	$A_5+A_{14}+A_{10}+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+2*A_{20}-A_4+A_8-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{13}+2*A_9-2*A_6+2*A_{19}-A_{11}-A_2-A_3-S$	$S-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-2*A_{23}+A_4+A_7+A_{11}+A_{15}-A_5-A_9-A_{14}$	A22	T-S-A33	A33	L-T-A45	A45
A3	$A_{12}+A_{18}+A_{14}+A_{21}+A_{20}+A_{17}+A_7+A_8+A_{15}+A_9-2*A_6+A_{19}+A_{11}-A_2-2*A_3-S$	A10	$2*S+A_4-A_8+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_9+2*A_6-2*A_{19}+A_2+A_3-A_{12}-A_5-2*A_{14}-A_{10}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-2*A_{20}$	$A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+2*A_{23}-A_4-A_7-A_{11}+A_5+A_9+A_{14}-2*A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}$	A23	$2*S-2*T+A_{29}+A_{30}+A_{31}+A_{32}+A_{33}$	$3*T-3*S-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}$	L-T-A46	A46
T-S-A25	$A_{30}-A_{29}-2*A_9+A_{13}-A_{25}+2*S-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-A_{18}-2*A_{19}-3*A_{20}-A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_{10}+A_2+A_4+A_{11}-A_5+2*A_6-A_8+A_3$	T-S-A26	T-S-A27	T-S-A28	$2*A_{25}+A_{28}+A_{27}+A_{26}-A_{30}+A_{29}+2*A_9-A_{13}-T-S+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+A_{18}+2*A_{19}+3*A_{20}+A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}+2*A_{10}-A_2-A_4-A_{11}+A_5-2*A_6+A_8-A_3$	(T-S)/2	$(7*S-5*T)/2$	L-T-A47	A47
A25	$A_{29}-A_{30}+2*A_9-A_{13}+T+A_{25}-A_{11}-3*S+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+A_{18}+2*A_{19}+3*A_{20}+A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}+2*A_{10}-A_2-A_4+A_5-2*A_6+A_8-A_3$	A26	A27	A28	$A_{30}-A_{29}-A_{28}-A_{27}-A_{26}-2*A_9+A_{13}+2*T-2*A_{25}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-A_{18}-2*A_{19}-3*A_{20}-A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_{10}+A_2+A_4+A_{11}-A_5+2*A_6-A_8+A_3$	$(7*S-5*T)/2$	(T-S)/2	$3*T-3*L+A_{41}+A_{42}+A_{43}+A_{44}+A_{45}+A_{46}+A_{47}$	$4*L-4*T-A_{41}-A_{42}-A_{43}-A_{44}-A_{45}-A_{46}-A_{47}$
L-T-A35	$A_{32}+T-A_{31}+2*S-A_{21}-2*A_{22}-2*A_{23}-A_{26}+A_{18}-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{14}+2*A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}-A_{41}+A_4+A_{42}-A_{35}+A_{27}+A_{11}+A_7-A_5-A_9-2*T$	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	$A_9+2*T-A_{32}+T+A_{36}+A_{31}-2*S+A_{21}+2*A_{22}+2*A_{23}+A_2-6-A_{18}+A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{14}-2*A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}+A_{38}+A_{39}+A_{40}+A_{37}+A_{41}-A_4-A_{42}+2*A_{35}-2*L-A_{27}-A_{11}-A_7+A_5$	(L-T)/2	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
A35	$A_9+2*T-A_{32}-2*T+A_{31}-2*S+A_{21}+2*A_{22}+2*A_{23}+A_{26}+A_{18}+A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{14}-2*A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}+A_{41}-A_4-A_{42}+A_{35}+L-A_{27}-A_{11}-A_7+A_5$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$A_{32}-2*T-A_{36}-A_{31}+2*S-A_{21}-2*A_{22}-2*A_{23}-A_{26}+A_{18}-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{14}+2*A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}-A_{38}-A_{39}-A_{40}-A_{37}-A_{41}+A_4+A_{42}-2*A_{35}+3*L+A_{27}+A_{11}+A_7-A_5-A_9-2*T$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	(L-T)/2

Details:

It is also a *cornered* magic square of order 10 with magic square of order 6 at the upper left corner It includes magic square order 8 also as a *cornered* magic square . The letters S, T and L represents the magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums pairs (T, L) and (S, T) should be of same type, i.e., either *even* or *odd* numbers. See the examples below.

Example 3.7. Let's consider following two examples:

7a	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										280	7b	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										281
	145	17	23	31	39	-105	-17	67	-11	91	280		145	17	23	31	39	-94	-7	67	-31	91	281		
	-15	19	25	33	41	47	-19	69	-13	93	280		-4	19	25	33	41	47	-9	69	-33	93	281		
	-19	15	27	35	43	49	-21	71	-15	95	280		-19	26	27	35	43	49	-11	71	-35	95	281		
	11	-137	143	37	45	51	-23	73	-17	97	280		11	-126	143	37	45	51	-13	73	-37	97	281		
	13	21	-97	293	-133	53	-25	75	-19	99	280		13	21	-86	282	-122	53	-15	75	-39	99	281		
	15	215	29	-279	115	55	255	-205	-21	101	280		15	204	29	-257	115	55	235	-175	-41	101	281		
	-9	-323	-11	-13	-15	521	25	25	-23	103	280		1	-301	-1	-3	-5	489	30	11	-43	103	281		
	59	373	61	63	65	-471	25	25	439	-359	280		59	361	61	63	65	-429	11	30	499	-439	281		
	1	-141	-1	-3	-5	-7	-9	485	40	-80	280		-19	-140	-21	-23	-25	-27	-29	524	30	11	281		
	79	221	81	83	85	87	89	-405	-80	40	280		79	200	81	83	85	87	89	-464	11	30	281		
	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280		281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281	281		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 150$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 200$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 280$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 161$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 221$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 281$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 50 \times 150$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 80 \times 320$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 60 \times 180$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 60 \times 240$$

Result 3.8. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$A1-A3-A5-A6-A8+A7$	$A6+A8-2*m+A11+A1-A3-A5$	$2*m$	$2*m+2*A3+2*A5-A7-A11-2*A1$	$A5+2*A3-A7-A11+A10-A9$	$2*m-A9-A5-A10$	$A9-2*A3+A7+A11$	$A9$	$L-4*m-A19$	$A19$
$m+A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-A1$	$3*m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11-A1$	$(-m)$	$A7-m+A11+2*A1-2*A3-2*A5$	$m+A9-A10+A11-A5-2*A3+A7$	$A9+A5+A10-m$	$m-A9+2*A3-A7-A11$	$m-A9$	$L-4*m-A20$	$A20$
$2*A3+2*A5-A7-A11-A1$	$A1$	$A6+A8+A11-A3-A5$	$2*m+A7-A3-A5-A6-A8$	$A5+2*A3-A7-A11$	$A5$	$2*m+A7+A11-A10-2*A3-2*A5$	$A10$	$3*(4*m-L)+A19+A20+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25$	$4*(L-4*m)-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25$
$A1+m-2*A3-2*A5+A7+A11$	$m-A1$	$m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11$	$A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-m$	$m+A7+A11-A5-2*A3$	$m-A5$	$2*A3+2*A5-A7-A11+A10-m$	$m-A10$	$L-4*m-A21$	$A21$
$A3+A2-A7-A11+A4$	$2*m-A3-A2-A4$	$A7+A11-A3$	$A3$	$2*m-A6-A8-A11$	$A6+A8-A7$	$A7$	$A11$	$L-4*m-A22$	$A22$
$m+A7+A11-A4-A3-A2$	$A3+A2+A4-m$	$m+A3-A7-A11$	$m-A3$	$A6+A8+A11-m$	$m+A7-A6-A8$	$m-A7$	$m-A11$	$L-4*m-A23$	$A23$
$A2+2*A3-A7-A11$	$A2$	$2*m+A7+A11-2*A2-A4-2*A3$	$A4$	$A6+A11-A7$	$A6$	$A8$	$2*m+A7-2*A6-A8-A11$	$L-4*m-A24$	$A24$
$m+A7+A11-A2-2*A3$	$m-A2$	$2*A3-A7-A11+2*A2+A4-m$	$m-A4$	$m+A7-A11-A6$	$m-A6$	$m-A8$	$2*A6+A8+A11-A7-m$	$L-4*m-A25$	$A25$
$L-4*m-A13$	$7*m-2*A10-2*A2-2*A4-A19+A20-A13+A11+3*A7-2*A5-2*A6-2*A8-4*A3$	$m-2*L+2*A13-A20+A19+2*A4+2*A6+2*A8-3*A7+4*A3+2*A5+2*A10+2*A2-A11+A14+A15+A16+A17+A18$	$L-4*m-A14$	$L-4*m-A15$	$L-4*m-A16$	$L-4*m-A17$	$L-4*m-A18$	$(L-4*m)/2$	$(9*4*m-7*L)/2$
$A13$	$L-11*m+2*A10+2*A2+2*A4+A19-A20+A13-A11-3*A7+2*A5+2*A6+2*A8+4*A3$	$3*L-5*m-2*A13+A20-A19-2*A4-2*A6-2*A8+3*A7-4*A3-2*A5-2*A10-2*A2+A11-A14-A15-A16-A17-A18$	$A14$	$A15$	$A16$	$A17$	$A18$	$(9*4*m-7*L)/2$	$(L-4*m)/2$

Details:

It is also a *cornered* magic square of order 10 with striped magic square of order 8 at the upper left corner. The letters T and L represents the magic squares of orders 8 and 10 respectively. Here the magic sum of order 8 is always an even numbers. To get the integer entries, the magic sum of order 10 should also be an even number, otherwise some of the entries may be decimal numbers. See the examples below.

Example 3.8. Let's consider following two examples:

8a	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										200	8b	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										221
	-34	-22	60	56	4	6	31	19	51	29	200		-34	-22	60	56	4	6	31	19	72	29	221		
	64	52	-30	-26	26	24	-1	11	50	30	200		64	52	-30	-26	26	24	-1	11	71	30	221		
	7	11	27	15	3	15	22	20	-16	96	200		7	11	27	15	3	15	22	20	-79	180	221		
	23	19	3	15	27	15	8	10	49	31	200		23	19	3	15	27	15	8	10	70	31	221		
	1	21	25	13	5	17	17	21	48	32	200		1	21	25	13	5	17	17	21	69	32	221		
	29	9	5	17	25	13	13	9	47	33	200		29	9	5	17	25	13	13	9	68	33	221		
	0	12	34	14	20	16	18	6	46	34	200		0	12	34	14	20	16	18	6	67	34	221		
	30	18	-4	16	10	14	12	24	45	35	200		30	18	-4	16	10	14	12	24	66	35	221		
	57	18	-25	56	55	54	53	52	40	-160	200		78	18	-67	77	76	75	74	73	50.5	-233.5	221		
	23	62	105	24	25	26	27	28	-160	40	200		23	83	168	24	25	26	27	28	-233.5	50.5	221		
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 120$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 200$$

Second Example

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 120$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 221$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 80 \times 320$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 101 \times 404$$

Here in the second example we have some entries as **decimal** values. It is due to the fact that magic square of order 8 is always an **even** number and the total magic sum of order 10 is an **odd** number.

Result 3.9. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$2^*M-2^*A4-2^*A7-A12+A3+A6$	$3^*A4+3^*A7-A15-A2+A12-A3-A6-2^*M$	$A2+A14-A16-4^*A4-4^*A7+A3+A6-A1+4^*M+A15$	$A16+3^*A4-3^*M+3^*A7-A3-A6+A1-A14$	A3	$2^*M-A9-A4-A7-A5-A3$	$A5+A8-A16+A3+A6-A1+A9$	$A16+A4+A7-A3-A6+A1-A8-M$	$L-2^*M-A25$	A25
A2	$A4+A7-A15-M$	A1	$2^*M-A4-A7+A15-A1-A2$	A5	$M-A9-A4-A7$	$A16+2^*A4-2^*M+2^*A7+A1-A10$	$A9-A4-A7+2^*M-A16-A1+A10-A5$	$L-2^*M-A26$	A26
$2^*A4+2^*A7-A13-M-A14+A16-A3-A6+A1-A2$	$4^*M-3^*A4-3^*A7-A12+A3+A6-A13-A1$	$2^*A4+2^*A7+A12-A3-A6+A13+A15-2^*M$	$A2+A13+A14-A16-A4-A7+A3+A6-A15$	$2^*A4-M-A8+A16+A7-A3-A6+A1-A5$	$A3-A4+2^*M-A16-2^*A7-A1+A10$	$A9+A7-A3$	$A8+A3+A6-A10+A5-A9-A4$	$L-2^*M-A27$	A27
$A12+A13+A14-A16-A1$	$A1-A4-A7+A13+2^*A15+A2$	$2^*A4+2^*A7-A12-A13-A14-M+A16-2^*A15-A2$	$2^*M-A4-A7-A13$	$2^*M-2^*A4+A8-A16-A7+A6-A1$	$A16+3^*A4-4^*M+4^*A7+A1+2^*A9+A5-A10$	$3^*M-A8-3^*A7-A6-2^*A9+A10-A5-2^*A4$	A4	$L-2^*M-A28$	A28
A6	$A9+M-A11-A6$	$A11-A8-A9$	A8	A12	$A15+M-A17-A12$	$A17-A14-A15$	A14	$L-2^*M-A29$	A29
A11	A9	A10	$M-A9-A10-A11$	A17	A15	A16	$M-A15-A16-A17$	$L-2^*M-A30$	A30
$A7+A8-A11$	$A6+A7-A10$	$M-A6-A7-A9$	$A9+A10+A11-A7-A8$	$A13+A14-A17$	$A12+A13-A16$	$M-A12-A13-A15$	$A15+A16+A17-A13-A14$	$L-2^*M-A31$	A31
$M-A6-A7-A8$	$A10-A7-2^*A9+A11$	$A6+A7+A8+2^*A9-A10-A11$	A7	$M-A12-A13-A14$	$A16-A13-2^*A15+A17$	$A12+A13+A14+2^*A15-A16-A17$	A13	$6^*M-3^*L+A25+A26+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31$	$4^*L-8^*M-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31$
$L-2^*M-A19$	$3^*A4+A26-A19+A12+3^*A7-A6-A3-2^*M-A15-A25$	$L-2^*M-A20$	$L-2^*M-A21$	$L-2^*M-A22$	$L-2^*M-A23$	$L-2^*M-A24$	$6^*M-2^*L+2^*A19+A15+A25-3^*A4-A26-A12-3^*A7+A6+A3+A20+A21+A22+A23+A24$	$(L-2^*M)/2$	$(9^*2^*M-7^*L)/2$
A19	$A15+A25-3^*A4-A26+A19+L-A12-3^*A7+A6+A3$	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	$3^*L-8^*M-2^*A19-A15-A25+3^*A4+A26+A12+3^*A7-A6-A3-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24$	$(9^*2^*M-7^*L)/2$	$(L-2^*M)/2$

Details:

It is also a *cornered* magic square of order 10 with *pandiagonal* magic square of order 8 at the left-upper corner. The letters T and L represents the magic squares of orders 8 and 10 respectively. The magic sum of order 8 is always an even numbers as it is formed by four equal sums magic squares of order 4. To get the integer entries, the magic sum of order 10 should also be an *even* number, otherwise some of the entries may be decimal numbers. See the examples below.

Example 3.9. Let's consider following two examples:

9a	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										220	9b	mgc	10x10 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										261
	59	-83	241	-127	19	33	77	-39	-67	107	220		59	-83	241	-127	19	33	77	-39	-26	107	261		
	15	-99	11	163	27	-11	-29	103	-71	111	220		15	-99	11	163	27	-11	-29	103	-30	111	261		
	-79	111	67	-9	-43	71	59	3	-75	115	220		-79	111	67	-9	-43	71	59	3	-34	115	261		
	95	161	-229	63	87	-3	-17	23	-79	119	220		95	161	-229	63	87	-3	-17	23	-38	119	261		
	31	51	-31	39	55	27	-55	63	-83	123	220		31	51	-31	39	55	27	-55	63	-42	123	261		
	51	43	47	-51	75	67	71	-123	-87	127	220		51	43	47	-51	75	67	71	-123	-46	127	261		
	23	19	-19	67	47	43	-91	91	-91	131	220		23	19	-19	67	47	43	-91	91	-50	131	261		
	-15	-23	93	35	-87	-47	165	59	713	-673	220		-15	-23	93	35	-87	-47	165	59	590	-509	261		
	-43	-147	-47	-51	-55	-59	-63	625	20	40	220		-2	-147	-6	-10	-14	-18	-22	543	40.5	-103.5	261		
	83	187	87	91	95	99	103	-585	40	20	220		83	228	87	91	95	99	103	-462	-103.5	40.5	261		
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220		261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 90$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 180$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 220$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 90$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 180$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 261$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 40 \times 160$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 81 \times 324$$

Here in the second example we have some entries as **decimal** values. It is due to the fact that magic square of order 8 is always an **even** number and the magic sum of order 10 is an **odd** number.

Result 3.10. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$2*(L-2*M)/2-A35-A20-A41$	$2*A41+A35+A34+A20-A21-2*A28-3*L/2+5*2*M/2-A27$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$3*(L-2*M)/2-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19$	A19	$A21+2*A28-A20+A27-A41-A34$	A20
A27	A28	$(L-2*M)/2-A15$	$(L-2*M)/2-A16$	$(L-2*M)/2-A17$	$(L-2*M)/2-A18$	$A15+A16+A17+A18+A19-2*(L-2*M)/2$	$(L-2*M)/2-A19$	$3*2*M/2-A21-L/2-A27-A28$	A21
$3*(L-2*M)/2-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$A22+A23+A24+A25+A26-2*(L-2*M)/2$	A1	M-A1-A2	A2	$4*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-2*A5-2*A4-A6$	$A5+2*A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	A5	$(L-2*M)/2-A29$	A29
A22	$(L-2*M)/2-A22$	$A1+A2+2*A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	$3*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-A1-A3$	M-A2-A3	$2*A5+A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	$3*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-A5-A4$	M-A5-A6	$(L-2*M)/2-A30$	A30
A23	$(L-2*M)/2-A23$	$4*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-2*A1-A2-2*A3$	$2*A1+A2+A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	A3	A4	M-A4-A6	A6	$A29+A30+A31+A32+A33-L+2*M$	$3*(L-2*M)/2-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33$
A24	$(L-2*M)/2-A24$	A7	M-A7-A9	A9	A11	M-A11-A13	A13	$(L-2*M)/2-A31$	A31
A25	$(L-2*M)/2-A25$	M-A7-A8	$A7+A8+A9+A10-M$	M-A9-A10	M-A11-A12	$A11+A12+A13+A14-M$	M-A13-A14	$(L-2*M)/2-A32$	A32
A26	$(L-2*M)/2-A26$	A8	M-A8-A10	A10	A12	M-A12-A14	A14	$(L-2*M)/2-A33$	A33
$5*2*M/2-3*L/2+A35+A20-A27$	$3*L/2-5*2*M/2-A20+A27+A28-A41+A21$	$(L-2*M)/2-A36$	$A36+A37+A38+A39+A40-L+2*M$	$(L-2*M)/2-A37$	$(L-2*M)/2-A38$	$(L-2*M)/2-A39$	$(L-2*M)/2-A40$	$A41+A20-A28$	$3*2*M/2-A35-L/2-A20-A21$
A41	$3*2*M/2-L/2-A41-A35-A34$	A36	$3*(L-2*M)/2-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A37	A38	A39	A40	A34	A35

Details:

It is also a *double-digit bordered* magic square of order 10 with a magic square of order 6. It contains four equal sums *semi-magic* square of order 3. The letters L, S and M represents the magic squares of orders 10, 6 and 3 respectively. See the examples below.

Example 3.10. Let's consider following two examples:

10	mgc											100	10	mgc											122
		-128	182	25	26	27	28	-138	29	19	30	100			-108	154	25	26	27	28	-108	29	19	30	122
		37	38	-26	-27	-28	-29	137	-30	-3	31	100			37	38	-16	-17	-18	-19	117	-20	-11	31	122
		-173	172	11	28	12	19	17	15	-40	39	100			-143	152	11	29	12	23	14	15	-30	39	122
		32	-33	31	-6	26	18	13	20	-41	40	100			32	-23	28	-3	27	15	16	21	-31	40	122
		33	-34	9	29	13	14	21	16	207	-208	100			33	-24	13	26	13	14	22	16	187	-178	122
		34	-35	17	15	19	21	7	23	-42	41	100			34	-25	17	16	19	21	8	23	-32	41	122
		35	-36	16	23	12	8	39	4	-43	42	100			35	-26	17	22	13	9	38	5	-33	42	122
		36	-37	18	13	20	22	5	24	-44	43	100			36	-27	18	14	20	22	6	24	-34	43	122
		143	-80	-47	242	-48	-49	-50	-51	43	-3	100			115	-52	-37	222	-38	-39	-40	-41	43	-11	122
		51	-37	46	-243	47	48	49	50	44	45	100			51	-45	46	-213	47	48	49	50	44	45	122
		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100			122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$SM_{3 \times 3} := 51$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 102$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 100$$

Second Example

$$SM_{3 \times 3} := 52$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 104$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 122$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 40 \times 160$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 81 \times 324$$

Result 3.11. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:

$2^*m-A35-A20-A41$	$2^*A41+A35+A34+A20-A21-2^*A28-A27$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$3^*m-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19$	A19	$A21+2^*A28-A20+A27-A41-A34$	A20
A27	A28	m-A15	m-A16	m-A17	m-A18	$A15+A16+A17+A18+A19-2^*m$	m-A19	$2^*m-A21-A27-A28$	A21
$3^*m-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$A22+A23+A24+A25+A26-2^*m$	$A1-A6+A7-A12+A13$	A1	$3^*m-2^*A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A7+A12-A13$	A2	A3	A4	m-A29	A29
A22	m-A22	$m+A6-A7+A12-A13-A1$	m-A1	$2^*A1+A2+A3+A4-A6+A7-A12+A13-2^*m$	m-A2	m-A3	m-A4	m-A30	A30
A23	m-A23	A5	$3^*m-A5-A6-A7-A8-A9$	A6	A7	A8	A9	$A29+A30+A31+A32+A33-2^*m$	$3^*m-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33$
A24	m-A24	m-A5	$A5+A6+A7+A8+A9-2^*m$	m-A6	m-A7	m-A8	m-A9	m-A31	A31
A25	m-A25	$A4+A7-A6+A10-A3$	A10	$3^*m-A4-A7+A6-2^*A10+A3-A11-A12-A13$	A11	A12	A13	m-A32	A32
A26	m-A26	$m-A4-A7+A6-A10+A3$	m-A10	$A4+A7-A6+2^*A10-A3+A11+A12+A13-2^*m$	m-A11	m-A12	m-A13	m-A33	A33
$A35+A20-A27$	$(-A20+A27+A28-A41+A21)$	m-A36	$A36+A37+A38+A39+A40-2^*m$	m-A37	m-A38	m-A39	m-A40	$A41+A20-A28$	$2^*m-A35-A20-A21$
A41	$2^*m-A41-A35-A34$	A36	$3^*m-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	A37	A38	A39	A40	A34	A35

Details:

It is also a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 10 with a magic square of order 6. It contains three magic rectangles of orders 2×6 . Sometimes, we call it a **striped** magic square of order 6. The letters L and S represents the magic squares of orders 10 and 6. m is the width of the magic rectangle of order $m \times 3m$. See the examples below.

Example 3.11. Let's consider following two examples:

10	mgc										130	
		-71	76	24	25	26	27	-52	28	18	29	130
		36	37	2	1	0	-1	78	-2	-51	30	130
		-87	113	12	10	20	11	12	13	-12	38	130
		31	-5	14	16	6	15	14	13	-13	39	130
		32	-6	14	-2	15	16	17	18	148	-122	130
		33	-7	12	28	11	10	9	8	-14	40	130
		34	-8	21	19	-25	20	21	22	-15	41	130
		35	-9	5	7	51	6	5	4	-16	42	130
		37	24	-19	183	-20	-21	-22	-23	42	-51	130
		50	-85	45	-157	46	47	48	49	43	44	130
		130	130	130	130	130	130	130	130	130	130	130

10	mgc										115	
		-77	76	24	25	26	27	-61	28	18	29	115
		36	37	-1	-2	-3	-4	84	-5	-57	30	115
		-96	119	12	10	11	11	12	13	-15	38	115
		31	-8	11	13	12	12	11	10	-16	39	115
		32	-9	14	-11	15	16	17	18	154	-131	115
		33	-10	9	34	8	7	6	5	-17	40	115
		34	-11	21	19	-34	20	21	22	-18	41	115
		35	-12	2	4	57	3	2	1	-19	42	115
		37	24	-22	189	-23	-24	-25	-26	42	-57	115
		50	-91	45	-166	46	47	48	49	43	44	115
		115	115	115	115	115	115	115	115	115	115	115

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 78$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 130$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 69$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 115$$

The sums of **magic rectangles** of orders $m \times 3m$ are given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 26 \times 78$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 23 \times 69$$

Result 3.12. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:

A1	M-A1-A2	A2	$4*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-2*A5-2*A4-A6$	$A5+2*A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	A5	T-2*M-A19	A19	L-T-A30	A30
$A1+A2+2*A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	$3*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-A1-A3$	M-A2-A3	$2*A5+A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	$3*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-A5-A4$	M-A5-A6	T-2*M-A20	A20	L-T-A31	A31
$4*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-2*A1-A2-2*A3$	$2*A1+A2+A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	A3	A4	M-A4-A6	A6	T-2*M-A21	A21	L-T-A32	A32
A7	M-A7-A9	A9	A11	M-A11-A13	A13	T-2*M-A22	A22	L-T-A33	A33
M-A7-A8	$A7+A8+A9+A10-M$	M-A9-A10	M-A11-A12	$A11+A12+A13+A14-M$	M-A13-A14	T-2*M-A23	A23	L-T-A34	A34
A8	M-A8-A10	A10	A12	M-A12-A14	A14	$2*2*M-2*T+A19+A20+A21+A22+A23$	$3*T-3*2*M-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23$	L-T-A35	A35
$2*T-4*M+A19-A20+A6-2*A11-A13-A12-A15+A10$	T-2*M-A15	T-2*M-A16	T-2*M-A17	T-2*M-A18	$6*M-A10-A19+A20-A6+2*A11+A13+A12+2*A15+A16+A17+A18-3*T$	$(T-2*M)/2$	$(7*2*M-5*T)/2$	L-T-A36	A36
$2*M+A20-A6+2*A11+A13+A12+A15-A10-A19-T$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$A10+A19+4*T-8*M-A20+A6-2*A11-A13-A12-2*A15-A16-A17-A18$	$(7*2*M-5*T)/2$	$(T-2*M)/2$	$3*T-3*L+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36$	$4*L-4*T-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36$
$2*L-T+A30-A31+A21-2*M-A22-A13-2*A14-A12-A17+A16-A24$	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	$3*T-A30+A31-A21+2*M+A22+A13+2*A14+A17-A16+2*A24+A25+A26+A27+A28+A29+A12-4*L$	$(L-T)/2$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
$A31-A21+2*M+A22+A13+2*A14+A12+A17-A16+A24-L-A30$	A24	A25	A26	A27	A28	A29	$5*L+A30-A31+A21-2*M-A22-A13-2*A14-A17+A16-2*A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A12-4*T$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	$(L-T)/2$

Details:

It is a *cornered* magic square of order 10 with magic square of order 8 at the left-upper corner. It again contains a magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner. This magic square of order 6 is composed of four equal sums *semi-magic* squares of order 3. The letters L, T, S and M represents the magic squares of orders 10, 8, 6 and 3 respectively. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×8 are of equal sums in each case. See the examples below.

Example 3.12. Let's consider following two examples:

10	mgc											150	10	mgc											161
	10	19	12	-74	97	18	-8	46	-38	68	150		10	9	12	-114	127	18	13	46	-28	68	161		
	125	-99	15	99	-61	3	-10	48	-40	70	150		155	-129	5	129	-91	-7	11	48	-30	70	161		
	-94	121	14	16	5	20	-12	50	-42	72	150		-134	151	14	16	-5	20	9	50	-32	72	161		
	22	-7	26	30	-23	34	-14	52	-44	74	150		22	-17	26	30	-33	34	7	52	-34	74	161		
	-5	59	-13	-21	91	-29	-16	54	-46	76	150		-15	69	-23	-31	101	-39	5	54	-36	76	161		
	24	-11	28	32	-27	36	174	-136	-48	78	150		24	-21	28	32	-37	36	132	-73	-38	78	161		
	-42	0	-2	-4	-6	168	19	-13	-50	80	150		0	21	19	17	15	105	29.5	-85.5	-40	80	161		
	80	38	40	42	44	-130	-13	19	428	-398	150		59	38	40	42	44	-46	-85.5	29.5	398	-358	161		
	-102	-26	-28	-30	-32	-34	-36	408	15	15	150		-61	-16	-18	-20	-22	-24	-26	347	20	-19	161		
	132	56	58	60	62	64	66	-378	15	15	150		101	56	58	60	62	64	66	-307	-19	20	161		
	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150		161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$SM_{3 \times 3} := 41$

$S_{6 \times 6} := 82$

$T_{8 \times 8} := 120$

$L_{10 \times 10} := 150$

Second Example

$SM_{3 \times 3} := 31$

$S_{6 \times 6} := 62$

$T_{6 \times 6} := 121$

$L_{10 \times 10} := 161$

Result 3.13. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:

$A1-A6+A7-A12+A13$	A1	$3*m-2*A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A7+A12-A13$	A2	A3	A4	$T-3*m-A18$	A18	$L-T-A29$	A29
$m+A6-A7+A12-A13-A1$	$m-A1$	$2*A1+A2+A3+A4-A6+A7-A12+A13-2*m$	$m-A2$	$m-A3$	$m-A4$	$T-3*m-A19$	A19	$L-T-A30$	A30
A5	$3*m-A5-A6-A7-A8-A9$	A6	A7	A8	A9	$T-3*m-A20$	A20	$L-T-A31$	A31
$m-A5$	$A5+A6+A7+A8+A9-2*m$	$m-A6$	$m-A7$	$m-A8$	$m-A9$	$T-3*m-A21$	A21	$L-T-A32$	A32
$A4+A7-A6+A10-A3$	A10	$3*m-A4-A7+A6-2*A10+A3-A11-A12-A13$	A11	A12	A13	$T-3*m-A22$	A22	$L-T-A33$	A33
$m-A4-A7+A6-A10+A3$	$m-A10$	$A4+A7-A6+2*A10-A3+A11+A12+A13-2*m$	$m-A11$	$m-A12$	$m-A13$	$2*3*m-2*T+A18+A19+A20+A21+A22$	$3*T-3*3*m-A18-A19-A20-A21-A22$	$L-T-A34$	A34
$2*T-10*m+A18-A19+A9-A8+2*A11+A4+A7-A6+2*A10-A3+A13-A14+A12$	$T-3*m-A14$	$T-3*m-A15$	$T-3*m-A16$	$T-3*m-A17$	$13*m-A12-A18+A19-A9+A8-2*A11-A4-A7+A6-2*A10+A3-A13+2*A14+A15+A16+A17-3*T$	$(T-3*m)/2$	$(7*3*m-5*T)/2$	$L-T-A35$	A35
$7*m+A19-A9+A8-2*A11-A4-A7+A6-2*A10+A3-A13+A14-A12-A18-T$	A14	A15	A16	A17	$A12+A18+4*T-16*m-A19+A9-A8+2*A11+A4+A7-A6+2*A10-A3+A13-2*A14-A15-A16-A17$	$(7*3*m-5*T)/2$	$(T-3*m)/2$	$3*T-3*L+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35$	$4*L-4*T-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35$
$2*L-T-A12+A29-A30+A20-5*m-A21+A13-A16+A15-A23$	$L-T-A23$	$L-T-A24$	$L-T-A25$	$L-T-A26$	$L-T-A27$	$L-T-A28$	$A30-A20+5*m+A21-A13+A16-A15+2*A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28+A12-4*L+3*T-A29$	$(L-T)/2$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
$A12-A29-L+A30-A20+5*m+A21-A13+A16-A15+A23$	A23	A24	A25	A26	A27	A28	$A29+5*L-A30+A20-5*m-A21+A13-A16+A15-2*A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A12-4*T$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	$(L-T)/2$

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 10 with magic square of order 8 at the left-upper corner. It again contains a magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner. This magic square of order 6 is composed of three magic rectangles of orders 2×6 . Sometimes we call this magic square of order 6 as **striped** magic square. The letters L, T and S represents the magic squares of orders 10, 8 and 6 respectively. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×8 are of equal sums in each case. See the examples below.

Example 3.13. Let's consider following two examples:

10	mgc										82	10	mgc										151
12	10	20	11	12	13	27	27	-88	38	82	12	10	35	11	12	13	-19	27	12	38	151		
14	16	6	15	14	13	26	28	-89	39	82	19	21	-4	20	19	18	-20	28	11	39	151		
14	-2	15	16	17	18	25	29	-90	40	82	14	13	15	16	17	18	-21	29	10	40	151		
12	28	11	10	9	8	24	30	-91	41	82	17	18	16	15	14	13	-22	30	9	41	151		
21	19	-25	20	21	22	23	31	-92	42	82	21	19	-10	20	21	22	-23	31	8	42	151		
5	7	51	6	5	4	37	17	-93	43	82	10	12	41	11	10	9	129	-121	7	43	151		
104	31	30	29	28	-60	27	-57	-94	44	82	-8	-15	-16	-17	-18	98	4	73	6	44	151		
-50	23	24	25	26	114	-57	27	437	-487	82	16	23	24	25	26	-90	73	4	137	-87	151		
-132	-82	-83	-84	-85	-86	-87	439	-25	307	82	12	18	17	16	15	14	13	95	25	-74	151		
82	32	33	34	35	36	37	-489	307	-25	82	38	32	33	34	35	36	37	-45	-74	25	151		
82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 78$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 132$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 82$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 93$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 101$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 151$$

The magic rectangles sums is given by

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 26 \times 78$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 31 \times 93$$

Result 3.14. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:

T-2*M-A23	$2*T+3*2*M+A25-A20-A15$	T-2*M-A20	$A24+2*A23-7*T+2*2*M+A22+A21+2*A20+A16+A17+A19+2*A15+A18$	T-2*M-A21	T-2*M-A22	T-2*M-A24	T-A16-A17-A19-A15-A18-A23-A25	L-T-A32	A32
T-2*M-A15	A1	M-A1-A2	A2	$4*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-2*A5-2*A4-A6$	$A5+2*A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	A5	A15	L-T-A33	A33
T-2*M-A16	$A1+A2+2*A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	$3*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-A1-A3$	M-A2-A3	$2*A5+A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	$3*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-A5-A4$	M-A5-A6	A16	L-T-A34	A34
T-2*M-A17	$4*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-2*A1-A2-2*A3$	$2*A1+A2+A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	A3	A4	M-A4-A6	A6	A17	L-T-A35	A35
T-2*M-A18	A7	M-A7-A9	A9	A11	M-A11-A13	A13	A18	L-T-A36	A36
T-2*M-A19	M-A7-A8	$A7+A8+A9+A10-M$	M-A9-A10	M-A11-A12	$A11+A12+A13+A14-M$	M-A13-A14	A19	L-T-A37	A37
T-2*M-A25	A8	M-A8-A10	A10	A12	M-A12-A14	A14	A25	L-T-A38	A38
$A23+A25+7*2*M+A16+A17+A19+A15+A18-6*T$	$A20+A15-T-A25-4*2*M$	A20	$8*T-A24-2*A23-3*2*M-A22-A21-2*A20-A16-A17-A19-2*A15-A18$	A21	A22	A24	A23	$3*T-3*L+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+6+A37+A38$	$4*L-4*T-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38$
$2*L-3*T+A32-A33+A16+A6+2*M-2*A11-A13-A12+A20-A26+A10$	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	$(-4*L+5*T-A10-A32+A33-A16-A6-2*M+2*A11+A13+A12-A20+2*A26+A27+A28+A29+A30+A31)$	(L-T)/2	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
$(-A32-L+2*T+A33-A16-A6-2*M+2*A11+A13+A12-A20+A26-A10)$	A26	A27	A28	A29	A30	A31	$A10+A32+5*L-6*T-A33+A16+A6+2*M-2*A11-A13-A12+A20-2*A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	(L-T)/2

Details:

It is also a *cornered* magic square of order 10 with *single-digit bordered* magic square of order 8 at the left-upper corner. It contains magic square of order 6 in the inner part. This magic square of order 6 is composed of 4 equal sums *semi-magic* squares of order 3. The letters L, T, S and M represents the magic squares of orders 10, 8, 6 and 3 respectively. See the examples below.

Example 3.14. Let's consider following two examples:

10 mgc											120										
-1	374	2	-171	1	0	-2	-105	-20	42	120	6	468	9	-300	8	7	5	-82	-12	42	151
7	11	10	12	-53	71	15	25	-21	43	120	14	11	18	12	-21	47	15	25	-13	43	151
6	85	-60	8	72	-41	2	26	-22	44	120	13	61	-36	16	48	-17	10	26	-14	44	151
5	-63	83	13	14	3	16	27	-23	45	120	12	-31	59	13	14	11	16	27	-15	45	151
4	17	-3	19	21	-11	23	28	-24	46	120	11	17	5	19	21	-3	23	28	-16	46	151
3	-2	41	-6	-10	57	-14	29	-25	47	120	10	6	33	2	-2	49	-6	29	-17	47	151
-3	18	-5	20	22	-13	24	35	-26	48	120	4	18	3	20	22	-5	24	35	-18	48	151
77	-342	30	203	31	32	34	33	249	-227	120	51	-429	30	339	31	32	34	33	225	-195	151
-20	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	207	11	21	120	-11	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	182	15	16	151
42	36	37	38	39	40	41	-185	21	11	120	41	36	37	38	39	40	41	-152	16	15	151
120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$SM_{3 \times 3} := 33$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 66$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 98$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 120$$

Second Example

$$SM_{3 \times 3} := 41$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 82$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 121$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 151$$

The magic sums of magic rectangles are given as follows:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 22 \times 88$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 30 \times 120$$

Result 3.15. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:

$T-3*m-A23$	$2*T+3*3*m+A14-A20-A15$	$T-3*m-A20$	$A24+2*A23-7*T+2*3*m+A22+A21+2*A20+A16+A17+A19+2*A15+A18$	$T-3*m-A21$	$T-3*m-A22$	$T-3*m-A24$	$T-A16-A17-A19-A15-A18-A23-A14$	L-T-A31	A31
$T-3*m-A15$	$A1-A6+A7-A12+A13$	A1	$3*m-2*A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A7+A12-A13$	A2	A3	A4	A15	L-T-A32	A32
$T-3*m-A16$	$m+A6-A7+A12-A13-A1$	$m-A1$	$2*A1+A2+A3+A4-A6+A7-A12+A13-2*m$	$m-A2$	$m-A3$	$m-A4$	A16	L-T-A33	A33
$T-3*m-A17$	A5	$3*m-A5-A6-A7-A8-A9$	A6	A7	A8	A9	A17	L-T-A34	A34
$T-3*m-A18$	$m-A5$	$A5+A6+A7+A8+A9-2*m$	$m-A6$	$m-A7$	$m-A8$	$m-A9$	A18	L-T-A35	A35
$T-3*m-A19$	$A4+A7-A6+A10-A3$	A10	$3*m-A4-A7+A6-2*A10+A3-A11-A12-A13$	A11	A12	A13	A19	L-T-A36	A36
$T-3*m-A14$	$m-A4-A7+A6-A10+A3$	$m-A10$	$A4+A7-A6+2*A10-A3+A11+A12+A13-2*m$	$m-A11$	$m-A12$	$m-A13$	A14	L-T-A37	A37
$A23+A14+7*3*m+A16+A17+A19+A15+A18-6*T$	$A20+A15-T-A14-4*3*m$	A20	$8*T-A24-2*A23-3*3*m-A22-A21-2*A20-A16-A17-A19-2*A15-A18$	A21	A22	A24	A23	$3*T-3*L+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37$	$4*L-4*T-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37$
$2*L-3*T+A31-A32+A16+A9-m-A8+2*A11+A4+A7-A6+2*A10-A3+A13+A20-A25+A12$	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	L-T-A28	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	$5*T+2*A25+A28-A4-A9-A7+A8+A3+A6-A12-2*A10+A29+A30+A26+A32-4*L+m+A27-A13-2*A11-A16-A20-A31$	(L-T)/2	$(9*T-7*L)/2$
$2*T+A32-A16-A9+m+A8-2*A11-A4-A7+A6-2*A10+A3-A13-A20+A25-A12-A31-L$	A25	A26	A27	A28	A29	A30	$A12+A16+A20+A31-6*T-2*A25-A28+A4+A9+A7-A8-A3-A6+2*A10-A29-A30-A26-A32+5*L-m-A27+A13+2*A11$	$(9*T-7*L)/2$	(L-T)/2

Details:

It is also a *cornered* magic square of order 10 with *single-digit bordered* magic square of order 8 at the left-upper corner. It contains magic square of order 6 in the inner part. This magic square of order 6 is composed of 3 equal sums *magic rectangles* of order 2×6 . The letters L, T and S represents the magic squares of orders 10, 8 and 6 respectively. See the examples below.

Example 3.15. Let's consider following two examples:

10 mgc											132
3	401	6	-229	5	4	2	-84	-17	41	132	
11	13	11	9	12	13	14	25	-18	42	132	
10	11	13	15	12	11	10	26	-19	43	132	
9	15	-13	16	17	18	19	27	-20	44	132	
8	9	37	8	7	6	5	28	-21	45	132	
7	22	20	-36	21	22	23	29	-22	46	132	
12	2	4	60	3	2	1	24	-23	47	132	
48	-365	30	265	31	32	34	33	236	-212	132	
66	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	111	12	24	132	
-42	35	36	37	38	39	40	-87	24	12	132	
132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	

10 mgc											121
-15	320	-12	-58	-13	-14	-16	-111	-1	41	121	
-7	13	11	0	12	13	14	25	-2	42	121	
-8	8	10	21	9	8	7	26	-3	43	121	
-9	15	-22	16	17	18	19	27	-4	44	121	
-10	6	43	5	4	3	2	28	-5	45	121	
-11	22	20	-45	21	22	23	29	-6	46	121	
-6	-1	1	66	0	-1	-2	24	-7	47	121	
147	-302	30	76	31	32	34	33	188	-148	121	
128	5	4	3	2	1	0	17	20	-59	121	
-88	35	36	37	38	39	40	23	-59	20	121	
121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 72$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 108$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 132$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 63$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 81$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 121$$

The magic sums of magic rectangles are given as follows:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 24 \times 72$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 24 \times 96$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 21 \times 63$$

$$MR_{2 \times 8} := 40 \times 160$$

4 Self-Made Semi-Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are 10 results for self-made semi-magic squares based on Examples 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3.

Result 4.1. Let's consider following semi-magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:

$2*(L-S)/2-A42-A28-A35$	$2*A35+A42+A41+A28-A29-2*A22+(5*S-3*L)/2-A21$	A23	A24	A25	A26	$3*(L-S)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27$	A27	$A29+2*A22-A28+A21-A35-A41$	A28
A21	A22	$(L-S)/2-A23$	$(L-S)/2-A24$	$(L-S)/2-A25$	$(L-S)/2-A26$	$A23+A24+A25+A26+A27-2*(L-S)/2$	$(L-S)/2-A27$	$(3*S-L)/2-A21-A22-A29$	A29
$3*(L-S)/2-A16-A17-A18-A19-A20$	$A16+A17+A18+A19+A20-2*(L-S)/2$	$4*S-6*M+A12$	$S-M+2*A14+2*A13-4*A12$	$2*A12+9*M-6*S-A14-A13$	S-M-A14	S-M-A13	A12	$(L-S)/2-A36$	A36
A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$	$4*M-3*S+A9+A10+A11$	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$4*S-5*M-A9-A10-A11$	$(L-S)/2-A37$	A37
A17	$(L-S)/2-A17$	S-M-A9	A6	A4	A5	$M-A4-A5-A6$	A9	$S-L+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40$	$3*(L-S)/2-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$
A18	$(L-S)/2-A18$	S-M-A10	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	A10	$(L-S)/2-A38$	A38
A19	$(L-S)/2-A19$	S--M-A11	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	A11	$(L-S)/2-A39$	A39
A20	$(L-S)/2-A20$	$5*M-3*S-A12$	$4*A12-2*A14-2*A13$	$7*(L-2*(L-S)/2)+A14+A13-2*A12-10*M$	A14	A13	$5*M-A12-3*S$	$(L-S)/2-A40$	A40
$(5*S-3*L)/2+A42+A28-A21$	$(3*L-5*S)/2-A28+A21+A22-A35+A29$	$(L-S)/2-A30$	$A30+A31+A32+A33+A34-2*(L-S)/2$	$(L-S)/2-A31$	$(L-S)/2-A32$	$(L-S)/2-A33$	$(L-S)/2-A34$	$A35+A28-A22$	$(3*S-L)/2-A28-A29-A42$
A35	$(3*S-L)/2-A35-A42-A41$	A30	$3*(L-S)/2-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34$	A31	A32	A33	A34	A41	A42

Details:

It is a double-digit bordered semi-magic square of order 10 embedded with single-digit bordered semi-magic squares of orders 6. These are semi-magic only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the following condition:

$$M = \frac{2}{3} \times S, \tag{1}$$

where M and S are magic sums of orders 4 and 6 respectively.

Below are three examples based on the Result 4.1. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (1)

Example 4.1. Let's consider a following **semi-magic** square based on the Result 4.1:

1a	semi	M=(2/3)*S									180
	-75	147	33	34	35	36	-85	37	0	38	200
	31	32	-3	-4	-5	-6	115	-7	8	39	200
	-50	80	42	56	-33	26	27	22	-16	46	200
	26	4	0	11	77	-11	13	50	-17	47	200
	27	3	31	16	14	15	45	19	180	-150	200
	28	2	30	9	8	53	20	20	-18	48	200
	29	1	29	54	-9	33	12	21	-19	49	200
	30	0	8	-6	83	24	23	8	-20	50	200
	109	-31	-10	150	-11	-12	-13	-14	51	-19	200
	45	-38	40	-120	41	42	43	44	51	52	200
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

The **magic** and **semi-magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 90$, $S_{Sm_{6 \times 6}} := 140$ and $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} := 200$. There are four magic rectangles with equal magic sums $MR_{2 \times 6} := 30 \times 90$.

Example 4.2. Let's consider a following magic square with **even** number magic sum based on the Result 4.1:

1b	mgc	M=(2/3)*S									260
	-55	157	33	34	35	36	-55	37	0	38	260
	31	32	7	6	5	4	95	3	38	39	260
	-20	60	22	66	-3	36	37	22	-6	46	260
	26	14	0	11	107	-11	13	60	-7	47	260
	27	13	41	16	14	15	75	19	160	-120	260
	28	12	40	9	8	83	20	20	-8	48	260
	29	11	39	84	-9	33	12	21	-9	49	260
	30	10	38	-6	63	24	23	38	-10	50	260
	119	-41	0	130	-1	-2	-3	-4	51	11	260
	45	-8	40	-90	41	42	43	44	51	52	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

The **magic** and **semi-magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 120$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 180$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 260$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (1), i.e., $M = \frac{2}{3} \times S$. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums is $MR_{2 \times 6} := 40 \times 120$.

Example 4.3. Let's consider a following magic square with **odd** number magic sum based on the Result 4.1:

1c	mgc	M=(2/3)*S									203
	-55	100	33	34	35	36	-55	37	0	38	203
	31	32	7	6	5	4	95	3	-19	39	203
	-20	60	22	47	-3	17	18	22	-6	46	203
	26	14	19	11	69	-11	13	22	-7	47	203
	27	13	22	16	14	15	37	19	160	-120	203
	28	12	21	9	8	45	20	20	-8	48	203
	29	11	20	46	-9	33	12	21	-9	49	203
	30	10	19	-6	44	24	23	19	-10	50	203
	62	16	0	130	-1	-2	-3	-4	51	-46	203
	45	-65	40	-90	41	42	43	44	51	52	203
	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203	203

The **magic** and **semi-magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 82$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 123$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 203$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (1), i.e., $M = \frac{2}{3} \times S$. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums is $MR_{2 \times 6} := 40 \times 120$

Result 4.2. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$10^*T+A43-9^*L$	$27^*L-2^*A43-28^*T-A42-A41-A40-A38-A37-A36-A34-A35-A32-A33-A29-A30-A31-A28-A39$	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	$A34+A35+A43+A32+A33+A29+A30+A31+A28+18^*T-17^*L$
A28-T	A18	A19	$2^*(T-S)/2-A15-A16-A17$	A15	A16	A17	$2^*S-T+A18-A19+A23$	$T-S-A23-2^*A18$	L-A28
A29	$2^*A13+A24+A14+2^*A18-2^*(T-S)/2-A19$	$T-S-2^*A18-A13$	$A15+A16+A17-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A15$	$(T-S)/2-A16$	$(T-S)/2-A17$	$T-S-A23-A13-A24-A18+A19$	$2^*S-T+A18+A23-A14$	L-T-A29
A30	$2^*(T-S)/2-A7-A8-A9$	$A7+A8+A9-(T-S)/2$	A1	$A4+S-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$A10+A11+A12-(T-S)/2$	$T-S-A10-A11-A12$	L-T-A30
A31	A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A6	A4	A5	$S-A4-A5-A6$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	A10	L-T-A31
A32	A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$S-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A11	L-T-A32
A33	A9	$(T-S)/2-A9$	$S-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2^*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2^*A4-A5-A6$	A2	$(T-S)/2-A12$	A12	L-T-A33
A34	$T-2^*A13-A14+A19-3^*A18-A23-A24$	$A23+3^*A18+A24-A19+A13-2^*(T-S)/2$	$A20+A21+A22-(T-S)/2$	$(T-S)/2-A20$	$(T-S)/2-A21$	$(T-S)/2-A22$	A13	A14	L-T-A34
A35	A23	$S-A23-A18-A24$	$T-S-A20-A21-A22$	A20	A21	A22	A24	A18	L-T-A35
$10^*L-9^*T-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A43$	$27^*T+2^*A43+A42+A41+A40+A38+A37+A36+A34+A35+A32+A33+A29+A30+A31+A28-26^*L+A39$	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	L-T-A41	L-T-A42	10^*L-11^*T-A43

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 10 embedded with *double-digit bordered magic square* of orders 8. These are *semi-magic* only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need some condition. It is given as

$$T = \frac{4}{5} \times L \quad (2)$$

where T and L are magic sums of orders 8 and 10 respectively.

Below are three examples based on the Result 4.2. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (2).

Example 4.4. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 4.2:

2a	semi	T=(4/5)*L									160
	-185	-195	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	-9	220
	-105	45	47	-43	39	41	43	63	-65	155	220
	67	127	-45	83	1	-1	-3	-65	73	-17	220
	69	5	35	11	75	-11	15	53	-13	-19	220
	71	23	17	21	17	19	33	11	29	-21	220
	73	25	15	7	5	49	29	9	31	-23	220
	75	27	13	51	-7	33	13	7	33	-25	220
	77	-137	155	113	-9	-11	-13	35	37	-27	220
	79	55	-67	-73	49	51	53	57	45	-29	220
	-1	245	-31	-33	-35	-37	-39	-41	-43	235	220
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

The **magic** and **semi-magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 90$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 170$ and $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} := 220$. There are four magic rectangles with equal magic sums $MR_{2 \times 4} := 40 \times 80$.

Example 4.5. Let's consider a following *magic* square with *even* number magic sum based on the Result 4.2:

2b	mgc	T=(4/5)*L									220
	-125	-363	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	99	220
	-111	45	47	-53	39	41	43	89	-75	155	220
	67	137	-55	88	-4	-6	-8	-75	99	-23	220
	69	-5	40	11	91	-11	15	58	-23	-25	220
	71	23	12	21	17	19	49	6	29	-27	220
	73	25	10	7	5	65	29	4	31	-29	220
	75	27	8	67	-7	33	13	2	33	-31	220
	77	-131	165	118	-14	-16	-18	35	37	-33	220
	79	55	-51	-83	49	51	53	57	45	-35	220
	-55	407	-37	-39	-41	-43	-45	-47	-49	169	220
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

The **magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 106$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 176$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 220$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (2), i.e., $T = \frac{4}{5} \times L$. Moreover, there are four magic rectangles with equal magic sums $MR_{2 \times 4} := 35 \times 70$.

Example 4.6. Let's consider a following magic square with **odd** number magic sum based on the Result 4.2:

2c	mgc	T=(4/5)*L									315
	-220	74	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	-148	315
	-187	45	47	-23	39	41	43	105	-45	250	315
	67	107	-25	73	11	9	7	-45	115	-4	315
	69	25	25	11	137	-11	15	43	7	-6	315
	71	23	27	21	17	19	95	21	29	-8	315
	73	25	25	7	5	111	29	19	31	-10	315
	75	27	23	113	-7	33	13	17	33	-12	315
	77	-55	135	103	1	-1	-3	35	37	-14	315
	79	55	-5	-53	49	51	53	57	45	-16	315
	211	-11	-18	-20	-22	-24	-26	-28	-30	283	315
	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315

The **magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 152$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 252$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 315$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (2), i.e., $T = \frac{4}{5} \times L$. Moreover, there are four magic rectangles with equal magic sums $MR_{2 \times 4} := 50 \times 100$.

Result 4.3. Let's consider following mgic squares of order 10 with reduced entries:

10^*T-9^*L	$27^*L-28^*T-A36-A35-A34-A32-A31-A30-A28-A29-A26-A27-A23-A24-A25-A22-A33$	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	$18^*T-17^*L+A28+A29+A26+A27+A23+A24+A25+A22$
A22-T	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	S-M-A10	A10	T-S-A17	A17	L-A22
A23	A6	A4	A5	$M-A4-A5-A6$	$A10+A11+A12-S+M$	$2^*S-2^*M-A10-A11-A12$	$T-4^*S-A17+A1+2^*M+2^*A9+2^*A8+3^*A4$	$A17-A1-2^*M+3^*S-2^*A9-2^*A8-3^*A4$	L-T-A23
A24	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	S-M-A11	A11	$2^*A17+A19+A20-A1-2^*M+5^*S-2^*T-2^*A9-2^*A8-3^*A4+A18$	$3^*T-6^*S-A19-A20-2^*A17+A1+2^*M+2^*A9+2^*A8+3^*A4-A18$	L-T-A24
A25	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2^*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2^*A4-A5-A6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	T-S-A18	A18	L-T-A25
A26	S-M-A8	$2^*S-A8-A1-3^*A4-2^*A10-A11-A12-M$	$2^*A8+A1+A9+3^*A4+2^*A10+A11+A12+M-2^*S$	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	$(5^*M-3^*S)/2$	T-S-A19	A19	L-T-A26
A27	A8	$A8+A1+3^*A4+2^*A10+A11+A12-S$	$3^*S-2^*A8-A1-A9-3^*A4-2^*A10-A11-A12-2^*M$	A9	$(5^*M-3^*S)/2$	(S-M)/2	T-S-A20	A20	L-T-A27
A28	$T+2^*S-3^*M-2^*A9-2^*A8$	$2^*A10+2^*A12-M+2^*S-2^*A9-2^*A8$	$A16-4^*S+4^*M-T+4^*A9+4^*A8+A15+A14-2^*A12-2^*A10$	T-S-A14	T-S-A15	T-S-A16	(T-S)/2	$(7^*S-5^*T)/2$	L-T-A28
a43	$2^*A9+2^*A8-3^*S+3^*M$	$2^*A9+2^*A8+M+T-3^*S-2^*A10-2^*A12$	$2^*T+3^*S-A15-A14-4^*M-4^*A9-4^*A8+2^*A12+2^*A10-A16$	A14	A15	A16	$(7^*S-5^*T)/2$	(T-S)/2	L-T-A29
$10^*L-9^*T-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29$	$27^*T+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31+A30+A28+A29+A26+A27+A23+A24+A25+A22-26^*L$	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	10^*L-11^*T

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 10 embedded with *cornered magic square* of order 8. The inner block is again a *cornered magic square* of order 6 with *magic square* of order 4 at the left upper corner. In order to bring it as a magic square we the same condition as given in (2).

Below are three examples based on the Result 4.3. First example is of **semi-magic** square and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (2)

Example 4.7. Let's consider a following *semi-magic square* based on the Result 4.3:

3a	semi	T=(4/5)*L									320
	-160	145	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	-116	240
	-158	21	67	-21	23	0	30	43	37	198	240
	43	26	24	25	15	63	-33	70	10	-3	240
	44	19	18	23	30	-1	31	4	76	-4	240
	45	24	-19	63	22	-2	32	42	38	-5	240
	46	2	-94	151	1	15	45	41	39	-6	240
	47	28	124	-121	29	45	15	40	40	-7	240
	48	56	160	-111	46	45	44	40	-80	-8	240
	49	24	-80	191	34	35	36	-80	40	-9	240
	236	-105	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	200	240
	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above **semi-magic** square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 90$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 200$ and $L_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} := 240$. The magic rectangle sums are given as $MR_{2 \times 4} := 30 \times 60$ and $MR_{2 \times 6} := 80 \times 240$.

Example 4.8. Let's consider a following magic square with even number magic sum based on the Result 4.3:

3b	mgc	T=(4/5)*L									280
	-280	553	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	-364	280
	-182	21	87	-21	23	10	30	37	37	238	280
	43	26	24	25	35	53	-13	14	60	13	280
	44	19	18	43	30	9	31	66	8	12	280
	45	44	-19	63	22	8	32	36	38	11	280
	46	12	-54	111	11	20	50	35	39	10	280
	47	28	94	-71	29	50	20	34	40	9	280
	48	80	200	-175	40	39	38	37	-35	8	280
	49	-6	-126	249	34	35	36	-35	37	7	280
	420	-497	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	336	280
	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280

The **magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 110$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 150$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 224$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 280$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the condition given in (2), i.e., i.e., $T = \frac{4}{5} \times L$. Moreover, the magic sums of magic rectangles are $MR_{2 \times 4} := 30 \times 60$ and $MR_{2 \times 4} := 74 \times 222$.

Example 4.9. Let's consider a following magic square with *odd* number magic sum based on the Result 4.3:

3c	mgc	T=(4/5)*L									305
	-305	668	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	-429	305
	-202	21	87	-21	23	10	30	57	37	263	305
	43	26	24	25	35	53	-13	34	60	18	305
	44	19	18	43	30	9	31	26	68	17	305
	45	44	-19	63	22	8	32	56	38	16	305
	46	12	-54	111	11	20	50	55	39	15	305
	47	28	94	-71	29	50	20	54	40	14	305
	48	100	200	-195	60	59	58	47	-85	13	305
	49	-6	-106	289	34	35	36	-85	47	12	305
	490	-607	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	366	305
	305	305	305	305	305	305	305	305	305	305	305

The **magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 110$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 150$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 244$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 305$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the condition given in (2), i.e., i.e., $T = \frac{4}{5} \times L$. Moreover, the magic sums of magic rectangles are $MR_{2 \times 4} := 40 \times 80$ and $MR_{2 \times 4} := 94 \times 282$.

Result 4.4. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

10^*T-9^*L	$27^*L-28^*T-A37-A36-A35-A33-A32-A31-A29-A30-A27-A28-A24-A25-A26-A23-A34$	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	$18^*T-17^*L+A29+A30+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23$
A23-T	4^*S-6^*M+A11	$S+2^*A12+2^*A13-4^*A11-M$	$2^*A11+9^*M-6^*S-A12-A13$	S-A12-M	S-A13-M	A11	T-S-A15	A15	L-A23
A24	$4^*M-3^*S+A8+A9+A10$	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$4^*S-A8-A9-A10-5^*M$	$T-8^*S-A15-A1-A12-A8-A13+2^*A11-3^*A4+10^*M$	$A15+A1+A12+A8+A13-2^*A11+7^*S+3^*A4-10^*M$	L-T-A24
A25	S-A8-M	A6	A4	A5	$M-A4-A5-A6$	A8	$2^*A15+A17+A18+A1-2^*T+9^*S+A12+A8+A13-2^*A11+3^*A4-10^*M+A16$	$3^*T-10^*S-A17-A18-2^*A15-A1-A12-A8-A13+2^*A11-3^*A4+10^*M-A16$	L-T-A25
A26	S-A9-M	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	A9	T-S-A16	A16	L-T-A26
A27	S-A10-M	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2^*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2^*A4-A5-A6$	A2	A10	T-S-A17	A17	L-T-A27
A28	$5^*M-A11-3^*S$	$4^*A11-2^*A12-2^*A13$	$7^*S+A12+A13-2^*A11-10^*M$	A12	A13	$5^*M-A11-3^*S$	T-S-A18	A18	L-T-A28
A29	$T-S+A12+A8+A13-2^*A11+2^*A1+7^*S+6^*A4-11^*M$	$8^*S+A12+A8+A13-2^*A11+2^*A1+6^*A4-11^*M$	$A20+A19+A21-T-2^*A12-2^*A8-2^*A13+4^*A11-4^*A1-14^*S-12^*A4+22^*M$	T-S-A19	T-S-A20	T-S-A21	$(T-S)/2$	$(7^*S-5^*T)/2$	L-T-A29
A30	$11^*M-A12-A8-A13+2^*A11-2^*A1-7^*S-6^*A4$	$T-9^*S-A12-A8-A13+2^*A11-2^*A1-6^*A4+11^*M$	$2^*T+13^*S+2^*A12+2^*A8+2^*A13-4^*A11+4^*A1+12^*A4-22^*M-A20-A19-A21$	A19	A20	A21	$(7^*S-5^*T)/2$	$(T-S)/2$	L-T-A30
$10^*L-9^*T-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30$	$27^*T+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31+A29+A30+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23-26^*L$	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	10^*L-11^*T

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 10 embedded with *cornered magic square* of order 8. The inner block is again a *single-digit bordered magic square* of order 6 with *magic square* of order 4 at the middle. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the same condition as given in (2).

Below are three examples based on the Result 4.4. First example is of **semi-magic** square and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (2).

Example 4.10. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 4.4:

4a	semi	T=(4/5)*L									210
	-330	-60	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	-110	270
	-133	41	68	-9	6	3	41	7	53	193	270
	80	55	11	83	-11	17	-5	-155	215	-20	270
	83	18	26	20	23	31	32	325	-265	-23	270
	86	15	5	2	55	38	35	4	56	-26	270
	89	12	58	-5	33	14	38	1	59	-29	270
	92	9	-18	59	44	47	9	-2	62	-32	270
	95	193	283	-272	-5	-8	-11	30	0	-35	270
	98	-133	-223	332	65	68	71	0	30	-38	270
	110	120	-41	-44	-47	-50	-53	-56	-59	390	270
	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270

The **magic** and **semi-magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 100$, $S_{Sm_{6 \times 6}} := 150$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 210$ and $L_{Sm_{12 \times 12}} := 270$. In this case there two magic rectangles with magic sums $MR_{2 \times 6} := 60 \times 180$

Example 4.11. Let's consider a following magic square with *even* number magic sum based on the Result 4.4:

4b	mgc	T=(4/5)*L									330
	-330	48	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	-158	330
	-187	1	78	51	16	13	41	11	53	253	330
	80	65	11	123	-11	17	-5	-101	165	-14	330
	83	28	26	20	23	71	32	267	-203	-17	330
	86	25	5	2	95	38	35	8	56	-20	330
	89	22	98	-5	33	14	38	5	59	-23	330
	92	59	-18	9	44	47	59	2	62	-26	330
	95	107	243	-146	-1	-4	-7	32	40	-29	330
	98	-43	-179	210	65	68	71	40	32	-32	330
	224	18	-35	-38	-41	-44	-47	-50	-53	396	330
	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330

The **magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 140$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 200$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 264$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 330$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (2). Moreover, in this case there are two magic rectangles with magic sums $MR_{2 \times 6} := 64 \times 192$.

Example 4.12. Let's consider a following magic square with *odd* number magic sum based on the Result 4.4:

4c	mgc	T=(4/5)*L									295
	-295	-113	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	-67	295
	-159	1	78	51	16	13	41	-17	53	218	295
	80	65	11	123	-11	17	-5	-129	165	-21	295
	83	28	26	20	23	71	32	323	-287	-24	295
	86	25	5	2	95	38	35	-20	56	-27	295
	89	22	98	-5	33	14	38	-23	59	-30	295
	92	59	-18	9	44	47	59	-26	62	-33	295
	95	79	243	-118	-29	-32	-35	18	110	-36	295
	98	-43	-207	154	65	68	71	110	18	-39	295
	126	172	-42	-45	-48	-51	-54	-57	-60	354	295
	295	295	295	295	295	295	295	295	295	295	295

The **magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 140$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 200$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 236$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 295$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (2). Moreover, in this case there are two magic rectangles with magic sums $MR_{2 \times 6} := 36 \times 108$.

Result 4.5. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

10*T-9*L	27*L-28*T-A40-A39-A38-A36-A35-A34-A32-A33-A30-A31-A27-A28-A29-A26-A37	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A32+A33+A30+A31+A27+A28+A29+A26+18*T-17*L
A26-T	T-S-A23	2*T+3*S+A14-A20-A15	T-S-A20	A24+2*A23-7*T+2*S+A22+A21+2*A20+A16+A17+A19+2*A15+A18	T-S-A21	T-S-A22	T-S-A24	T-A16-A17-A19-A15-A18-A23-A14	L-A26
A27	T-S-A15	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	A15	L-T-A27
A28	T-S-A16	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10+A11+A12-S+M	2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12	A16	L-T-A28
A29	T-S-A17	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	S-M-A11	A11	A17	L-T-A29
A30	T-S-A18	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	S-M-A12	A12	A18	L-T-A30
A31	T-S-A19	S-M-A8	2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M	2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	(5*M-3*S)/2	A19	L-T-A31
A32	T-S-A14	A8	A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S	3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M	A9	(5*M-3*S)/2	(S-M)/2	A14	L-T-A32
A33	A23+A14+7*S+A16+A17+A19+A15+A18-6*T	A20+A15-T-A14-4*S	A20	8*T-A24-2*A23-3*S-A22-A21-2*A20-A16-A17-A19-2*A15-A18	A21	A22	A24	A23	L-T-A33
10*L-9*T-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33	27*T+A40+A39+A38+A36+A35+A34+A32+A33+A30+A31+A27+A28+A29+A26-26*L+A37	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	10*L-11*T

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 10 embedded with *cornered magic square* of order 6. These are *semi-magic* at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need two conditions. These are as follows:

$$T = \frac{4}{5} \times L \quad \text{and} \quad S = \frac{3}{4} \times T, \tag{3}$$

where the letters M, S, T and L represents magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10.

Below are three examples based on the Result 4.5. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (3).

Example 4.13. Let's consider a following semi-magic square based on the Result 4.5:

5a	semi	S=(3/4)*T and T=(4/5)*L									730
	-170	-1015	143	147	151	155	159	163	167	430	330
	-169	-59	1189	-47	-377	-51	-55	-63	-257	219	330
	115	-27	11	101	-11	19	73	47	67	-65	330
	119	-31	31	23	27	39	33	87	71	-69	330
	123	-35	3	-1	71	47	69	51	75	-73	330
	127	-39	75	-3	33	15	65	55	79	-77	330
	131	-43	81	41	41	77	60	-60	83	-81	330
	135	-23	39	79	79	43	-60	60	63	-85	330
	139	537	-1149	87	417	91	95	103	99	-89	330
	-220	1065	-93	-97	-101	-105	-109	-113	-117	220	330
	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330

The magic and semi-magic sums of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 120$, $S_{Sm_{6 \times 6}} := 240$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 280$ and $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} := 330$. In this case the magic rectangles sums is given as $MR_{2 \times 4} := 120 \times 240$.

Example 4.14. Let's consider a following magic square with even number magic sum based on the Result 4.5:

5b	mgc	S=(3/4)*T and T=(4/5)*L									330
	-330	-567	143	147	151	155	159	163	167	142	330
	-153	-33	1031	-21	-349	-25	-29	-37	-273	219	330
	115	-1	11	101	-11	19	31	47	67	-49	330
	119	-5	31	23	27	39	75	3	71	-53	330
	123	-9	3	-1	71	47	27	51	75	-57	330
	127	-13	75	-3	33	15	23	55	79	-61	330
	131	-17	39	-43	125	35	39	3	83	-65	330
	135	3	39	121	-47	43	3	39	63	-69	330
	139	339	-965	87	415	91	95	103	99	-73	330
	-76	633	-77	-81	-85	-89	-93	-97	-101	396	330
	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330

The magic sums of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 120$, $S_{Sm_{6 \times 6}} := 198$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 264$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 330$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (3). Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sum is given as $MR_{2 \times 4} := 78 \times 156$.

Example 4.15. Let's consider a following magic square with *odd* number magic sum based on the Result 4.5:

5c	mgc	S=(3/4)*T and T=(4/5)*L									325
	-325	-590	143	147	151	155	159	163	167	155	325
	-149	-34	1014	-22	-327	-26	-30	-38	-277	214	325
	115	-2	11	102	-11	19	27	47	67	-50	325
	119	-6	31	23	27	40	79	-5	71	-54	325
	123	-10	3	-1	72	47	23	51	75	-58	325
	127	-14	76	-3	33	15	19	55	79	-62	325
	131	-18	35	-50	132	31	37	10	83	-66	325
	135	2	39	124	-58	43	10	37	63	-70	325
	139	342	-949	87	392	91	95	103	99	-74	325
	-90	655	-78	-82	-86	-90	-94	-98	-102	390	325
	325	325	325	325	325	325	325	325	325	325	325

The magic sums of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 121$, $S_{S_{m_6 \times 6}} := 195$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 260$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 325$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (3). Moreover, in this case the magic rectangles sum is given as $MR_{2 \times 4} := 74 \times 148$.

Result 4.6. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$10^*T+A46-9^*L$	$27^*L-2^*A46-28^*T-A45-A44-A43-A41-A40-A39-A37-A38-A35-A36-A32-A33-A34-A31-A42$	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	$A46+A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31+18^*T-17^*L$
A31-T	T-S-A27	$2^*T+3^*S+A17-2^*A14-A24-2^*A13-2^*A8-5^*M-3^*A4-A18-2^*A15$	T-S-A24	$A28+2^*A27+2^*A14-7^*T+2^*S+A26+A25+2^*A24+2^*A13+2^*A8+5^*M+3^*A4+A19+A20+A22+2^*A18+2^*A15+A21$	T-S-A25	T-S-A26	T-S-A28	T-A19-A20-A22-A18-A21-A27-A17	L-A31
A32	T-S-A18	S-M-A15	S-A13-M	$2^*A11-3^*A4-A13-A8+A9+M$	$3^*A4-3^*S+2^*A13+A14+2^*A8+A9-A10+2^*A15+2^*M$	S-A14-M	S-A8-A9-A10-A11-A15	A18	L-T-A32
A33	T-S-A19	S-M-A9	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	A9	A19	L-T-A33
A34	T-S-A20	S-M-A10	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10	A20	L-T-A34
A35	T-S-A21	S-M-A11	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	M-A1-A2-A4	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	A11	A21	L-T-A35
A36	T-S-A22	S-M-A8	M-A1-A2-A3	$A5-A2-2^*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2^*A4-A5-A6$	A2	A8	A22	L-T-A36
A37	T-S-A17	$A8-4^*S+A9+A10+A11+A15+5^*M$	A13	$S-2^*A11+3^*A4+A13+A8-A9-2^*M$	$4^*S+A11-3^*A4-2^*A13-A14-2^*A8-A10-2^*A15-3^*M$	A14	A15	A17	L-T-A37
A38	$A27+A17+7^*S+A19+A20+A22+A18+A21-6^*T$	$A24+2^*A13+2^*A8+5^*M+3^*A4+A18+2^*A15-T-A17+2^*A14-4^*S$	A24	$8^*T-A28-2^*A27-2^*A14-3^*S-A26-A25-2^*A24-2^*A13-2^*A8-5^*M-3^*A4-A19-A20-A22-2^*A18-2^*A15-A21$	A25	A26	A28	A27	L-T-A38
$10^*L-9^*T-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A46$	$27^*T+2^*A46+A45+A44+A43+A41+A40+A39+A37+A38+A35+A36+A32+A33+A34+A31-26^*L+A42$	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	L-T-A41	L-T-A42	L-T-A43	L-T-A44	L-T-A45	10^*L-11^*T-A46

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 10 embedded with magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8. These are *semi-magic* only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need three conditions. These are as follows:

$$T = \frac{4}{5} \times L \quad S = \frac{3}{4} \times T \quad \text{and} \quad M = \frac{3}{4} \times S, \quad (4)$$

where the letters M, S, T and L represents magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10.

Below are three examples based on the Result 4.6. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second and third examples are magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (4), where the magic sum for the second example is **even** number and for the third example is **odd** number.

Example 4.16. Let's consider a following **semi-magic** square based on the Result 4.6:

6a	semi	M=(2/3)*S, S=(3/4)*T and T=(4/5)*L									300
-79	-577	87	89	91	93	95	97	99	225	220	
-109	-13	-132	-7	538	-9	-11	-15	-171	149	220	
73	5	-9	-5	78	94	-7	-21	45	-33	220	
75	3	3	11	85	-11	15	27	47	-35	220	
77	1	1	21	17	19	43	29	49	-37	220	
79	-1	-1	7	5	59	29	31	51	-39	220	
81	-3	5	61	-7	33	13	25	53	-41	220	
83	7	131	35	-48	-64	37	39	43	-43	220	
85	181	182	57	-488	59	61	65	63	-45	220	
-145	617	-47	-49	-51	-53	-55	-57	-59	119	220	
220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	

The **magic** and **semi-magic sums** of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 100$, $S_{Sm_{6 \times 6}} := 130$, $T_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} := 180$ and $L_{Sm_{10 \times 10}} := 220$.

Example 4.17. Let's consider a following **magic square** with **even** number magic sum based on the Result 4.6:

6b	mgc	M=(2/3)*S, S=(3/4)*T and T=(4/5)*L									360
-259	179	87	89	91	93	95	97	99	-211	360	
-217	9	122	15	174	13	11	7	-63	289	360	
73	27	33	37	122	-76	35	65	45	-1	360	
75	25	45	11	129	-11	15	27	47	-3	360	
77	23	43	21	17	19	87	29	49	-5	360	
79	21	41	7	5	103	29	31	51	-7	360	
81	19	47	105	-7	33	13	25	53	-9	360	
83	29	7	35	-50	148	37	39	43	-11	360	
85	135	-50	57	-102	59	61	65	63	-13	360	
283	-107	-15	-17	-19	-21	-23	-25	-27	331	360	
360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	

The magic sums of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 144$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 216$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 288$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 360$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (4).

Example 4.18. Let's consider a following magic square with **odd** number magic sum based on the Result 4.6:

6c	mgc	M=(2/3)*S, S=(3/4)*T and T=(4/5)*L									345
	-244	110	87	89	91	93	95	97	99	-172	345
	-205	6	101	12	210	10	8	4	-75	274	345
	73	24	30	34	116	-61	32	56	45	-4	345
	75	22	42	11	123	-11	15	27	47	-6	345
	77	20	40	21	17	19	81	29	49	-8	345
	79	18	38	7	5	97	29	31	51	-10	345
	81	16	44	99	-7	33	13	25	53	-12	345
	83	26	13	35	-47	130	37	39	43	-14	345
	85	144	-32	57	-141	59	61	65	63	-16	345
	241	-41	-18	-20	-22	-24	-26	-28	-30	313	345
	345	345	345	345	345	345	345	345	345	345	345

The magic sums of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 138$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 207$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 276$ and $L_{10 \times 10} := 345$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (4).

Result 4.7. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

10*T-9*L	27*L-28*T-A49-A48-A47-A45-A44-A43-A41-A42-A39-A40-A36-A37-A38-A35-A46	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	A41+A42+A39+A40+A36+A37+A38+A35+18*T-17*L
A35-T	A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-A4-A7-A11-A15	A4	A7	A11	A15	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23	T-S-A29	A29	L-A35
A36	S-A12-A5-A8-A16-A19	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	T-S-A30	A30	L-T-A36
A37	A4+A7+A11+A15-A20-A21-A22-A23-A1-A2-A3+A5+A8+A12+A16	S-A4-A5-A12+A21+A22+A23-A17-A7-A8-A15-A16-A13-A9-A11+A1+A2+A3	A9	A13	A17	A20	T-S-A31	A31	L-T-A37
A38	A1	S+A16+A13+A6-A19+A3-A1-A18-A14-2*A21-A22-A23-A20	A21+A22+A23+A20-A16-A13-A6+A19-A3	A14	A18	A21	T-S-A32	A32	L-T-A38
A39	A2	A6	S+A16+A13-A9+A6-A19+A3-A10-A21-A22-A23-A20-A7-A8	A5+A14+A10+2*A21+A22+3*A23+2*A20-A4+A8-A15-A16-A13+2*A9-2*A6+2*A19-A11-A2-A3-S	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-2*A23+A4+A7+A11+A15-A5-A9-A14	A22	T-S-A33	A33	L-T-A39
A40	A3	A12+A18+A14+A21+A20+A17+A7+A8+A15+A9-2*A6+A19+A11-A2-2*A3-S	A10	2*S+A4-A8+A15+A16-2*A9+2*A6-2*A19+A2+A3-A12-A5-2*A14-A10-2*A21-A22-3*A23-2*A20	A19+A20+A21+A22+2*A23-A4-A7-A11+A5+A9+A14-2*A15-A16-A17-A18	A23	2*S-2*T+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33	3*T-3*S-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33	L-T-A40
A41	T-S-A25	A30-A29-2*A9+A13-A25+2*S-2*A21-A22-3*A23-A18-2*A19-3*A20-A14+A15+A16-2*A10+A2+A4+A11-A5+2*A6-A8+A3	T-S-A26	T-S-A27	T-S-A28	2*A25+A28+A27+A26-A30+A29+2*A9-A13-T-S+2*A21+A22+3*A23+A18+2*A19+3*A20+A14-A15-A16+2*A10-A2-A4-A11+A5-2*A6+A8-A3	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2	L-T-A41
A42	A25	A29-A30+2*A9-A13+T+A25-A11-3*S+2*A21+A22+3*A23+A18+2*A19+3*A20+A14-A15-A16+2*A10-A2-A4+A5-2*A6+A8-A3	A26	A27	A28	A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-2*A9+A13+2*T-2*A25-2*A21-A22-3*A23-A18-2*A19-3*A20-A14+A15+A16-2*A10+A2+A4+A11-A5+2*A6-A8+A3	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2	L-T-A42
10*L-9*T-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42	27*T+A49+A48+A47+A45+A44+A43+A41+A42+A39+A40+A36+A37+A38+A35-26*L+A46	L-T-A43	L-T-A44	L-T-A45	L-T-A46	L-T-A47	L-T-A48	L-T-A49	10*L-11*T

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 10 embedded with a *cornered magic squares* of orders 8 containing magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner. These are *semi-magic* only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (2). The letters T and L represents magic squares of orders 8 and 10.

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.7. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example is magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (2).

Example 4.19. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 4.7:

7a	semi	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										310	7b	mgc	T=(4/5)*L										275
	-230	-955	143	147	151	155	159	163	167	370	270		-275	-820	143	147	151	155	159	163	167	285	275		
	-109	78	14	17	21	25	-5	31	39	159	270		-109	78	14	17	21	25	-5	31	39	164	275		
	115	40	15	18	22	26	29	30	40	-65	270		115	40	15	18	22	26	29	30	40	-60	275		
	119	-4	55	19	23	27	30	29	41	-69	270		119	-4	55	19	23	27	30	29	41	-64	275		
	123	11	-21	77	24	28	31	28	42	-73	270		123	11	-21	77	24	28	31	28	42	-68	275		
	127	12	16	-1	110	-19	32	27	43	-77	270		127	12	16	-1	110	-19	32	27	43	-72	275		
	131	13	71	20	-50	63	33	65	5	-81	270		131	13	71	20	-50	63	33	65	5	-76	275		
	135	35	-72	34	33	32	148	35	-25	-85	270		135	35	-72	34	33	32	148	35	-25	-80	275		
	139	35	142	36	37	38	-78	-25	35	-89	270		139	35	142	36	37	38	-78	-25	35	-84	275		
	-280	1005	-93	-97	-101	-105	-109	-113	-117	280	270		-230	875	-88	-92	-96	-100	-104	-108	-112	330	275		
	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270		275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275		

The **magic** and **semi-magic sums** of above magic square are

First Example

$M_{6 \times 6} := 150$
 $T_{8 \times 8} := 220$
 $L_{10 \times 10} := 270$

Second Example

$M_{6 \times 6} := 150$
 $T_{8 \times 8} := 220$
 $L_{10 \times 10} := 275.$

The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$MR_{2 \times 6} := 70 \times 210$

Second Example

$MR_{2 \times 6} := 70 \times 210.$

Result 4.8. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

10^*T-9^*L	$27^*L-28^*T-A51-A50-A49-A47-A46-A45-A43-A44-A41-A42-A38-A39-A40-A37-A48$	A45	A46	A47	A48	A49	A50	A51	$A43+A44+A41+A42+A38+A39+A40+A37+18^*T-17^*L$
A37-T	T-S-A28	$2^*T+3^*S+A30-A25-A31$	T-S-A25	$A29+2^*A28-7^*T+2^*S+A27+A26+2^*A25+A32+A33+A35+2^*A31+A34$	T-S-A26	T-S-A27	T-S-A29	T-A32-A33-A35-A31-A34-A28-A30	L-A37
A38	T-S-A31	$A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-A4-A7-A11-A15$	A4	A7	A11	A15	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23	A31	L-T-A38
A39	T-S-A32	S-A12-A5-A8-A16-A19	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	A32	L-T-A39
A40	T-S-A33	$A4+A7+A11+A15-A20-A21-A22-A23-A1-A2-A3+A5+A8+A12+A16$	S-A4-A5-A12+A21+A22+A23-A17-A7-A8-A15-A16-A13-A9-A11+A1+A2+A3	A9	A13	A17	A20	A33	L-T-A40
A41	T-S-A34	A1	S+A16+A13+A6-A19+A3-A1-A18-A14-2^*A21-A22-A23-A20	$A21+A22+A23+A20-A16-A13-A6+A19-A3$	A14	A18	A21	A34	L-T-A41
A42	T-S-A35	A2	A6	$S+A16+A13-A9+A6-A19+A3-A10-A21-A22-A23-A20-A7-A8$	$A5+A14+A10+2^*A21+A22+3^*A23+2^*A20-A4+A8-A15-A16-A13+2^*A9-2^*A6+2^*A19-A11-A2-A3-S$	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-2^*A23+A4+A7+A11+A15-A5-A9-A14	A22	A35	L-T-A42
A43	T-S-A30	A3	$A12+A18+A14+A21+A20+A17+A7+A8+A15+A9-2^*A6+A19+A11-A2-2^*A3-S$	A10	$2^*S+A4-A8+A15+A16-2^*A9+2^*A6-2^*A19+A2+A3-A12-A5-2^*A14-A10-2^*A21-A22-3^*A23-2^*A20$	$A19+A20+A21+A22+2^*A23-A4-A7-A11+A5+A9+A14-2^*A15-A16-A17-A18$	A23	A30	L-T-A43
A44	$A28+A30+7^*S+A32+A33+A35+A31+A34-6^*T$	$A25+A31-T-A30-4^*S$	A25	$8^*T-A29-2^*A28-3^*S-A27-A26-2^*A25-A32-A33-A35-2^*A31-A34$	A26	A27	A29	A28	L-T-A44
$10^*L-9^*T-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44$	$27^*T+A51+A50+A49+A47+A46+A45+A43+A44+A41+A42+A38+A39+A40+A37-26^*L+A48$	L-T-A45	L-T-A46	L-T-A47	L-T-A48	L-T-A49	L-T-A50	L-T-A51	10^*L-11^*T

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 10 embedded with a magic squares of orders 6. It is *semi-magic* only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need two conditions given in (3). The letters S, T and L represents magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10.

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.8. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example is a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (3).

Example 4.20. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 4.8:

8a	semi	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									110	8b	mgc	T=(4/5)*L and S=(3/4)*T									250	
	-430	880	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-586	270		-250	340	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-246	250	
	-153	12	814	15	-586	14	13	11	-93	223	270		-153	12	814	15	-586	14	13	11	-93	203	250	
	48	9	78	14	17	21	25	-5	41	22	270		48	9	78	14	17	21	25	-5	41	2	250	
	49	8	40	15	18	22	26	29	42	21	270		49	8	40	15	18	22	26	29	42	1	250	
	50	7	-4	55	19	23	27	30	43	20	270		50	7	-4	55	19	23	27	30	43	0	250	
	51	6	11	-21	77	24	28	31	44	19	270		51	6	11	-21	77	24	28	31	44	-1	250	
	52	5	12	16	-1	110	-19	32	45	18	270		52	5	12	16	-1	110	-19	32	45	-2	250	
	53	10	13	71	20	-50	63	33	40	17	270		53	10	13	71	20	-50	63	33	40	-3	250	
	54	143	-764	35	636	36	37	39	38	16	270		54	143	-764	35	636	36	37	39	38	-4	250	
	496	-810	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	500	270		296	-290	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	300	250	
	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270		250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

The **magic** and **semi-magic sums** of above magic square are

First Example

$$M_{6 \times 6} := 150$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 200$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 270$$

Second Example

$$M_{6 \times 6} := 150$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 200$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 250.$$

Result 4.9. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

10^*T-9^*L	$27^*L-28^*T-A28-A27-A26-A24-A23-A22-A20-A21-A18-A19-A15-A16-A17-A14-A25$	A22	A23	A24	A25	A26	A27	A28	$A20+A21+A18+A19+A15+A16+A17+A14+18^*T-17^*L$
A14-T	$A1-A3-A5-A6-A8+A7$	$A6+A8-2^*m+A11+A1-A3-A5$	2^*m	$2^*m+2^*A3+2^*A5-A7-A11-2^*A1$	$A5+2^*A3-A7-A11+A10-A9$	$2^*m-A9-A5-A10$	$A9-2^*A3+A7+A11$	A9	L-A14
A15	$m+A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-A1$	$3^*m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11-A1$	(-m)	$A7-m+A11+2^*A1-2^*A3-2^*A5$	$m+A9-A10+A11-A5-2^*A3+A7$	$A9+A5+A10-m$	$m-A9+2^*A3-A7-A11$	m-A9	L-T-A15
A16	$2^*A3+2^*A5-A7-A11-A1$	A1	$A6+A8+A11-A3-A5$	$2^*m+A7-A3-A5-A6-A8$	$A5+2^*A3-A7-A11$	A5	$2^*m+A7+A11-A10-2^*A3-2^*A5$	A10	L-T-A16
A17	$A1+m-2^*A3-2^*A5+A7+A11$	m-A1	$m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11$	$A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-m$	$m+A7+A11-A5-2^*A3$	m-A5	$2^*A3+2^*A5-A7-A11+A10-m$	m-A10	L-T-A17
A18	$A3+A2-A7-A11+A4$	$2^*m-A3-A2-A4$	$A7+A11-A3$	A3	$2^*m-A6-A8-A11$	$A6+A8-A7$	A7	A11	L-T-A18
A19	$m+A7+A11-A4-A3-A2$	$A3+A2+A4-m$	$m+A3-A7-A11$	m-A3	$A6+A8+A11-m$	$m+A7-A6-A8$	m-A7	m-A11	L-T-A19
A20	$A2+2^*A3-A7-A11$	A2	$2^*m+A7+A11-2^*A2-A4-2^*A3$	A4	$A6+A11-A7$	A6	A8	$2^*m+A7-2^*A6-A8-A11$	L-T-A20
A21	$m+A7+A11-A2-2^*A3$	m-A2	$2^*A3-A7-A11+2^*A2+A4-m$	m-A4	$m+A7-A11-A6$	m-A6	m-A8	$2^*A6+A8+A11-A7-m$	L-T-A21
$10^*L-9^*T-A14-A15-A16-A17-A18-A19-A20-A21$	$27^*T+A28+A27+A26+A24+A23+A22+A20+A21+A18+A19+A15+A16+A17+A14-26^*L+A25$	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	L-T-A27	L-T-A28	10^*L-11^*T

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic* square of order 10 embedded with a *striped* magic square of order 8. It is *semi-magic* only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (2). The letters T and L represents magic squares of orders 8 and 10.

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.9. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example is a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (2).

Example 4.21. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 4.9:

9a	semi	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									60
	-380	995	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	-640	220
	-136	-34	-42	80	76	4	26	31	19	196	220
	25	74	82	-40	-36	36	14	9	21	35	220
	26	7	11	27	35	3	15	42	20	34	220
	27	33	29	13	5	37	25	-2	20	33	220
	28	1	41	25	13	25	17	17	21	32	220
	29	39	-1	15	27	15	23	23	19	31	220
	30	0	12	54	14	20	16	18	26	30	220
	31	40	28	-14	26	20	24	22	14	29	220
	540	-935	28	27	26	25	24	23	22	440	220
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

9b	mgc	T=(4/5)*L									200
	-200	455	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	-300	200
	-136	-34	-42	80	76	4	26	31	19	176	200
	25	74	82	-40	-36	36	14	9	21	15	200
	26	7	11	27	35	3	15	42	20	14	200
	27	33	29	13	5	37	25	-2	20	13	200
	28	1	41	25	13	25	17	17	21	12	200
	29	39	-1	15	27	15	23	23	19	11	200
	30	0	12	54	14	20	16	18	26	10	200
	31	40	28	-14	26	20	24	22	14	9	200
	340	-415	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	240	200
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

The **magic** and **semi-magic sums** of above magic square are

First Example

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 160$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 220$$

Second Example

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 160$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 200.$$

In both the examples the magic sums of 8 magic rectangles appearing magic square of order 8 are of equal sums, i.e., 40×80 .

Result 4.10. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:

$10*2*S+A35-9*L$	$27*L-2*A35-28*2*S-A34-A33-A32-A30-A29-A28-A26-A27-A24-A25-A21-A22-A23-A20-A31$	A28	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	$A35+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20+18*2*S-17*L$
A20-2*S	$2*S-2*A4-2*A7-A12+A3+A6$	$3*A4+3*A7-A15-A2+A12-A3-A6-2*S$	$A2+A14-A16-4*A4-4*A7+A3+A6-A1+4*S+A15$	$A16+3*A4-3*S+3*A7-A3-A6+A1-A14$	A3	$2*S-A9-A4-A7-A5-A3$	$A5+A8-A16+A3+A6-A1+A9$	$A16+A4+A7-A3-A6+A1-A8-S$	L-A20
A21	A2	$A4+A7-A15-S$	A1	$2*S-A4-A7+A15-A1-A2$	A5	$S-A9-A4-A7$	$A16+2*A4-2*S+2*A7+A1-A10$	$A9-A4-A7+2*S-A16-A1+A10-A5$	$L-2*S-A21$
A22	$2*A4+2*A7-A13-S-A14+A16-A3-A6+A1-A2$	$4*S-3*A4-3*A7-A12+A3+A6-A13-A1$	$2*A4+2*A7+A1-2-A3-A6+A13+A15-2*S$	$A2+A13+A14-A16-A4-A7+A3+A6-A15$	$2*A4-S-A8+A16+A7-A3-A6+A1-A5$	$A3-A4+2*S-A16-2*A7-A1+A10$	$A9+A7-A3$	$A8+A3+A6-A10+A5-A9-A4$	$L-2*S-A22$
A23	$A12+A13+A14-A16-A1$	$A1-A4-A7+A13+2*A15+A2$	$2*A4+2*A7-A12-A13-A14-S+A16-2*A15-A2$	$2*S-A4-A7-A13$	$2*S-2*A4+A8-A16-A7+A6-A1$	$A16+3*A4-4*S+4*A7+A1+2*A9+A5-A10$	$3*S-A8-3*A7-A6-2*A9+A10-A5-2*A4$	A4	$L-2*S-A23$
A24	A6	$A9+S-A11-A6$	$A11-A8-A9$	A8	A12	$A15+S-A17-A12$	$A17-A14-A15$	A14	$L-2*S-A24$
A25	A11	A9	A10	$S-A9-A10-A11$	A17	A15	A16	$S-A15-A16-A17$	$L-2*S-A25$
A26	$A7+A8-A11$	$A6+A7-A10$	$S-A6-A7-A9$	$A9+A10+A11-A7-A8$	$A13+A14-A17$	$A12+A13-A16$	$S-A12-A13-A15$	$A15+A16+A17-A13-A14$	$L-2*S-A26$
A27	$S-A6-A7-A8$	$A10-A7-2*A9+A11$	$A6+A7+A8+2*A9-A10-A11$	A7	$S-A12-A13-A14$	$A16-A13-2*A15+A17$	$A12+A13+A14+2*A15-A16-A17$	A13	$L-2*S-A27$
$10*L-9*2*S-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A35$	$27*2*S+2*A35+A34+A33+A32+A30+A29+A28+A26+A27+A24+A25+A21+A22+A23+A20-26*L+A31$	$L-2*S-A28$	$L-2*S-A29$	$L-2*S-A30$	$L-2*S-A31$	$L-2*S-A32$	$L-2*S-A33$	$L-2*S-A34$	$10*L-11*2*S-A35$

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic* square of order 10 embedded with a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 8 divided in four equal sums magic squares of order 4. It is *semi-magic* only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (2). The letters T and L represents magic squares of orders 8 and 10.

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.10. First example is of *semi-magic* squares and the second example is a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (2).

Example 4.22. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 4.11:

10a	semi	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									230	10b	mgc	T=(4/5)*L									300	
	-345	1005	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	-637	310		-255	735	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	-467	300	
	-210	185	-191	409	-283	13	162	44	-99	280	310		-210	185	-191	409	-283	13	162	44	-99	270	300	
	31	12	-114	11	211	15	70	-161	196	39	310		31	12	-114	11	211	15	70	-161	196	29	300	
	32	-109	360	-137	6	-100	188	23	9	38	310		32	-109	360	-137	6	-100	188	23	9	28	300	
	33	32	65	-163	186	192	-300	214	14	37	310		33	32	65	-163	186	192	-300	214	14	27	300	
	34	16	102	-16	18	22	96	-22	24	36	310		34	16	102	-16	18	22	96	-22	24	26	300	
	35	21	19	20	60	27	25	26	42	35	310		35	21	19	20	60	27	25	26	42	25	300	
	36	14	13	68	25	20	19	50	31	34	310		36	14	13	68	25	20	19	50	31	24	300	
	37	69	-14	48	17	51	-20	66	23	33	310		37	69	-14	48	17	51	-20	66	23	23	300	
	627	-935	32	31	30	29	28	27	26	415	310		527	-675	22	21	20	19	18	17	16	315	300	
	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310	310		300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

Result 4.11. *Let's consider following self-made magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:*

$10*T+A39-9*L$	$27*L-2*A39-28*T-A38-A37-A36-A34-A33-A32-A30-A31-A28-A29-A25-A26-A27-A24-A35$	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	$A30+A31+A39+A28+A29+A25+A26+A27+A24+18*T-17*L$
A24-T	A1	M-A1-A2	A2	$4*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-2*A5-2*A4-A6$	$A5+2*A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	A5	T-2*M-A19	A19	L-A24
A25	$A1+A2+2*A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	$3*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-A1-A3$	M-A2-A3	$2*A5+A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	$3*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-A5-A4$	M-A5-A6	T-2*M-A20	A20	L-T-A25
A26	$4*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-2*A1-A2-2*A3$	$2*A1+A2+A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	A3	A4	M-A4-A6	A6	T-2*M-A21	A21	L-T-A26
A27	A7	M-A7-A9	A9	A11	M-A11-A13	A13	T-2*M-A22	A22	L-T-A27
A28	M-A7-A8	$A7+A8+A9+A10-M$	M-A9-A10	M-A11-A12	$A11+A12+A13+A14-M$	M-A13-A14	T-2*M-A23	A23	L-T-A28
A29	A8	M-A8-A10	A10	A12	M-A12-A14	A14	$2*2*M-2*T+A19+A20+A21+A22+A23$	$3*T-3*2*M-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23$	L-T-A29
A30	$2*T-4*M+A19-A20+A6-2*A11-A13-A12-A15+A10$	T-2*M-A15	T-2*M-A16	T-2*M-A17	T-2*M-A18	$6*M-A10-A19+A20-A6+2*A11+A13+A12+2*A15+A16+A17+A18-3*T$	$(T-2*M)/2$	$(7*2*M-5*T)/2$	L-T-A30
A31	$2*M+A20-A6+2*A11+A13+A12+A15-A10-A19-T$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$A10+A19+4*T-8*M-A20+A6-2*A11-A13-A12-2*A15-A16-A17-A18$	$(7*2*M-5*T)/2$	$(T-2*M)/2$	L-T-A31
$10*L-9*T-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A39$	$27*T+2*A39+A38+A37+A36+A34+A33+A32+A30+A31+A28+A29+A25+A26+A27+A24-26*L+A35$	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	$10*L-11*T-A39$

Details:

It is a single-digit bordered semi-magic square of order 10 embedded with a cornered magic square of order 8. It contains magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner. This magic square of order 6 is composed of four equal sums semi-magic squares of order 3. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (2). The letters L, T, S and M represents magic squares of orders 10, 8, 6 and 3.

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.11. First example is of semi-magic squares and the second example is a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (2).

Example 4.23. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 4.10:

10	semi	T=(4/5)*L									210	10	mgc	T=(4/5)*L									180
	-6	-1078	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	470	170		-56	-920	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	372	180
	-61	10	38	13	-58	97	22	-46	64	91	170		-65	10	27	13	-102	130	22	-20	64	101	180
	82	139	-110	32	100	-53	14	-49	67	-52	170		82	172	-143	21	133	-86	3	-23	67	-46	180
	85	-88	133	16	19	17	25	-52	70	-55	170		85	-132	166	16	19	6	25	-26	70	-49	180
	88	28	-1	34	40	-25	46	-55	73	-58	170		88	28	-12	34	40	-36	46	-29	73	-52	180
	91	2	69	-10	-22	117	-34	-58	76	-61	170		91	-9	80	-21	-33	128	-45	-32	76	-55	180
	94	31	-7	37	43	-31	49	314	-296	-64	170		94	31	-18	37	43	-42	49	262	-218	-58	180
	97	-126	-34	-37	-40	-43	334	9	77	-67	170		97	-74	-8	-11	-14	-17	256	22	-10	-61	180
	100	144	52	55	58	61	-316	77	9	-70	170		100	118	52	55	58	61	-212	-10	22	-64	180
	-400	1108	-73	-76	-79	-82	-85	-88	-91	36	170		-336	956	-67	-70	-73	-76	-79	-82	-85	92	180
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above magic square are

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 61(\text{semi} - \text{magic})$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 122$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 140$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 170(\text{semi} - \text{magic})$$

Second Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 50(\text{semi} - \text{magic})$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 100$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 144$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 180.$$

Result 4.12. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:

$10^*T+A38-9^*L$	$27^*L-2^*A38-28^*T-A37-A36-A35-A33-A32-A31-A29-A30-A27-A28-A24-A25-A26-A23-A34$	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	$A29+A30+A38+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23+18^*T-17^*L$
A23-T	$A1-A6+A7-A12+A13$	A1	$3^*m-2^*A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A7+A12-A13$	A2	A3	A4	$T-3^*m-A18$	A18	L-A23
A24	$m+A6-A7+A12-A13-A1$	m-A1	$2^*A1+A2+A3+A4-A6+A7-A12+A13-2^*m$	m-A2	m-A3	m-A4	$T-3^*m-A19$	A19	L-T-A24
A25	A5	$3^*m-A5-A6-A7-A8-A9$	A6	A7	A8	A9	$T-3^*m-A20$	A20	L-T-A25
A26	m-A5	$A5+A6+A7+A8+A9-2^*m$	m-A6	m-A7	m-A8	m-A9	$T-3^*m-A21$	A21	L-T-A26
A27	$A4+A7-A6+A10-A3$	A10	$3^*m-A4-A7+A6-2^*A10+A3-A11-A12-A13$	A11	A12	A13	$T-3^*m-A22$	A22	L-T-A27
A28	$m-A4-A7+A6-A10+A3$	m-A10	$A4+A7-A6+2^*A10-A3+A11+A12+A13-2^*m$	m-A11	m-A12	m-A13	$2^*3^*m-2^*T+A18+A19+A20+A21+A22$	$3^*T-3^*3^*m-A18-A19-A20-A21-A22$	L-T-A28
A29	$2^*T-10^*m+A18-A19+A9-A8+2^*A11+A4+A7-A6+2^*A10-A3+A13-A14+A12$	$T-3^*m-A14$	$T-3^*m-A15$	$T-3^*m-A16$	$T-3^*m-A17$	$13^*m-A12-A18+A19-A9+A8-2^*A11-A4-A7+A6-2^*A10+A3-A13+2^*A14+A15+A16+A17-3^*T$	$(T-3^*m)/2$	$(7^*3^*m-5^*T)/2$	L-T-A29
A30	$7^*m+A19-A9+A8-2^*A11-A4-A7+A6-2^*A10+A3-A13+A14-A12-A18-T$	A14	A15	A16	A17	$A12+A18+4^*T-16^*m-A19+A9-A8+2^*A11+A4+A7-A6+2^*A10-A3+A13-2^*A14-A15-A16-A17$	$(7^*3^*m-5^*T)/2$	$(T-3^*m)/2$	L-T-A30
$10^*L-9^*T-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A38$	$27^*T+2^*A38+A37+A36+A35+A33+A32+A31+A29+A30+A27+A28+A24+A25+A26+A23-26^*L+A34$	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	10^*L-11^*T-A38

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic square* of order 10 embedded with a *cornered magic square* of order 8. It contains magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner. This magic square of order 6 is composed of three magic rectangles of order 2×6 of equal sums. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (2). The letters L, T and S represents magic squares of orders 10, 8 and 6. The letter m represents the width of magic rectangle of order $m \times 3m$

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.12. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example is a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (2).

Example 4.24. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 4.12:

10	semi	T=(4/5)*L									140	10	mgc	T=(4/5)*L									160
	-99	-757	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	273	180		-39	-961	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	397	160
	-64	16	10	52	13	16	19	-47	61	104	180		-52	16	10	22	13	16	19	-29	61	84	160
	79	26	32	-10	29	26	23	-50	64	-39	180		79	16	22	10	19	16	13	-32	64	-47	160
	82	22	-14	25	28	31	34	-53	67	-42	180		82	22	-44	25	28	31	34	-35	67	-50	160
	85	20	56	17	14	11	8	-56	70	-45	180		85	10	76	7	4	1	-2	-38	70	-53	160
	88	43	37	-83	40	43	46	-59	73	-48	180		88	43	37	-113	40	43	46	-41	73	-56	160
	91	-1	5	125	2	-1	-4	307	-293	-51	180		91	-11	-5	145	-8	-11	-14	271	-239	-59	160
	94	60	-35	-38	-41	-44	140	7	91	-54	180		94	136	-17	-20	-23	-26	46	16	16	-62	160
	97	-46	49	52	55	58	-126	91	7	-57	180		97	-104	49	52	55	58	-14	16	16	-65	160
	-273	797	-60	-63	-66	-69	-72	-75	-78	139	180		-365	993	-68	-71	-74	-77	-80	-83	-86	71	160
	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180		160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above magic square and magic rectangles are given by

First Example

$T_{6 \times 6} := 126$
 $T_{8 \times 8} := 140$
 $L_{10 \times 10} := 180(\text{semi} - \text{magic})$
 $m \times 3m := 42 \times 126$

Second Example

$T_{6 \times 6} := 96$
 $T_{8 \times 8} := 128$
 $L_{10 \times 10} := 160$
 $m \times 3m := 32 \times 96.$

Result 4.13. Let's consider following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:

$10^*T+A41-9^*L$	$27^*L-2^*A41-28^*T-A40-A39-A38-A36-A35-A34-A32-A33-A30-A31-A27-A28-A29-A26-A37$	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	$A32+A33+A41+A30+A31+A27+A28+A29+A26+18^*T-17^*L$
A26-T	$T-2^*M-A23$	$2^*T+3^*2^*M+A25-A20-A15$	$T-2^*M-A20$	$A24+2^*A23-7^*T+2^*2^*M+A22+A21+2^*A20+A16+A17+A19+2^*A15+A18$	$T-2^*M-A21$	$T-2^*M-A22$	$T-2^*M-A24$	$T-A16-A17-A19-A15-A18-A23-A25$	L-A26
A27	$T-2^*M-A15$	A1	M-A1-A2	A2	$4^*M-2^*A9-A7-2^*A8-A10-2^*A5-2^*A4-A6$	$A5+2^*A4+A6+2^*A9+A7+2^*A8+A10-3^*M$	A5	A15	L-T-A27
A28	$T-2^*M-A16$	$A1+A2+2^*A3+2^*A11+A12+A13+2^*A14-3^*M$	$3^*M-2^*A11-A12-A13-2^*A14-A1-A3$	M-A2-A3	$2^*A5+A4+A6+2^*A9+A7+2^*A8+A10-3^*M$	$3^*M-2^*A9-A7-2^*A8-A10-A5-A4$	M-A5-A6	A16	L-T-A28
A29	$T-2^*M-A17$	$4^*M-2^*A11-A12-A13-2^*A14-2^*A1-A2-2^*A3$	$2^*A1+A2+A3+2^*A11+A12+A13+2^*A14-3^*M$	A3	A4	M-A4-A6	A6	A17	L-T-A29
A30	$T-2^*M-A18$	A7	M-A7-A9	A9	A11	M-A11-A13	A13	A18	L-T-A30
A31	$T-2^*M-A19$	M-A7-A8	$A7+A8+A9+A10-M$	M-A9-A10	M-A11-A12	$A11+A12+A13+A14-M$	M-A13-A14	A19	L-T-A31
A32	$T-2^*M-A25$	A8	M-A8-A10	A10	A12	M-A12-A14	A14	A25	L-T-A32
A33	$A23+A25+7^*2^*M+A16+A17+A19+A15+A18-6^*T$	$A20+A15-T-A25-4^*2^*M$	A20	$8^*T-A24-2^*A23-3^*2^*M-A22-A21-2^*A20-A16-A17-A19-2^*A15-A18$	A21	A22	A24	A23	L-T-A33
$10^*L-9^*T-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A41$	$27^*T+2^*A41+A40+A39+A38+A36+A35+A34+A32+A33+A30+A31+A27+A28+A29+A26-26^*L+A37$	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	10^*L-11^*T-A41

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic* square of order 10 and 8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is composed of four equal sums *semi-magic* squares of order 3. In order to bring it as a magic square we need two conditions given in (2) and (3). The letters L, T, S and M represents magic squares of orders 10, 8, 6 and 3.

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.13. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example is a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (2) and (3).

Example 4.25. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 4.13:

10 semi	S=(3/4)*T and T=(4/5)*L										114	10 mgc	S=(3/4)*T and T=(4/5)*L										300
-100	-756	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	280	250	-170	-470	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	114	300		
-117	-6	763	3	-300	0	-3	-9	-246	165	250	-155	-16	983	-7	-470	-10	-13	-19	-208	215	300		
88	18	10	43	13	-38	82	22	52	-40	250	88	8	10	67	13	58	10	22	52	-28	300		
91	15	124	-95	37	85	-38	19	55	-43	250	91	5	52	-23	61	13	34	43	55	-31	300		
94	12	-68	118	16	19	22	25	58	-46	250	94	2	28	46	16	19	46	25	58	-34	300		
97	9	28	4	34	40	-20	46	61	-49	250	97	-1	28	28	34	40	4	46	61	-37	300		
100	6	7	64	-5	-17	112	-29	64	-52	250	100	-4	31	40	19	7	88	-5	64	-40	300		
103	-12	31	-2	37	43	-26	49	82	-55	250	103	-22	31	22	37	43	-2	49	82	-43	300		
106	160	-693	67	370	70	73	79	76	-58	250	106	268	-923	67	530	70	73	79	76	-46	300		
-212	804	-61	-64	-67	-70	-73	-76	-79	148	250	-54	530	-49	-52	-55	-58	-61	-64	-67	230	300		
250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300		

The **magic** and **semi-magic sums** of above magic squares are given by

First Example

$$M_{3 \times 3} := 66(\text{semi} - \text{magic})$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 132$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 202$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 250(\text{semi} - \text{magic})$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 90$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 180$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 240$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 300.$$

Result 4.14. *Let's consider following self-made magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:*

$10*T+A40-9*L$	$27*L-2*A40-28*T-A39-A38-A37-A35-A34-A33-A31-A32-A29-A30-A26-A27-A28-A25-A36$	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	$A31+A32+A40+A29+A30+A26+A27+A28+A25+18*T-17*L$
A25-T	$T-3*m-A23$	$2*T+3*3*m+A14-A20-A15$	$T-3*m-A20$	$A24+2*A23-7*T+2*3*m+A22+A21+2*A20+A16+A17+A19+2*A15+A18$	$T-3*m-A21$	$T-3*m-A22$	$T-3*m-A24$	$T-A16-A17-A19-A15-A18-A23-A14$	L-A25
A26	$T-3*m-A15$	$A1-A6+A7-A12+A13$	A1	$3*m-2*A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A7+A12-A13$	A2	A3	A4	A15	L-T-A26
A27	$T-3*m-A16$	$m+A6-A7+A12-A13-A1$	m-A1	$2*A1+A2+A3+A4-A6+A7-A12+A13-2*m$	m-A2	m-A3	m-A4	A16	L-T-A27
A28	$T-3*m-A17$	A5	$3*m-A5-A6-A7-A8-A9$	A6	A7	A8	A9	A17	L-T-A28
A29	$T-3*m-A18$	m-A5	$A5+A6+A7+A8+A9-2*m$	m-A6	m-A7	m-A8	m-A9	A18	L-T-A29
A30	$T-3*m-A19$	$A4+A7-A6+A10-A3$	A10	$3*m-A4-A7+A6-2*A10+A3-A11-A12-A13$	A11	A12	A13	A19	L-T-A30
A31	$T-3*m-A14$	$m-A4-A7+A6-A10+A3$	m-A10	$A4+A7-A6+2*A10-A3+A11+A12+A13-2*m$	m-A11	m-A12	m-A13	A14	L-T-A31
A32	$A23+A14+7*3*m+A16+A17+A19+A15+A18-6*T$	$A20+A15-T-A14-4*3*m$	A20	$8*T-A24-2*A23-3*3*m-A22-A21-2*A20-A16-A17-A19-2*A15-A18$	A21	A22	A24	A23	L-T-A32
$10*L-9*T-A25-A26-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32-A40$	$27*T+2*A40+A39+A38+A37+A35+A34+A33+A31+A32+A29+A30+A26+A27+A28+A25-26*L+A36$	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	L-T-A35	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	$10*L-11*T-A40$

Details:

*It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 10 and 8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is composed of three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 . In order to bring it as a magic square we need two conditions given in (2) and (3). The letters L, T and S represents magic squares of orders 10, 8 and 6. The letter m represents the width of magic rectangle of order $m \times 3m$*

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.14. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example is a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (2) and (3).

Example 4.26. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 4.14:

10	semi	S=(3/4)*T and T=(4/5)*L										-72	10	mgc	S=(3/4)*T and T=(4/5)*L										275
	-81	-401	75	77	79	81	83	85	87	135	220			-186	-8	75	77	79	81	83	85	87	-98	275	
	-122	33	590	39	-458	37	35	31	-126	161	220			-161	0	884	6	-587	4	2	-2	-87	216	275	
	61	49	15	11	22	13	15	17	39	-22	220			61	16	15	11	94	13	15	17	39	-6	275	
	63	47	16	20	9	18	16	14	41	-24	220			63	14	40	44	-39	42	40	38	41	-8	275	
	65	45	19	-22	21	23	25	27	43	-26	220			65	12	19	50	21	23	25	27	43	-10	275	
	67	43	12	53	10	8	6	4	45	-28	220			67	10	36	5	34	32	30	28	45	-12	275	
	69	41	33	29	-68	31	33	35	47	-30	220			69	8	33	29	4	31	33	35	47	-14	275	
	71	51	-2	2	99	0	-2	-4	37	-32	220			71	18	22	26	51	24	22	20	37	-16	275	
	73	-128	-502	49	546	51	53	57	55	-34	220			73	142	-829	49	642	51	53	57	55	-18	275	
	-46	440	-36	-38	-40	-42	-44	-46	-48	120	220			153	63	-20	-22	-24	-26	-28	-30	-32	241	275	
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220			275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above magic square and magic rectangles are given by

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 93$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 181$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 220$$

$$m \times 3m := 31 \times 93$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 165$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 220$$

$$L_{10 \times 10} := 275$$

$$m \times 3m := 55 \times 165$$

5 Self-Made Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 10

This section brings 29 pandiagonal self-made magic squares of order 10. By self-made we understand that these are complete in themselves. Just put the values of variables and choose the magic sum, we get the magic square. Since, we are working here with **pandiagonal** magic squares, it requires some conditions to avoid decimal or fractional entries. Most the results are based on the Sections 4 and 5. Some results are new.

5.1 Four Blocks of Order 5

Result 5.1. *Let's consider following self-made magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:*

$A7-A23+A15$	$A1$	$S-A7+A23-A15-A1-A2-A3$	$A2$	$A3$	$A7$	$A8$	$S-A7-A8-A9-A10$	$A9$	$A10$
$A21-A28+A13-A1+A6$	$A4$	$A7-A23+A15+A1+A2+A3-A4-A5-A21+A28-A13$	$A5$	$S-A7+A23-A15-A2-A3-A6$	$A14-A8+A13$	$A11$	$A7+A8+A9+A10-A11-A12-A13$	$A12$	$S-A7-A9-A10-A14$
$A1+A2+A3-A4-A21+A28-A13$	$S-A7+A23-A15-A1-A2-A3+A5-A6$	$A21-A28+A13$	$A21-A28+A13-A1-A2+A4+A6$	$A7-A23+A15+A1+A2-A5-A21+A28-A13$	$A8+A9+A10-A11-A13$	$S-A7-A8-A9-A10+A12-A14$	$A13$	$A13-A8-A9+A11+A14$	$A7+A8+A9-A12-A13$
$A21-A28+A13-A2+A4$	$A7-A23+A15-A5+A6$	$A1+A2-A21+A28-A13$	$S-A7+A23-A15-A4-A6-A21+A28-A13$	$A21-A28+A13-A1+A5$	$A13-A9+A11$	$A7-A12+A14$	$A8+A9-A13$	$S-A7-A11-A13-A14$	$A13-A8+A12$
$S-A7+A23-A15-A3-A6-A21+A28-A13$	$A2+A3-A4$	$A21-A28+A13-A1-A2+A4+A5$	$A7-A23+A15+A1-A5$	$A6$	$S-A7-A10-A13-A14$	$A9+A10-A11$	$A13-A8-A9+A11+A12$	$A7+A8-A12$	$A14$
$A15$	$A16$	$S-A15-A16-A17-A18$	$A17$	$A18$	$A23$	$A24$	$S-A23-A24-A25+A3-A18-A10$	$A25$	$A18+A10-A3$
$A22-A16+A21$	$A19$	$A15+A16+A17+A18-A19-A20-A21$	$A20$	$S-A15-A17-A18-A22$	$A22+A14-A6-A24+A28$	$A26$	$A23+A24+A25-A3+A18+A10-A26-A27-A28$	$A27$	$S-A23-A25+A3-A18-A10-A22-A14+A6$
$A16+A17+A18-A19-A21$	$S-A15-A16-A17-A18+A20-A22$	$A21$	$A21-A16-A17+A19+A22$	$A15+A16+A17-A20-A21$	$A24+A25-A3+A18+A10-A26-A28$	$S-A23-A24-A25+A3-A18-A10+A27-A22-A14+A6$	$A28$	$A28-A24-A25+A26+A22+A14-A6$	$A23+A24+A25-A27-A28$
$A21-A17+A19$	$A15-A20+A22$	$A16+A17-A21$	$S-A15-A19-A21-A22$	$A21-A16+A20$	$A28-A25+A26$	$A23-A27+A22+A14-A6$	$A24+A25-A28$	$S-A23-A26-A28-A22-A14+A6$	$A28-A24+A27$
$S-A15-A18-A21-A22$	$A17+A18-A19$	$A21-A16-A17+A19+A20$	$A15+A16-A20$	$A22$	$S-A23+A3-A18-A10-A28-A22-A14+A6$	$A25-A3+A18+A10-A26$	$A28-A24-A25+A26+A27$	$A23+A24-A27$	$A22+A14-A6$

Details:

It a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 10 divided in four equal sums blocks of order 5. These blocks are also **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5. The magic sum of order 10 is represented by letter $T = 2S$, where S is the sum of magic square of order 5. In this case we always have *even* number magic sums of order 10.

There are no conditions on the magic sum of order 5 to bring this **pandiagonal** magic square of order 10. See below two examples:

Example 5.1. Let's consider the following two examples:

10x10	pan	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	10x10	pan	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	
180	9	11	45	12	13	17	18	16	19	20	180	150	9	11	30	12	13	17	18	1	19	20	150
180	21	14	0	15	40	29	21	8	22	10	180	150	21	14	0	15	25	29	21	8	22	-5	150
180	6	44	16	23	1	13	14	23	31	9	180	150	6	29	16	23	1	13	-1	23	31	9	150
180	18	10	7	35	20	25	19	14	5	27	180	150	18	10	7	20	20	25	19	14	-10	27	150
180	36	11	22	5	16	6	18	29	13	24	180	150	21	11	22	5	16	-9	18	29	13	24	150
180	25	26	-16	27	28	33	34	-47	35	35	180	150	25	26	-31	27	28	33	34	-62	35	35	150
180	37	29	16	30	-22	44	36	26	37	-53	180	150	37	29	16	30	-37	44	36	26	37	-68	150
180	21	-18	31	39	17	30	-50	38	45	27	180	150	21	-33	31	39	17	30	-65	38	45	27	150
180	33	27	22	-27	35	39	36	31	-57	41	180	150	33	27	22	-42	35	39	36	31	-72	41	150
	-26	26	37	21	32	-56	34	42	30	40	180		-41	26	37	21	32	-71	34	42	30	40	150
©IJT	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	©IJT	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

These are two examples of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 10 based on the Result 5.1. The magic sums of the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 180$ and $S_{5 \times 5} := 90$. For the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 150$ and $S_{5 \times 5} := 75$ The four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 for each example are given by

	pan	90	90	90	90	90		pan	90	90	90	90	90		pan	75	75	75	75	75		pan	75	75	75	75	75	
90	9	11	45	12	13	90	90	17	18	16	19	20	90	75	9	11	30	12	13	75	75	17	18	1	19	20	75	
90	21	14	0	15	40	90	90	29	21	8	22	10	90	75	21	14	0	15	25	75	75	29	21	8	22	-5	75	
90	6	44	16	23	1	90	90	13	14	23	31	9	90	75	6	29	16	23	1	75	75	13	-1	23	31	9	75	
90	18	10	7	35	20	90	90	25	19	14	5	27	90	75	18	10	7	20	20	75	75	25	19	14	-10	27	75	
	36	11	22	5	16	90		6	18	29	13	24	90		21	11	22	5	16	75		-9	18	29	13	24	75	
	90	90	90	90	90	90		90	90	90	90	90	90		75	75	75	75	75	75		75	75	75	75	75	75	75
	pan	90	90	90	90	90		pan	90	90	90	90	90		pan	75	75	75	75	75		pan	75	75	75	75	75	
90	25	26	-16	27	28	90	90	33	34	-47	35	35	90	75	25	26	-31	27	28	75	75	33	34	-62	35	35	75	
90	37	29	16	30	-22	90	90	44	36	26	37	-53	90	75	37	29	16	30	-37	75	75	44	36	26	37	-68	75	
90	21	-18	31	39	17	90	90	30	-50	38	45	27	90	75	21	-33	31	39	17	75	75	30	-65	38	45	27	75	
90	33	27	22	-27	35	90	90	39	36	31	-57	41	90	75	33	27	22	-42	35	75	75	39	36	31	-72	41	75	
	-26	26	37	21	32	90		-56	34	42	30	40	90		-41	26	37	21	32	75		-71	34	42	30	40	75	
	90	90	90	90	90	90		90	90	90	90	90	90		75	75	75	75	75	75		75	75	75	75	75	75	75

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 5 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

5.2 Double-Digit Bordered Magic Squares

Result 5.2. *Let's consider the following self-made magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:*

$(2/3)*S-A29-A18-A14$	$(2/3)*S-A18-2*A19$	A26	A27	$A6-A9-A12+A18+A19+A7+A23-2*A24-A15-A16-2*A26+2*A5+A10-A13+A8-A3-2*A4+A14-2*A29+(5/6)*S$	A28	$A22+A23+2*A24+A26-2*A5-A10+A13-A8+2*A3+A2+2*A4+A20-A14-A28-(1/3)*S-A18-A19-A7$	$A9+A12+(1/2)*S-A27-A22-2*A23+A15+A16-A3-A2-A20+2*A29-A6$	$2*A18+2*A19+A14-(2/3)*S$	A29
A18	A19	$(1/3)*S-A26$	$(1/3)*S-A27$	$A9+A12-(1/2)*S-A18-A19-A7-A23+2*A24+A15+A16+2*A26-2*A5-A10+A13-A8+A3+2*A4-A14+2*A29-A6$	$((5/3)*S-S)/2-A28$	$A28+(2/3)*S+A18+A19+A7-A22-A23-2*A24-A26+2*A5+A10-A13+A8-2*A3-A2-2*A4-A20+A14$	$A6-A9-A12-(1/6)*S+A27+A22+2*A23-A15-A16+A3+A2+A20-2*A29$	$(2/3)*S-A14-A18-A19$	A14
$(1/2)*S-A18-A19+A24-A17-A5+A3+A2+A4-A14-A28$	$(1/6)*S+A18+A19-A24+A17+A5-A3-A2-A4+A14$	$(1/3)*S+A19-A25-A20$	A1	A2	A3	A4	$(2/3)*S-A19+A25-A3-A1-A2-A4+A20$	$(1/3)*S-A20$	A20
A15	$(1/3)*S-A15$	A5	$S-A24-A26+A10-A13+A8+A25-A1-A3-A2-A4+A20-A29-A19$	A6	$(5/3)*S+A7-2*A24-2*A26+A5+A10+A8-A1-2*A3-A2-2*A4-2*A29-A9$	$A19+A24+A26-A10-A8-A25+A1+A3+A2+A4-A20+A29-(1/3)*S-A12$	$A9+A12-(4/3)*S-A7+2*A24+2*A26-2*A5-A10+A13-A8+A1+2*A3+A2+2*A4+2*A29-A6$	$(1/3)*S-A21$	A21
A16	$(1/3)*S-A16$	A7	$A19+A27+A23-A10+A13+A11-A8-A25+A3+A2+A4-A20-A29-A9-A12$	$A1+2*A26-A5-A10-A11-A8+A1$	A8	$A9-(2/3)*S-A19+A27-A7+A23+A24+A26-A5-A8+A25+A3+A4+A20$	$A6-A9+(13/6)*S-A27+A7-A23-3*A24-3*A26+2*A5+2*A10-A13+2*A8-A1-3*A3-A2-3*A4-2*A29$	$A20+A21+A22+A23+A24-(2/3)*S$	$S-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24$
A17	$(1/3)*S-A17$	$A24+A26-A5-A11+A25+A20+A29-A19-A7$	A9	A10	$(1/3)*S+A7-A24-A26+A5+A11-A3-A29$	$2*S/3-A4-A9-A1$	$A19-A25+A3+A1+A4-A20-A10$	$(1/3)*S-A22$	A22
$A28+(5/6)*S+A19-A22-A23-A24+A5-A3-A2-A4-A20$	$A22+A23+A24-A5+A3+A2+A4+A20-A28-(1/2)*S-A19$	A11	A12	$A6-2*A9-A12+(7/3)*S+A7-3*A24-3*A26+2*A5+A10-A13+2*A8-A1-2*A3-A2-3*A4-3*A29$	$A9-S-A7+2*A24+2*A26-2*A5-A10-A11-A8+A1+2*A3+A2+2*A4+2*A29$	A13	$A9-(1/3)*S+A24+A26-A8+A4+A29-A6$	$(1/3)*S-A23$	A23
$A18+A22+A23-A15-A16+A20+A14-(1/3)*S$	$(2/3)*S-A18-A22-A23+A15+A16-A20-A14$	$(2/3)*S-A24-A26-A29$	$A24+A26-A11+2*A29-A27-A23$	$A9-(5/6)*S+A27+A23+A24+A26-A5-A10+A13+A11-A8+A3+2*A4-A6$	$A24+A26-A8+A29-A7$	$A12+(4/3)*S-A27+A7-A23-2*A24-2*A26+A5+A10-A13+2*A8-2*A3-A2-2*A4-A29$	$A6-A9-A12-(1/6)*S+A27+A23+A3+A2-A29$	$(1/3)*S-A24$	A24
$(1/3)*S-A19+A29-A18$	$(1/3)*S-A29$	$(1/3)*S-A25$	$2*A19+A21+A5-A25+A1-A20-(1/3)*S$	$A28+A18+A19+A7-A22-A23-3*A24+A17-2*A26-A21+2*A5+A10-A13+A8-2*A3-A2-2*A4-A20+A14-A29+(7/6)*S$	$A6-A9-A12+A22+A23-A15+A3+A2-A29$	$A9+A12-A18-2*A19-A7+2*A24+A15+2*A26-2*A5-A10+A13-A8+A25+A3+2*A4+A20-A14+2*A29-(2/3)*S-A6$	$(1/2)*S-A28+A24-A17-A5-A19+A25-A1+A20$	$A18-(1/3)*S+A14+A29$	$(1/3)*S+A19-A29-A14$
$A18+A19-(1/3)*S+A14$	$A18+A19+A29-(1/3)*S$	A25	$(2/3)*S-2*A19-A21-A5+A25-A1+A20$	$A22+A23+3*A24-A17+2*A26+A21-2*A5-A10+A13-A8+2*A3+A2+2*A4+A20-A14+A29-(5/6)*S-A28-A18-A19-A7$	$A9+A12+(1/3)*S-A22-A23+A15-A3-A2+A29-A6$	$A6-A9-A12+A18+2*A19+A7-2*A24-A15-2*A26+2*A5+A10-A13+A8-A25-A3-2*A4-A20+A14-2*A29+S$	$A28-(1/6)*S-A24+A17+A5+A19-A25+A1-A20$	$S-2*A18-A19-A14-A29$	$(1/3)*S-A19$

Details:

It a double-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square of order 10 having pandiagonal magic square of order 6 in the middle. The four magic rectangles of order 2×6 are of equal width and length. We have both the magic squares of orders 10 and 6 pandiagonal. The magic sum of order 10 is given as $T = \frac{5}{3} \times S$, where S is the magic sum of order 6.

In order to bring this pandiagonal magic square of order 10 without decimal entries, the magic sum of order 6 should be multiple of 6. See below two examples:

Example 5.2. *Let's consider the following example:*

10x10	pan	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	10x10	pan	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	
80	-59	-54	36	37	-119	38	68	-12	106	39	80	90	-55	-50	36	37	-114	38	66	-9	102	39	90
80	28	29	-20	-21	135	-22	-52	28	-49	24	80	90	28	29	-18	-19	132	-20	-48	27	-45	24	90
80	-64	80	-20	11	12	13	14	18	-14	30	80	90	-61	79	-18	11	12	13	14	22	-12	30	90
80	25	-9	15	-60	16	-164	47	194	-15	31	80	90	25	-7	15	-54	16	-154	45	186	-13	31	90
80	26	-10	17	-1	135	18	140	-261	128	-112	80	90	26	-8	17	-1	132	18	136	-248	124	-106	90
80	27	-11	92	19	20	-53	-12	-18	-16	32	80	90	27	-9	92	19	20	-51	-8	-18	-14	32	90
80	-46	62	21	22	-270	160	23	92	-17	33	80	90	-41	59	21	22	-256	154	23	90	-15	33	90
80	80	-64	-77	57	135	74	-164	23	-18	34	80	90	78	-60	-73	57	130	74	-156	22	-16	34	90
80	-2	-23	-19	34	-141	1	170	3	75	-18	80	90	0	-21	-17	32	-134	1	166	6	73	-16	90
	65	80	35	-18	157	15	-154	13	-100	-13	80		63	78	35	-14	152	17	-148	12	-94	-11	90
©IJT	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	©IJT	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 80$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 48$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 90$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 54$.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.3. Let's consider the following *self-made magic square of order 10 with reduced entries*:

$A_{11} - (9/20)*M$	$(19/20)*M - 2*A_{11} + A_{13}$	$(129/20)*M - A_7 - A_{17} - A_{16} + A_{10} - A_{14}$	$A_3 + A_{17} - A_8 + A_{14} + A_{12} - 5*M - A_6 - A_{11}$	A_6	A_7	$A_{11} - A_{10} - (1/5)*M$	$(1/4)*M - A_3 + A_{16} + A_8 - A_{12}$	$(21/4)*M + A_{11} - A_{13}$	$-(19/4)*M$
$(1/20)*M - A_{13}$	A_{11}	$A_7 + A_{17} + A_{16} - A_{10} + A_{14} - (119/20)*M$	$(11/2)*M + A_6 + A_{11} - A_3 - A_{17} + A_8 - A_{14} - A_{12}$	$(1/2)*M - A_6$	$(1/2)*M - A_7$	$(7/10)*M - A_{11} + A_{10}$	$(1/4)*M + A_3 - A_{16} - A_8 + A_{12}$	$-(26/5)*M$	$(123/20)*M - A_{11} + A_{13}$
$A_{17} + A_{16} - A_9 - A_{10} + A_{14} - A_4 - A_2 + A_1 - (27/5)*M - A_3$	$(59/10)*M + A_3 - A_{17} - A_{16} + A_9 + A_{10} - A_{14} + A_4 + A_2 - A_1$	$(1/2)*M + A_{11} - A_{14} - A_{12}$	$A_3 - A_1 + A_4$	A_1	$(1/2)*M - A_{11} - A_3 + A_{14} - A_4 + A_{12}$	A_5	$(1/2)*M - A_5$	$(1/2)*M - A_{12}$	A_{12}
$(119/20)*M + A_{11} - A_{17} - A_{14} + A_4 + A_2 - A_1 - A_{12}$	$A_{17} + A_{14} - A_4 - A_2 + A_1 + A_{12} - (109/20)*M - A_{11}$	A_2	$(1/2)*M - A_{11} - A_3 + A_{14} - A_4 - A_2 + A_1 + A_{12}$	$(1/2)*M + A_{11} - A_{14} + A_2 - A_1 - A_{12}$	$A_3 + A_4 - A_2$	$(1/4)*M + A_{11} - A_{14} + A_4 + A_2 - A_1 - A_{12}$	$(1/4)*M - A_{11} + A_{14} - A_4 - A_2 + A_1 + A_{12}$	$(4/5)*M + 2*A_{11} - A_5 - A_{15} - A_9 - A_{10} - A_{14} - A_{12}$	$A_5 + A_{15} + A_9 + A_{10} + A_{14} + A_{12} - (3/10)*M - 2*A_{11}$
A_8	$(1/2)*M - A_8$	$M/2 - A_1$	$A_{11} + A_3 - A_{14} + A_4 - A_{12}$	$-(A_{11} + A_{14} + A_{12})$	$(1/2)*M - A_3 + A_1 - A_4$	$(1/4)*M - A_{11} + A_{14} - A_4 + A_{12}$	$(1/4)*M + A_{11} - A_{14} + A_4 - A_{12}$	$A_7 + A_3 + A_{15} + A_9 + A_4 + A_2 - A_1 - (11/20)*M$	$(21/20)*M - A_7 - A_3 - A_{15} - A_9 - A_4 - A_2 + A_1$
A_9	$(1/2)*M - A_9$	$-(A_{11} + A_{14} - A_2 + A_1 + A_{12})$	$(1/2)*M - A_3 - A_4 + A_2$	$M/2 - A_2$	$A_{11} + A_3 - A_{14} + A_4 + A_2 - A_1 - A_{12}$	$(1/2)*M - A_5 - A_2 + A_1$	$A_5 + A_2 - A_1$	$A_1 + A_6 - A_3 + A_{16} + A_8 - A_4 - A_2 - (9/20)*M$	$(19/20)*M - A_1 - A_6 + A_3 - A_{16} - A_8 + A_4 + A_2$
A_{10}	$(1/2)*M - A_{10}$	$(3/4)*M + A_{11} - A_5 - A_{14} - A_{12}$	A_3	A_4	$(1/4)*M - A_{11} - A_3 + A_5 + A_{14} - A_4 + A_{12}$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M - A_6 - A_{11} + A_{17} - A_8 + A_{14} + A_{12}$	$(1/4)*M + A_6 + A_8 + A_{11} - A_{17} - A_{14} - A_{12}$
$(19/20)*M - A_{11} + A_3 - A_{16} - A_8 + A_{12}$	$A_{16} + A_8 + A_{11} - A_{12} - (9/20)*M - A_3$	$A_5 + A_{14} + A_{12} - (1/4)*M - A_{11}$	$(1/2)*M - A_3$	$(1/2)*M - A_4$	$(1/4)*M + A_{11} + A_3 - A_5 - A_{14} + A_4 - A_{12}$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$(19/20)*M - A_7 - A_{11} + A_5 - A_{17} - A_{16} + A_{10} + A_{12}$	$A_7 + A_{11} - A_5 + A_{17} + A_{16} - A_{10} - A_{12} - (9/20)*M$
$A_{13} - (43/10)*M - A_{11}$	$(21/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M - A_{14}$	$A_3 + A_5 + A_{15} + A_9 + A_{10} + A_4 + A_2 - A_1 - (4/5)*M$	$(1/2)*M - A_{15}$	$(1/2)*M - A_{16}$	$(1/2)*M - A_{17}$	$(3/10)*M - A_3 - A_5 + A_{17} + A_{16} - A_9 - A_{10} + A_{14} - A_4 - A_2 + A_1$	$(19/20)*M - A_{11}$	$2*A_{11} - A_{13} - (9/10)*M$
$(57/10)*M$	$A_{11} - A_{13} - (26/5)*M$	A_{14}	$(13/10)*M - A_3 - A_5 - A_{15} - A_9 - A_{10} - A_4 - A_2 + A_1$	A_{15}	A_{16}	A_{17}	$(1/5)*M + A_3 + A_5 - A_{17} - A_{16} + A_9 + A_{10} - A_{14} + A_4 + A_2 - A_1$	A_{13}	$(1/2)*M - (5/2)*M - A_{11} - (3/4)*M$

Details:

It a *double-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square of order 10 having cornered pandiagonal magic square of order 6 in the middle*. It contains a *pandiagonal magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner*. The magic rectangles of order 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal width and length in each case. All the magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3}{2} \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 4.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal magic square of order 10 without decimal entries*, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 20. See below two examples:

Example 5.3. *Let's consider the following example:*

10x10	pan	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		10x10	pan	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150
100	3	19	184	-169	16	17	-7	19	208	-190	100		150	-6	38	313	-269	16	17	-11	24	313	-285	150
100	-21	21	-164	189	4	3	27	1	-208	248	100		150	-20	21	-283	299	14	13	41	6	-312	371	150
100	-206	226	-5	16	11	18	15	5	-2	22	100		150	-314	344	5	16	11	28	15	15	8	22	150
100	201	-181	12	17	-4	15	0	20	-51	71	100		150	320	-290	12	27	6	15	5	25	-35	65	150
100	18	2	9	2	25	4	21	-1	67	-47	100		150	18	12	19	2	25	14	26	4	56	-26	150
100	19	1	24	5	8	3	4	16	14	6	100		150	19	11	24	15	18	3	14	16	5	25	150
100	20	0	-10	13	14	23	10	10	28	-8	100		150	20	10	5	13	14	28	15	15	33	-3	150
100	8	12	30	7	6	-3	10	10	4	16	100		150	27	3	25	17	16	2	15	15	23	7	150
100	-170	210	-4	75	-5	-6	-7	7	17	-17	100		150	-256	315	6	59	5	4	3	13	36	-35	150
	228	-210	24	-55	25	26	27	13	23	-1	100			342	-314	24	-29	25	26	27	17	23	9	150
©IJT	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		©IJT	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 100$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 60$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 40$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 150$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 90$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 60$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.4. Let's consider the following *self-made magic square* of order 10 with reduced entries:

$(5/2)*M-A13-A2-2*A1-A11-A10-A3-A16-A15$	$A11+A10+A3+A16+A15+A12-(5/2)*M+2*A13+A2+2*A1$	$(3/4)*M-A5+A13-A3-A16-A15+A7+A9+A18-A2-A1$	$A15-A11+A8+A6+(1/2)*M-A9-A13-A18$	$A11+A16-A6$	$A5$	$2*M-A13-A1-A11-A10-A16-A15-A7$	$A11+A10+A3+A16+A15-A8-(7/4)*M+A13+A2+2*A1$	$(5/2)*M-A13-A2-2*A1+A18-A11-A10-A3-A16-A15-A12$	$A11+A10+A3+A16+A15-(3/2)*M+A2+2*A1-A18$
$(5/2)*M-A2-2*A1-A11-A10-A3-A16-A15-A12$	$(1/2)*M-A13$	$A3+A16+A15-A7-A9-A18+A2+A1-(1/4)*M+A5-A13$	$A11-A8-A6+A9+A13+A18-A15$	$(1/2)*M+A6-A11-A16$	$(1/2)*M-A5$	$A16+A15-(3/2)*M+A7+A11+A10+A13+A1$	$A8+(9/4)*M-A13-A2-2*A1-A11-A10-A3-A16-A15$	$(1/2)*M-A18$	$A11+A10+A3+A16+A15+A12-(5/2)*M+A13+A2+2*A1+A18$
$(3/4)*M-A18-A17$	$A17-(1/4)*M+A18$	$(1/4)*M$	$2*A8+2*A6+M-2*A9-2*A13+2*A4-2*A11-2*A10-2*A16$	$A11+A10+A16-A8-A6-(1/4)*M+A9+A13-A4$	$A4+A1-(1/4)*M$	$A11+A10+A16-A8-A6+(1/2)*M+A9+A13-2*A4-A1$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A9$	$A9$
$A11+A10-A8-A6-(1/2)*M+A9+A13+A18$	$M-A11-A10+A8+A6-A9-A13-A18$	$2*A11+2*A10+2*A16-2*A8-2*A6-(1/4)*M+2*A9+2*A13-2*A4-A1$	$A1$	$A2$	$A8+A6+(3/2)*M-A9-A13-A2-A1-A11-A10-A16$	$A11+A10+A16-A8-A6-(1/2)*M+A9+A13$	$2*A8+2*A6+(3/4)*M-2*A9-2*A13+2*A4+A1-2*A11-2*A10-2*A16$	$(5/4)*M-A16-A17-A14-A15+A9-A1$	$A16+A17+A14+A15-A9+A1-(3/4)*M$
$A6$	$(1/2)*M-A6$	$A8+A6+(3/2)*M-A9-A13+A4-A2-A1-A11-A10-A3-A16$	$A3$	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A11+A10+A3+A16-A8-A6-(3/2)*M+A9+A13+A2+2*A1$	$A8+A6+(3/2)*M-A9-A13-A1-A11-A10-A3-A16$	$A11+A10+A3+A16-A8-A6-M+A9+A13-A4+A2+A1$	$A16+A14+A15+A5+A17-A7-A9-(1/4)*M-A13$	$(3/4)*M+A9+A13-A16-A14-A15-A5-A17+A7$
$A17+(5/4)*M-A7-A11-A10-A9-A13$	$A7+A11+A10+A9+A13-(3/4)*M-A17$	$(1/2)*M-A4$	$A11+A10+A16-A8-A6-M+A9+A13+A2+A1$	$A8+A6+M-A9-A13-A11-A10-A16$	$M/2-A1$	$M/2-A2$	$A4$	$(1/2)*M-A10$	$A10$
$A7$	$(1/2)*M-A7$	$A3-A16+A8+A6-(3/4)*M-A9-A13+2*A4+A2+2*A1-A11-A10$	$A8+A6+2*M-A9-A13-A2-2*A1-A11-A10-A3-A16$	$A11+A10+A3+A16-A8-A6-M+A9+A13+A1$	$M/2-A3$	$A1+A2+A3-M/2$	$A11+A10-A3+A16-A8-A6+(5/4)*M+A9+A13-2*A4-A2-2*A1$	$(1/2)*M-A11$	$A11$
$A8$	$(1/2)*M-A8$	$(1/4)*M$	$2*A11+2*A10+2*A16-2*A8-2*A6-(1/2)*M+2*A9+2*A13-2*A4$	$A8+A6+(3/4)*M-A9-A13+A4-A11-A10-A16$	$(3/4)*M-A4-A1$	$A8+A6-A9-A13+2*A4+A1-A11-A10-A16$	$(1/4)*M$	$A1-A5+A7+A11+A10+A9+A13-M$	$(3/2)*M-A1+A5-A7-A11-A10-A9-A13$
$2*A11+2*A10+2*A3+2*A16+2*A15+A12-4*M+A13+2*A2+4*A1-A18$	$2*M-A2-2*A1+A18-A11-A10-A3-A16-A15$	$A9+A13-(1/4)*M$	$A14+A15+A16+A17-(1/4)*M-A9-A13$	$(1/2)*M-A14$	$(1/2)*M-A15$	$(1/2)*M-A16$	$(1/2)*M-A17$	$A11+A10+A3+A16+A15-2*M+A13+A2+2*A1$	$5*M-2*A13-2*A2-4*A1-2*A11-2*A10-2*A3-2*A16-2*A15-A12$
$A18$	$M-A18-A13-A12$	$(3/4)*M-A9-A13$	$(3/4)*M+A9+A13-A14-A15-A16-A17$	$A14$	$A15$	$A16$	$A17$	$A12$	$A13$

Details:

It is a *double-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square* of order 10 having *single-digit pandiagonal magic square* of order 6 with *pandiagonal magic square* of order 4. The four magic rectangles of order 2×6 are of equal width and length. All the magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3}{2} \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 4.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal magic square* of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4. See below two examples:

Result 5.5. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:

$A7+A11-A12$	$2*A12-A7$	$A7+A11+A17-A10-A3$	$A3-A7-A9-A11-A17+(4/3)*M$	$A8+A7+A9+A6+A11-A12-A3-A16-A13$	$A3+A5-A7+A13-A11-A8+A12-(2/3)*M+A10+A16$	$A7+A11-A12+M-A1-A2-A5$	$A2-A7-A6-A11+A12+(1/3)*M+A1$	$A17+A7-A12$	$(4/3)*M-A17-A7-A11$
$A7$	$(2/3)*M-A12$	$A3-A7-A11-A17+(2/3)*M+A10$	$A7+A9+A11+A17-(2/3)*M-A3$	$(2/3)*M+A3+A16+A13-A8-A7-A9-A6-A11+A12$	$A7-A13+A11+A8-A12+(4/3)*M-A10-A16-A3-A5$	$A2+A5-A7-A11+A12+A1-(1/3)*M$	$A7+A6+A11-A12+(1/3)*M-A1-A2$	$(2/3)*M-A17$	$A17+A12-A7$
$(4/3)*M-A3-A16-A17$	$A3+A16+A17-(2/3)*M$	$M-A1-A2$	$A2$	$A1$	$M-A3-A4$	$A4$	$A3$	$(4/3)*M-A15-A16-A13+A8-A14$	$A15+A16+A13-A8+A14-(2/3)*M$
$A3-A15+A17$	$(2/3)*M-(A3-A15+A17)$	$A2+2*A1-(2/3)*M$	$M/3$	$(4/3)*M-2*A1-A2$	$A4-(2/3)*M+2*A3$	$M/3$	$(4/3)*M-2*A3-A4$	$(2/3)*M-A8$	$A8$
$A3+A15+A16+A13-A8+A2+A1-A7-A11+A12-A6-(2/3)*M$	$(4/3)*M-A3-A15-A16-A13+A8-A2-A1+A7+A11-A12+A6$	$(2/3)*M-A1$	$(2/3)*M-A2$	$A1+A2-(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A3$	$(2/3)*M-A4$	$A3+A4-(1/3)*M$	$2*A3+A2+A10-A7+A16+A13-A11-(4/3)*M+A1$	$2*M-2*A3-A16-A13+A7+A11-A2-A1-A10$
$A7-A13+A11+A8-A12+(4/3)*M-A3-A2-A1-A5$	$A3+A2+A1+A5-A7+A13-A11-A8+A12-(2/3)*M$	$A3+A4-M/3$	$2*M/3-A4$	$2*M/3-A3$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$A7+A9+A15+A11-A2+A14-A1-2*A3$	$2*A3-A7-A9-A15-A11+(2/3)*M+A2-A14+A1$
$A5$	$(2/3)*M-A5$	$4*M/3-2*A3-A4$	$M/3$	$2*A3+A4-2*M/3$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	$M/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$(2/3)*M-A9$	$A9$
$A6$	$(2/3)*M-A6$	$A3$	$A4$	$M-A3-A4$	$A1$	$A2$	$M-A1-A2$	$(2/3)*M-A10$	$A10$
$A12+(4/3)*M-2*A7-A11-A17$	$A17+A7+A11-(2/3)*M$	$A15+A16+A13-A8+A12-(1/3)*M+A14-A1-A2$	$A2+A8-A12-(1/3)*M+A1$	$(2/3)*M-A13$	$(2/3)*M-A14$	$(2/3)*M-A15$	$(2/3)*M-A16$	$(2/3)*M-A7-A11+A12$	$2*A7+A11-2*A12$
$A17$	$(4/3)*M-A17-A12-A11$	$A2-A15-A16-A13+A8-A12+M-A14+A1$	$A12+M-A1-A2-A8$	$A13$	$A14$	$A15$	$A16$	$A11$	$A12$

Details:

It is a *double-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 having *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 with four equal sums *semi-magic* squares of order 3. The four magic rectangles of order 2×6 are of equal width and length. The magic squares of orders 6 and 10 are *pandiagonal* and the blocks of order 3 are *semi-magic*. The magic sums of orders 10 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10}{3} \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 2 \times M$, where M is the *semi-magic* sum of order 3.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples:

Example 5.5. *Let's consider the following example:*

10x10	pan	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	10x10	pan	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160
150	21	43	53	-49	3	63	23	-3	33	-37	150	160	21	43	53	-45	3	61	26	-2	33	-33	160
150	23	-3	-23	79	27	-33	7	33	-13	53	150	160	23	-1	-21	77	29	-29	6	34	-11	53	160
150	-39	69	21	13	11	13	17	15	-67	97	150	160	-35	67	24	13	11	16	17	15	-63	95	160
150	19	11	5	15	25	17	15	13	5	25	150	160	19	13	3	16	29	15	16	17	7	25	160
150	57	-27	19	17	9	15	13	17	45	-15	150	160	55	-23	21	19	8	17	15	16	41	-9	160
150	13	17	17	13	15	9	17	19	103	-73	150	160	17	15	16	15	17	8	19	21	103	-71	160
150	19	11	13	15	17	25	15	5	3	27	150	160	19	13	17	16	15	29	16	3	5	27	160
150	21	9	15	17	13	11	13	21	1	29	150	160	21	11	15	17	16	11	13	24	3	29	160
150	-27	67	121	1	-5	-7	-9	-11	9	11	150	160	-23	65	120	0	-3	-5	-7	-9	11	11	160
	43	-47	-91	29	35	37	39	41	31	33	150		43	-43	-88	32	35	37	39	41	31	33	160
©IJT	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	©IJT	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

The magic sums for the first example are $T_{10 \times 10} := 150$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 90$ and $T_{3 \times 3} := 45$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 160$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 96$ and $T_{3 \times 3} := 48$ respectively. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6 and 10 are **pandiagonal**. The four equal sums of order 3 are **semi-magic**

Result 5.6. Let's consider the following *self-made magic square* of order 10 with reduced entries:

$(2/5)*m+A9+A14-A2-A4-2*A1+A8+A13$	$2*A2+2*A4+4*A1-A8-(4/5)*m-2*A9-2*A14$	$A8+A3+A17+A13+(7/5)*m-A2-2*A4-2*A1-A12$	$2*m+A4+A1-A8-A3-A17-A13-A11$	$A3-A10+(1/2)*m+A14-A4-A1+A7$	$A1+A12-A3+A11+A10+A6-A14+A2+A4-(19/10)*m$	$A8+A13+(2/5)*m+A9+A14-A2-A4-A1-A6$	$(3/5)*m-A9-A14+A2+2*A4+2*A1-A7-A8-A13$	$A17+A9+A14-A4-2*A1+(2/5)*m+A8-A2$	$2*m-A8-A17-A13$
A8	$(7/5)*m+A9+A14-A2-A4-2*A1$	$A2+2*A4+2*A1+A12-A8-A3-A17-A13-(2/5)*m$	$A8+A3+A17+A13+A11-m-A4-A1$	$A10+(1/2)*m-A14+A4+A1-A7-A3$	$(29/10)*m-A1-A12+A3-A11-A10-A6+A14-A2-A4$	$(3/5)*m-A9-A14+A2+A4+A1+A6-A8-A13$	$(2/5)*m+A8+A13+A9+A14-A2-2*A4-2*A1+A7$	m-A17	$A17-A9-A14+A2+A4+2*A1-(2/5)*m-A8$
$(22/5)*m+A14-A2-A4-2*A1-A5-A17-A11-A10-A6$	$A17+A11+A10+A6-(17/5)*m-A14+A2+A4+2*A1+A5$	$(12/5)*m-A2-2*A1-A4$	A1	$(3/5)*m$	A2	$A4+A1-A3$	A3	m-A9	A9
$A3+A17+m-A4-A1-A16$	$A4+A1+A16-A3-A17$	$2*A1-(7/5)*m+A4+A2$	m-A1	$(2/5)*m$	m-A2	$m+A3-A4-A1$	m-A3	$A8+A3+A13+A9+A14-2*A2-3*A4-3*A1+(33/10)*m-A15-A6-A5$	$2*A2+3*A4+3*A1-(23/10)*m+A15+A6+A5-A8-A3-A13-A9-A14$
$A11+A16+A10-(12/5)*m-A14+A2+2*A4+3*A1-A7-A3$	$A3-A11-A16-A10+(17/5)*m+A14-A2-2*A4-3*A1+A7$	$(9/10)*m-A1$	$(3/2)*m-A4-A2$	$A4+A2+A1-(9/10)*m$	$(3/2)*m-A4-A1$	$2*A4-A3+A2-(3/2)*m+2*A1$	$(3/2)*m-A4-A2+A3-A1$	$A11+A15+A10+A6+A5-A14+A12+2*A2+3*A4+3*A1-(43/10)*m-A8-A3-A13$	$A8+A3+A13-A11-A15-A10-A6-A5+A14-A12-2*A2-3*A4-3*A1+(53/10)*m$
A5	m-A5	$(1/10)*m+A1$	$A4+A2-(1/2)*m$	$(19/10)*m-A4-A2-A1$	$A4+A1-(1/2)*m$	$(5/2)*m-2*A4-A2-2*A1+A3$	$A4+A2-A3+A1-(1/2)*m$	m-A10	A10
A6	m-A6	$(12/5)*m+A3-2*A4-A2-2*A1$	$A4+A1-A3$	$(3/5)*m-A4+A3$	$A4+A2-A3$	A1	A4	m-A11	A11
A7	m-A7	$2*A4+A2+2*A1-A3-(7/5)*m$	$m+A3-A4-A1$	$A4+(2/5)*m-A3$	$m-A4-A2+A3$	m-A1	m-A4	m-A12	A12
$(8/5)*m-A9-A14+A2+A4+2*A1-2*A8-A17-A13$	$A8-m+A17+A13$	m-A14	$A2+2*A4+2*A1+A15+A6+A5-A8-A3-A13-(19/10)*m$	m-A15	$A8+A13+A11+A16+A10-(3/2)*m-A4$	m-A16	$(17/5)*m+A3-A11-A10-A6+A14-A2-A4-2*A1-A5$	$A2+A4+2*A1-A8-A13+(3/5)*m-A9-A14$	$(4/5)*m+2*A9+2*A14-2*A2-2*A4-4*A1+2*A8+A13$
A17	$(12/5)*m-A17+A9+A14-A2-A4-2*A1-A13$	A14	$A8+A3+A13+(29/10)*m-A2-2*A4-2*A1-A15-A6-A5$	A15	$(5/2)*m+A4-A8-A13-A11-A16-A10$	A16	$A11+A10+A6-(12/5)*m-A14+A2+A4+2*A1+A5-A3$	A13	$A2+A4+2*A1-(2/5)*m-A9-A14$

Details:

It is a **double-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square** of order 10 having **striped pandiagonal magic square** of order 6 with three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 . The four magic rectangles of order 2×6 are of equal width and length. The magic squares of orders 6 and 10 are **pandiagonal**. The magic sums of orders 10 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := 5 \times m$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 3 \times m$, where magic rectangle of order $m \times 3m$.

In order to bring this **pandiagonal magic square** of order 10 without **decimal** entries, the width of magic rectangles of order 2×6 should be multiple of 10. See below two examples:

Example 5.6. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	10x10	pan	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
150	48	-32	39	-17	24	22	43	-21	52	-8	150	150	200	52	-40	53	3	29	3	47	-15	56	12	200	
150	18	37	-9	47	6	8	-13	51	3	2	150	150	200	18	51	-13	37	11	37	-7	55	13	-2	200	
150	9	21	24	11	18	12	12	13	11	19	150	150	200	53	-13	48	11	24	12	12	13	21	19	200	
150	19	11	6	19	12	18	18	17	41	-11	150	150	200	29	11	-8	29	16	28	28	27	74	-34	200	
150	14	16	16	19	10	20	4	21	11	19	150	150	200	-10	50	25	34	1	35	-11	36	-32	72	200	
150	15	15	14	11	20	10	26	9	10	20	150	150	200	15	25	15	6	39	5	51	4	20	20	200	
150	16	14	23	12	17	13	11	14	9	21	150	150	200	16	24	47	12	23	13	11	14	19	21	200	
150	17	13	7	18	13	17	19	16	8	22	150	150	200	17	23	-7	28	17	27	29	26	18	22	200	
150	-33	38	6	7	5	49	4	19	-18	73	150	150	200	-17	28	16	-12	15	34	14	53	-12	81	200	
	27	17	24	23	25	-19	26	11	23	-7	150	150		27	41	24	52	25	6	26	-13	23	-11	200	
©IJT	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	©IJT	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 150$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 90$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 200$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 120$ respectively. The magic rectangles of order $m \times 3m$ in each case are 30×90 and 40×120 .

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

5.3 Cornered Magic Squares

Result 5.7. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$A_2 - A_7 + A_4$	$A_{13} + A_{12} + A_{11} + 2*A_7 + A_{14} + A_5 + A_6 - A_1 - M - 2*A_2$	$A_9 + A_1 - A_{13} + A_{14} - A_{12} + A_{11} - A_8$	$A_8 - A_6 - A_5 - A_9 + 2*M + A_2 - 2*A_{14} - 2*A_{11} - A_7 - A_4$	A_2	A_3	$(1/2)*M - A_3 - A_2 + A_{11} - A_{15} + A_7$	$(1/2)*M - A_{11} + A_{15} - A_7$	$(1/2)*M - A_{10}$	A_{10}
A_1	$2*M - A_7 - A_6 - A_5 + A_2 - A_{13} - A_{12} - A_{11} - A_{14} - A_4$	$A_8 - A_9 + A_2 + A_{13} - A_{14} + A_{12} - A_{11} - A_7 + A_4$	$2*A_{11} + 2*A_7 + A_6 + 2*A_{14} + A_5 + A_9 - A_1 - M - A_8 - 2*A_2$	$A_{13} + A_{12} + A_{11} + 2*A_7 - A_3 - 2*A_2 - A_{15}$	$M + A_2 + A_{15} - A_{13} - A_{12} - A_{11} - 2*A_7$	$A_{13} + A_{12} + A_7 - (1/2)*M$	$A_3 + (1/2)*M + A_2 - A_{13} - A_{12} - A_7$	$A_{15} + A_{13} + A_{12} - (1/2)*M$	$M - A_{15} - A_{13} - A_{12}$
$A_8 - A_9 + (1/2)*M - A_1 + A_{13} - A_{14} + A_{12} - A_{11}$	$2*A_{11} + A_6 - A_2 + 2*A_{14} + A_7 + A_5 + A_9 + A_4 - (3/2)*M - A_8$	$(1/2)*M - A_2 + A_7 - A_4$	$(3/2)*M + A_1 + 2*A_2 - A_{13} - A_{12} - A_{11} - 2*A_7 - A_{14} - A_5 - A_6$	$A_3 + A_2 - A_{11} + A_{15} - A_7$	$A_{11} - A_{15} + A_7$	$M/2 - A_2$	$M/2 - A_3$	$(1/2)*M - A_{11}$	A_{11}
$(1/2)*M - A_{13} - A_{12} + A_9 - A_2 + A_{14} + A_{11} + A_7 - A_4 - A_8$	$(3/2)*M + A_8 + 2*A_2 - 2*A_{11} - 2*A_7 - A_6 - 2*A_{14} - A_5 - A_9 + A_1$	$M/2 - A_1$	$A_7 + A_6 + A_5 - (3/2)*M - A_2 + A_{13} + A_{14} + A_{12} + A_{11} + A_4$	$M - A_{13} - A_{12} - A_7$	$A_{13} + A_{12} + A_7 - A_3 - A_2$	$(1/2)*M + A_3 + 2*A_2 + A_{15} - A_{13} - A_{12} - A_{11} - 2*A_7$	$A_{13} + A_{12} + A_{11} + 2*A_7 - A_2 - (1/2)*M - A_{15}$	$(1/2)*M - A_{12}$	A_{12}
A_4	A_5	$A_6 - A_2 + A_{14} + A_{11} + A_7 - (1/2)*M$	$(3/2)*M - A_4 - A_5 - A_6 + A_2 - A_{14} - A_{11} - A_7$	A_7	$M - A_{15} - A_9 - A_{14}$	A_8	$A_{15} + A_9 + A_{14} - A_8 - A_7$	$(1/2)*M - A_{13}$	A_{13}
A_6	$M - A_4 - A_5 - A_6$	$A_4 + (1/2)*M + A_2 - A_{14} - A_{11} - A_7$	$A_5 - (1/2)*M - A_2 + A_{14} + A_{11} + A_7$	A_9	$A_{15} + A_{14} - A_7$	$A_7 - A_8 + A_9$	$M - A_{15} - 2*A_9 - A_{14} + A_8$	$(1/2)*M - A_{14}$	A_{14}
$M - A_6 + A_2 - A_{14} - A_{11} - A_7$	$A_4 + A_5 - M + A_6 - A_2 + A_{14} + A_{11} + A_7$	$M/2 - A_4$	$M/2 - A_5$	$M/2 - A_8$	$A_7 + (1/2)*M - A_{15} - A_9 - A_{14} + A_8$	$M/2 - A_7$	$A_{15} + A_9 + A_{14} - (1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*M - A_{15}$	A_{15}
$A_{14} + A_{11} + A_7 - A_4 - A_2$	$M - A_5 + A_2 - A_{14} - A_{11} - A_7$	$M/2 - A_6$	$A_4 + A_5 + A_6 - M/2$	$M/2 - A_7 + A_8 - A_9$	$A_{15} + 2*A_9 + A_{14} - A_8 - (1/2)*M$	$M/2 - A_9$	$A_7 + (1/2)*M - A_{15} - A_{14}$	$A_{14} + A_{11} + A_{10} - (1/2)*M$	$M - A_{14} - A_{11} - A_{10}$
$A_2 + A_{10} + A_4 - (1/4)*M - A_7$	$A_7 + A_6 + A_5 + A_{14} - A_2 + A_{11} + A_4 - (3/4)*M - A_{15}$	$(1/4)*M + A_7 - A_2 - A_4 + A_{11}$	$(7/4)*M - A_7 - A_{14} - A_6 - A_5 + A_2 - A_{13} - A_{11} - A_4$	$A_7 + A_{13} - (1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M - A_{15} + A_7$	$(1/4)*M + A_{15} - A_7$	$(3/4)*M - A_7 - A_{11} + A_{15} - A_{10}$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$
$(3/4)*M + A_7 - A_2 - A_{10} - A_4$	$(5/4)*M + A_{15} - A_7 - A_6 - A_5 - A_{14} + A_2 - A_{11} - A_4$	$(1/4)*M - A_7 + A_2 + A_4 - A_{11}$	$A_7 + A_{14} + A_6 + A_5 - A_2 + A_{13} + A_{11} + A_4 - (5/4)*M$	$(3/4)*M - A_{13} - A_7$	$(1/4)*M + A_{15} - A_7$	$(1/4)*M - A_{15} + A_7$	$A_7 + A_{11} - A_{15} + A_{10} - (1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$

Details:

It is a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 having *pandiagonal* magic square of order 8 at the upper-left corner. It contains four equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4. The two magic rectangles of order 2×8 are of equal width and length. The magic squares of orders 4, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10 and 8 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3}{2} \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 4.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4.
 See below two examples:

Example 5.7. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	7	141	13	-117	13	15	9	7	-7	29	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	11	-115	5	143	65	-49	69	-41	85	-63	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	9	139	15	-119	13	15	9	7	-9	31	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	17	-121	11	137	-47	63	-43	71	-11	33	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	17	19	77	-69	23	-59	25	55	-13	35	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	21	-13	-39	75	27	53	25	-61	-15	37	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	-55	91	5	3	-3	-33	-1	81	-17	39	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	61	-53	1	35	-3	83	-5	-31	75	-53	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	25	63	35	-93	47	-5	27	-11	11	11	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
	-3	-41	-13	115	-25	27	-5	33	11	11	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
©IJT	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110

10x10	pan	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	7	137	13	-109	13	15	11	9	-5	29	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	
120	11	-107	5	139	65	-45	67	-39	83	-59	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	
120	11	133	17	-113	13	15	11	9	-7	31	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	
120	19	-115	13	131	-43	63	-41	69	-9	33	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	
120	17	19	75	-63	23	-55	25	55	-11	35	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	
120	21	-9	-37	73	27	53	25	-57	-13	37	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	
120	-51	87	7	5	-1	-31	1	79	-15	39	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	
120	61	-49	3	33	-1	81	-3	-29	73	-49	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	
120	24	60	36	-86	46	-4	28	-8	12	12	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	
	0	-36	-12	110	-22	28	-4	32	12	12	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	
©IJT	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 110$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 88$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 44$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 120$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 96$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 48$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.8. Let's consider the following *self-made magic square of order 10 with reduced entries*:

$2 \cdot A_3 + A_1 + (25/2) \cdot m - A_5 + 2 \cdot A_2$	$-(29/2) \cdot m - A_2 - A_3 + A_5$	$2 \cdot m$	$2 \cdot m - A_3 - A_1 - A_2$	$5 \cdot A_3 - A_4 + 2 \cdot A_1 + 36 \cdot m - 3 \cdot A_5 + 5 \cdot A_2$	$3 \cdot A_5 - 4 \cdot A_2 + A_4 - A_1 - 38 \cdot m - 4 \cdot A_3$	$11 \cdot m + A_3 - A_5 + 2 \cdot A_2$	$A_5 - 3 \cdot A_2 - 7 \cdot m - 2 \cdot A_3 - A_1$	$12 \cdot m + 2 \cdot A_3 - A_5 + (3/2) \cdot A_1 + 2 \cdot A_2$	$A_5 - (3/2) \cdot A_1 - 2 \cdot A_2 - 11 \cdot m - 2 \cdot A_3$
$A_5 - 2 \cdot A_2 - (23/2) \cdot m - 2 \cdot A_3 - A_1$	$(31/2) \cdot m + A_3 - A_5 + A_2$	$(-m)$	$A_3 + A_1 - m + A_2$	$A_4 - 2 \cdot A_1 - 35 \cdot m - 5 \cdot A_3 + 3 \cdot A_5 - 5 \cdot A_2$	$4 \cdot A_3 + A_1 + 39 \cdot m - 3 \cdot A_5 + 4 \cdot A_2 - A_4$	$A_5 - 2 \cdot A_2 - 10 \cdot m - A_3$	$2 \cdot A_3 + A_1 + 8 \cdot m - A_5 + 3 \cdot A_2$	$A_5 - 2 \cdot A_2 + A_8 - (29/2) \cdot m - A_3$	$A_3 - A_5 + 2 \cdot A_2 + (31/2) \cdot m - A_8$
$(-A_3 - A_2)$	A_1	$A_5 - A_2 - (25/2) \cdot m - A_1 - A_3$	$(29/2) \cdot m + 2 \cdot A_3 - A_5 + 2 \cdot A_2$	$A_5 - 2 \cdot A_3 - 3 \cdot A_2 - 9 \cdot m$	$A_1 + 9 \cdot m + A_3 - A_5 + 2 \cdot A_2$	$A_4 - 2 \cdot A_1 - 36 \cdot m - 4 \cdot A_3 + 3 \cdot A_5 - 4 \cdot A_2$	$5 \cdot A_3 - A_4 + A_1 + 38 \cdot m - 3 \cdot A_5 + 5 \cdot A_2$	$3 \cdot A_5 - 2 \cdot A_1 - 6 \cdot A_2 + A_7 - (61/2) \cdot m - 5 \cdot A_3$	$5 \cdot A_3 - 3 \cdot A_5 + 2 \cdot A_1 + 6 \cdot A_2 + (63/2) \cdot m - A_7$
$m + A_3 + A_2$	$m - A_1$	$A_1 + (27/2) \cdot m + A_3 - A_5 + A_2$	$A_5 - 2 \cdot A_2 - (27/2) \cdot m - 2 \cdot A_3$	$2 \cdot A_3 + 10 \cdot m - A_5 + 3 \cdot A_2$	$A_5 - 2 \cdot A_2 - 8 \cdot m - A_1 - A_3$	$4 \cdot A_3 + 2 \cdot A_1 + 37 \cdot m - 3 \cdot A_5 + 4 \cdot A_2 - A_4$	$A_4 - A_1 - 37 \cdot m - 5 \cdot A_3 + 3 \cdot A_5 - 5 \cdot A_2$	$m - A_5$	A_5
$A_4 - 4 \cdot A_3 - 18 \cdot m + 2 \cdot A_5 - 4 \cdot A_2 - A_1$	$2 \cdot m - A_3 - A_2 - A_4$	$4 \cdot A_3 + A_1 + 18 \cdot m - 2 \cdot A_5 + 5 \cdot A_2$	A_3	$(11/2) \cdot m - A_3 - A_2$	$2 \cdot A_5 - 4 \cdot A_2 - (43/2) \cdot m - 4 \cdot A_3 - A_1$	$5 \cdot A_3 + A_1 + 27 \cdot m - 3 \cdot A_5 + 7 \cdot A_2$	$A_5 - 2 \cdot A_2 - 9 \cdot m$	$(29/2) \cdot m + A_3 + 2 \cdot A_2$	$(-27/2) \cdot m - A_3 - 2 \cdot A_2$
$4 \cdot A_3 - A_4 + A_1 + 19 \cdot m - 2 \cdot A_5 + 4 \cdot A_2$	$A_3 + A_2 + A_4 - m$	$2 \cdot A_5 - 5 \cdot A_2 - 17 \cdot m - 4 \cdot A_3 - A_1$	$m - A_3$	$A_3 - (9/2) \cdot m + A_2$	$(45/2) \cdot m + 4 \cdot A_3 + A_1 - 2 \cdot A_5 + 4 \cdot A_2$	$3 \cdot A_5 - 7 \cdot A_2 - 26 \cdot m - 5 \cdot A_3 - A_1$	$10 \cdot m - A_5 + 2 \cdot A_2$	$m - A_7$	A_7
$2 \cdot A_5 - 4 \cdot A_2 - A_1 - 3 \cdot A_3 - 18 \cdot m$	A_2	$3 \cdot A_3 - A_4 + A_1 + 20 \cdot m - 2 \cdot A_5 + 3 \cdot A_2$	A_4	$3 \cdot A_5 - 6 \cdot A_2 - A_1 - 4 \cdot A_3 - 27 \cdot m$	$9 \cdot m + A_3 - A_5 + 3 \cdot A_2$	$(-7/2) \cdot m$	$3 \cdot A_3 + A_1 + (47/2) \cdot m - 2 \cdot A_5 + 3 \cdot A_2$	$m - A_8$	A_8
$3 \cdot A_3 + A_1 + 19 \cdot m - 2 \cdot A_5 + 4 \cdot A_2$	$m - A_2$	$A_4 - A_1 - 19 \cdot m - 3 \cdot A_3 + 2 \cdot A_5 - 3 \cdot A_2$	$m - A_4$	$28 \cdot m + 4 \cdot A_3 + A_1 - 3 \cdot A_5 + 6 \cdot A_2$	$A_5 - 3 \cdot A_2 - 8 \cdot m - A_3$	$(9/2) \cdot m$	$2 \cdot A_5 - (45/2) \cdot m - A_1 - 3 \cdot A_2 - 3 \cdot A_3$	$(39/2) \cdot m + 3 \cdot A_3 - 2 \cdot A_5 + 4 \cdot A_2 + (1/2) \cdot A_1$	$2 \cdot A_5 - 4 \cdot A_2 - (1/2) \cdot A_1 - (37/2) \cdot m - 3 \cdot A_3$
$m - (1/2) \cdot A_1$	$(1/2) \cdot m + A_2 - A_8$	$(41/2) \cdot m + A_1 + 2 \cdot A_3 - 2 \cdot A_5 + 3 \cdot A_2 - A_7$	$16 \cdot m$	$(-21/2) \cdot m - A_2$	$2 \cdot A_5 - 2 \cdot A_2 + A_7 - 24 \cdot m - A_1 - 2 \cdot A_3$	$A_8 - 4 \cdot m$	$(9/2) \cdot m + (1/2) \cdot A_1 - A_2$	$(1/2) \cdot m$	$(1/2) \cdot m$
$(1/2) \cdot A_1$	$(1/2) \cdot m + A_8 - A_2$	$2 \cdot A_5 - 3 \cdot A_2 + A_7 - (39/2) \cdot m - A_1 - 2 \cdot A_3$	$(-15 \cdot m)$	$A_2 + (23/2) \cdot m$	$25 \cdot m + A_1 + 2 \cdot A_3 - 2 \cdot A_5 + 2 \cdot A_2 - A_7$	$5 \cdot m - A_8$	$A_2 - (7/2) \cdot m - (1/2) \cdot A_1$	$(1/2) \cdot m$	$(1/2) \cdot m$

Details:

It is a **cornered pandiagonal magic square of order 10** having **pandiagonal magic square of order 8** at the upper-left corner. It contains eight equal sums **magic rectangles of order 2×4** . The two magic rectangles of order 2×8 are of equal width and length. The magic squares of orders 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**. The magic sums of orders 10 and 8 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := 5 \times m$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 4 \times m$, where m is the width of the magic rectangle of order $m \times 2m$.

In order to bring this **pandiagonal magic square of order 10** without **decimal entries**, the width magic rectangle of order sum of order 2×4 should be multiple of 2. Also the first entry, i.e., A_1 , should be multiple of 2. See below two examples:

Example 5.8. *Let's consider the following example:*

10x10	pan	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160		10x10	pan	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180
160	446	-471	64	25	1232	-1257	372	-283	435	-403	160		180	496	-529	72	33	1376	-1409	416	-311	483	-447	180
160	-414	503	-32	7	-1200	1289	-340	315	-453	485	160		180	-460	565	-36	3	-1340	1445	-380	347	-511	547	180
160	-29	10	-417	500	-337	318	-1203	1286	-1060	1092	160		180	-29	10	-467	558	-373	354	-1347	1438	-1182	1218	180
160	61	22	449	-468	369	-286	1235	-1254	10	22	160		180	65	26	503	-522	409	-318	1383	-1402	14	22	180
160	-639	16	671	16	147	-770	979	-292	506	-474	160		180	-711	24	743	16	169	-856	1087	-328	564	-528	180
160	671	16	-639	16	-115	802	-947	324	4	28	160		180	747	12	-707	20	-133	892	-1051	364	8	28	180
160	-642	13	674	19	-950	321	-112	805	1	31	160		180	-714	13	754	19	-1058	357	-126	899	5	31	180
160	674	19	-642	13	982	-289	144	-773	685	-653	160		180	750	23	-718	17	1094	-321	162	-863	763	-727	180
160	27	-2	665	512	-349	-764	-97	136	16	16	160		180	31	0	747	576	-391	-860	-113	154	18	18	180
	5	34	-633	-480	381	796	129	-104	16	16	160			5	36	-711	-540	427	896	149	-118	18	18	180
©IJT	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160		©IJT	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 160$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 128$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 180$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 144$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.9. Let's consider the following *self-made magic square of order 10 with reduced entries*:

$(3/4)*M+A12+A16-(1/2)*A2-(3/2)*A1$	$M-A13+A8-A14$	$A15-A5+(11/4)*M+A13+2*A12-(5/2)*A2-(9/2)*A1-A9-A7+A16-A6$	$A5$	$(5/2)*A2+(9/2)*A1+A9+A7-A16-A15-(7/4)*M-A13-2*A12$	$A6$	$A16+A14-A8$	$(1/2)*A2+(3/2)*A1+A13-(3/4)*M-A12-2*A16$	$(1/2)*M-A13$	$A13$
$(3/2)*A2+A14+(1/2)*A1+A13-(3/2)*M-A8$	$2*A1-(1/4)*M-A12-A16$	$(5/2)*A2+(9/2)*A1+A9+A7-A16+A6-A15+A5-(9/4)*M-A13-2*A12$	$(1/2)*M-A5$	$A15+(9/4)*M+A13+2*A12-(5/2)*A2-(9/2)*A1-A9-A7+A16$	$(1/2)*M-A6$	$A12-A2-A14-A1+(5/4)*M$	$(3/2)*M+A16-(1/2)*A2-(3/2)*A1+A8-A13$	$(1/2)*M-A14$	$A14$
$A5-A13+A9+A7-5*A12-4*A16-A11+6*A2+11*A1+A6-(19/4)*M-2*A15$	$2*A15-A5+A13-A9-A7+5*A12+4*A16+A11-6*A2-11*A1-A6+(21/4)*M$	$A1$	$(3/2)*M-(1/2)*A2-(3/2)*A1-A4$	$A4-A3-(1/2)*M+(1/2)*A2+(1/2)*A1$	$A3$	$(7/2)*A2+(13/2)*A1+A9-2*A16+A6-A15-(5/2)*M-A13-3*A12$	$A15+3*M+A13+3*A12-(7/2)*A2-(13/2)*A1-A9+2*A16-A6$	$5*A2+9*A1-A15-A11+A9-4*M-4*A12-4*A16$	$(9/2)*M+4*A12+4*A16-5*A2-9*A1+A15+A11-A9$
$(3/2)*M+A15-A5+A12+A16+A11-(3/2)*A2-(5/2)*A1$	$(5/2)*A1+(3/2)*A2-A15-A11-A12-A16-M+A5$	$A4$	$(1/2)*M-(1/2)*A2-(1/2)*A1$	$A3+(3/2)*A2+A14+(1/2)*A1+A13-(3/2)*M$	$2*M-A3-A2-A14-A13-A4$	$A2+2*A1+A7-(3/4)*M-A12-A16$	$(5/4)*M+A12+A16-A2-2*A1-A7$	$(1/2)*M+A15+A13-(1/2)*A2-(3/2)*A1-A10-A9+A14$	$(1/2)*A2+(3/2)*A1+A10+A9-A14-A15-A13$
$3*M+3*A12-(7/2)*A2-(13/2)*A1+A15+A13-A9-A7+2*A16$	$A9+A7-3*A12-2*A16+(7/2)*A2+(13/2)*A1-(5/2)*M-A15-A13$	$A2+A3-A4$	$(3/2)*M-A3-(1/2)*A2-A14+(1/2)*A1-A13$	$(1/2)*M-(1/2)*A2-(1/2)*A1$	$A14+A13+A4-M$	$A3+A5+A12+2*A16+A14-2*A1-(1/4)*M$	$(3/4)*M-A3-A5-A12-2*A16-A14+2*A1$	$3*M+A15+A10+4*A12+4*A16+A11-(9/2)*A2-(15/2)*A1$	$(9/2)*A2+(15/2)*A1-(5/2)*M-A15-A10-4*A12-4*A16-A11$
$(5/4)*M+A12+A16-A2-2*A1-A6$	$A2+2*A1+A6-(3/4)*M-A12-A16$	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A3+(3/2)*A2+A14+(3/2)*A1+A13+A4-(5/2)*M$	$(5/2)*M-A4-A13-(3/2)*A2-A14-(1/2)*A1$	$A2$	$(9/2)*M+A15-A3-A5+A13+3*A12-(9/2)*A2-(13/2)*A1-A9-A7+A16-A14-A6$	$A3+A5-A13-3*A12+(9/2)*A2+(13/2)*A1+A9+A7-A16+A14+A6-4*M-A15$	$(1/2)*M-A15$	$A15$
$(3/2)*M+A8-A16-(3/2)*A2-A14-(1/2)*A1$	$(1/4)*M+A12+2*A16+A14-2*A1$	$A15+(9/4)*M+A13+2*A12-(5/2)*A2-(9/2)*A1-A9+A16-A6$	$(1/2)*M-A7$	$(13/4)*M+A15-A3-A5+2*A12+A16+A11-(7/2)*A2-A14-(9/2)*A1$	$A3+A5-A13-4*A12+6*A2+9*A1+A9+A7-2*A16-A11+A14+A6-5*M-2*A15$	$A2+A1-(1/4)*M-A12-A16$	$(3/2)*A1+(1/2)*A2-(1/2)*M-A8$	$(1/2)*M-A16$	$A16$
$(1/4)*M-A13-A12+(1/2)*A2+(3/2)*A1$	$A13-A16-A8$	$(5/2)*A2+(9/2)*A1+A9-A16+A6-A15-(7/4)*M-A13-2*A12$	$A7$	$A5-2*A12-A16-A11+(7/2)*A2+A14+(9/2)*A1-(11/4)*M-A15+A3$	$2*A15-A3-A5+(11/2)*M+A13+4*A12-6*A2-9*A1-A9-A7+2*A16+A11-A14-A6$	$A8$	$(3/4)*M+A12+A16-(1/2)*A2-(3/2)*A1$	$(1/2)*M+A16$	$(-A16)$
$(1/2)*M-(3/2)*A1+A13-(1/2)*A2+A12+A16$	$A12+A16+A2-A1+A14-(1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A9$	$(1/2)*M-A13-A2+A1+A10+A9+A11-A14$	$(1/2)*M-A10$	$(1/2)*M-A11$	$(1/2)*M-A12$	$(1/2)*A2+(3/2)*A1-2*A16-(1/2)*M-A12$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$
$(3/2)*A1-A13+(1/2)*A2-A12-A16$	$M-A12-A16-A2+A1-A14$	$A9$	$A13+A2-A1-A10-A9-A11+A14$	$A10$	$A11$	$A12$	$M+A12-(1/2)*A2-(3/2)*A1+2*A16$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$

Details:

It is a *cornered pandiagonal magic square of order 10 having double-digit pandiagonal magic square of order 8 at the upper-left corner*. It contains a *pandiagonal magic square of order 4*. The two magic rectangles of order 2×8 are of equal length and width. The magic squares of orders 4, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10, 8 and 4 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 2 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of magic square of order 4.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal magic square of order 10 without decimal entries*, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4. See below two examples:

Example 5.9. *Let's consider the following example:*

10x10	pan	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110		10x10	pan	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90
110	108	-21	163	23	-168	26	74	-117	-25	47	110		90	102	-29	141	23	-154	26	74	-111	-29	47	90
110	26	-87	-141	-1	190	-4	23	82	-28	50	110		90	38	-85	-123	-5	172	-8	13	70	-32	50	90
110	-518	540	12	21	-6	17	-266	288	-457	479	110		90	-480	498	12	9	-2	17	-246	264	-425	443	90
110	186	-164	20	9	75	-60	-66	88	74	-52	110		90	174	-156	20	5	87	-76	-60	78	70	-52	90
110	285	-263	11	-49	9	73	211	-189	511	-489	110		90	261	-243	11	-61	5	81	213	-195	487	-469	90
110	91	-69	1	63	-34	14	165	-143	-31	53	110		90	81	-63	-7	83	-54	14	129	-111	-35	53	90
110	-35	193	193	-7	188	-330	-85	-29	-34	56	110		90	-47	191	175	-11	162	-290	-83	-25	-38	56	90
110	-55	-41	-171	29	-166	352	32	108	78	-56	110		90	-57	-41	-157	29	-144	308	32	102	74	-56	90
110	144	130	-13	37	-16	-19	-22	-153	11	11	110		90	140	134	-17	33	-20	-23	-26	-149	9	9	90
	-122	-108	35	-15	38	41	44	175	11	11	110			-122	-116	35	-15	38	41	44	167	9	9	90
©IJT	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110		©IJT	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 110$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 88$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 44$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 90$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 72$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 36$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.10. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:

S-A13-A15-A1-A5-A18	A1	A2	A13+A15-A3+A5-A2-A4+A18	A3	A4	(5/6)*S-A18-A5-A16-A12-A15-A1+A14+A21	A18+A5-(1/2)*S+A16+A12+A15+A1-A14-A21	(1/3)*S-A19	A19
A5	A6	A7	A10+3*A18+A5-2*A20+2*A17+A12+3*A13+3*A15-A6+A8+A1-4*A14-3*A21+(1/3)*S-A9	A9-A10-3*A18-2*A5+2*A20-2*A17-4*A13-3*A15-A8+A4+A3-A1+4*A14+3*A21+(1/6)*S-A7	A13-A12+(1/2)*S-A3-A4	(1/3)*S-A13	A13	(1/2)*S-A13-A18	A13+A18-(1/6)*S
A13+A15-A6+A12-A2+A18-A21+(2/3)*S-2*A14	A3-A6+A11-A7+(1/6)*S	A20-A17-A12-2*A13-2*A15+A6-A8-A3-A1+3*A14+2*A21+(2/3)*S-A10-A11-2*A18-A5	A8	A9-2*A15-A17+A6-A12-2*A18+(1/3)*S+A14+A21+A20-A8-A13	A7-A9+A10+A2+3*A18+A5-2*A20+2*A17+A12+2*A13+3*A15+A8+A1-2*A14-2*A21-(5/6)*S	(1/3)*S-A15-A17-A18+A20+A4	A15+A17+A18-A20-A4	A13+A15+A16+A12+A1+A5+A18-A21-(1/6)*S-2*A14	A21+(1/2)*S+2*A14-A13-A15-A16-A12-A1-A5-A18
A2-2*A18-A5+A20-A17-A12-2*A13-2*A15+A6+A4+3*A14+2*A21-(1/3)*S-A11	A9	A10	2*A13+2*A15+A17-A6+A12+2*A18+A5+A1-3*A14-2*A21+A11-A20+A3	2*S/3-A3-A9-A1	2*S/3-A4-A2-A10	(1/3)*S-A14	A14	A14+A21+A20-(2/3)*S	S-A14-A21-A20
A11	A7-A9+A18+A5-A20+A17+2*A13+A15-A4-A3-3*A14-2*A21+(7/6)*S	A13-A9+A8+2*A15+A17+A12-(1/2)*S+2*A18+A5+A1-A14-A21-A20	A9-A10-A11-3*A18-2*A5+2*A20-2*A17-A12-3*A13-3*A15+A6-A8-A1+4*A14+3*A21+(1/3)*S	A8+2*A13+2*A15+A17-A6+A10+2*A18+A5-(2/3)*S+A1-A14-A21-A20	A20-A17-2*A13-2*A15-A8+A4+A3-A1+A14+A21+(2/3)*S-A7+A9-2*A18-A5	A21+2*A14-(2/3)*S	S-2*A14-A21	(1/3)*S-A20	A20
2*A18+A5+2*A15+A1-A14-A21-A20+A17+2*A13-(1/3)*S-A4	2*A21+3*A14-A5-2*A13-A15-A17-A18-A1+A20+A4-A11-(1/3)*S	(5/6)*S-2*A14+A3-A6+A13+A9+A11-A7-A2-A21	A2-3*A18-A5+A20-A17-A12-3*A13-3*A15+A6-A8+A4-A1+3*A14+2*A21+(1/3)*S	A7-A9+3*A18+A5-2*A20+2*A17+A12+3*A13+3*A15+A8-A4-A3+A1-4*A14-3*A21+(1/2)*S	A21+A14-A13-A15-A17-A18+A20	A13+2*A15+A16+A17+A12-(1/6)*S-A20+A1+A5-A4+2*A18-2*A21-2*A14	A20-A16-A17-A12-A13-2*A15+A4-A1+2*A14+2*A21+(1/2)*S-2*A18-A5	(1/3)*S-A21	A21
(1/3)*S+A16+A12-A14-A21-A13	(1/2)*S-A18-A15	2*A18+A5-(1/6)*S+A12+2*A15+A1-2*A14-A21-A20+A17+A13-A4	2*A14+A21+A20-A17-(2/3)*S	(1/3)*S-A12	A4-A18-A5+(2/3)*S-A16-A12-A15-A1+A14+A21	(1/6)*S	(1/6)*S	A18	(1/3)*S-A18
A14+A21+A13-A16-A12	A18+A15-(1/6)*S	(1/2)*S-A12-2*A15-A1+2*A14+A21+A20-A17-A13+A4-2*A18-A5	S-2*A14-A21-A20+A17	A12	A18+A5+A16+A12+A15+A1-A14-A21-A4-(1/3)*S	(1/6)*S	(1/6)*S	A19-A18-A5+(2/3)*S-A16-A12-A15-A1+A14+A21	A18+A5-(1/3)*S+A16+A12+A15+A1-A14-A21-A19
A19-A18-A5-A13-A15-A1+(5/6)*S	(1/3)*S-A15	(1/3)*S-A16	(1/3)*S-A17	A20-(2/3)*S+A21+2*A14-A12	A13+A15+A17+(1/6)*S+A18-A14-A20	(1/3)*S-A18	A18+A5-(1/3)*S+A16+A12+A15+A1-A14-A21-A19	(1/6)*S	(1/6)*S
A18+A5+A13+A15+A1-(1/2)*S-A19	A15	A16	A17	A12-A20-A21+S-2*A14	(1/6)*S-A18+A14+A20-A13-A15-A17	A18	A19-A18-A5+(2/3)*S-A16-A12-A15-A1+A14+A21	(1/6)*S	(1/6)*S

Details:

It is a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 having *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 8 at the upper-left corner. It contains a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×8 are of equal length and width in each case. The magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10, 8 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{3} \times S$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{4}{3} \times S$, where S is the magic sum of order 6.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 6 should be multiple of 6. See below two examples:

Example 5.10. *Let's consider the following example:*

10x10	pan	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	10x10	pan	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	
60	-66	11	12	52	13	14	-42	54	-17	29	60	70	-60	11	12	52	13	14	-37	51	-15	29	70
60	15	16	17	96	-100	-8	-11	23	-33	45	60	70	15	16	17	98	-99	-5	-9	23	-30	44	70
60	15	7	-95	18	-64	155	-24	36	65	-53	60	70	19	8	-91	18	-62	150	-22	36	64	-50	70
60	-43	19	20	81	-19	-22	-12	24	61	-49	60	70	-45	19	20	81	-15	-18	-10	24	57	-43	70
60	21	-10	100	-108	118	-85	55	-43	-18	30	60	70	21	-3	97	-106	114	-81	51	-37	-16	30	70
60	94	-7	-18	-103	88	-18	70	-58	-19	31	60	70	92	-9	-13	-101	91	-18	69	-55	-17	31	70
60	-18	-35	75	58	-10	-34	6	6	28	-16	60	70	-16	-32	74	54	-8	-30	7	7	28	-14	70
60	30	47	-63	-46	22	46	6	6	-19	31	60	70	30	46	-60	-40	22	44	7	7	-15	29	70
60	-43	-13	-14	-15	63	55	-16	31	6	6	60	70	-38	-11	-12	-13	59	56	-14	29	7	7	70
	55	25	26	27	-51	-43	28	-19	6	6	60		52	25	26	27	-45	-42	28	-15	7	7	70
©IJT	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	©IJT	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 60$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 48$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 36$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 70$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 56$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 42$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.11. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

A1	M-A1-A3	A3+A1-A2	A2-A1	(1/2)*M-A4	A4	A1+(1/4)*M-A5	(1/4)*M-A1+A5	(1/2)*M-A9	A9
A3	0	A2	M-A2-A3	(7/4)*M+A1	-(5/4)*M-A1	A6	(1/2)*M-A6	A10+A6-(1/4)*M	(3/4)*M-A10-A6
(1/2)*M-A1+A2-A3	A1-A2+(1/2)*M	(1/2)*M-A1	A1+A3-(1/2)*M	(3/4)*M-A1+A2-A8-A6	A1-A2+A8+A6-(1/4)*M	A7	(1/2)*M-A7	A7+A6-A1-A4	A4-A7+(1/2)*M-A6+A1
(1/2)*M-A2	A2-(1/2)*M+A3	(1/2)*M-A3	(1/2)*M	A8+A4+A6-2*M-A2	(5/2)*M+A2-A8-A4-A6	A4-A7-(5/4)*M-A1	A7+(7/4)*M+A1-A4	A4-A7+(1/2)*M-A6	A7+A6-A4
A1+A4-(1/4)*M	(-M-A1)	A8+A6-A2	(9/4)*M+A2-A6-A4-A8	(1/4)*M	(1/4)*M	A8	(1/2)*M-A8	(1/4)*M	(1/4)*M
(3/4)*M-A1-A4	A1+(3/2)*M	(1/2)*M+A2-A8-A6	A4-(7/4)*M+A8-A2+A6	(1/4)*M	(1/4)*M	A5-A4-A6+(5/2)*M-A8	A8-A5+A4+A6-2*M	(1/2)*M+A5-A6	A6-A5
A5	(3/4)*M-A6	(3/4)*M-A1-A7	A7+(3/2)*M+A1-A4	(1/2)*M-A8	A8-A5+A4+A6-2*M	(1/4)*M	(1/4)*M	(1/2)*M-A10	A10
(1/2)*M-A5	A6-(1/4)*M	A7+A1-(1/4)*M	A4-A1-A7-M	A8	(5/2)*M-A8+A5-A4-A6	(1/4)*M	(1/4)*M	A1+A9-A5	(1/2)*M+A5-A1-A9
A1+A9-(1/4)*M	M-A10-A6	(3/4)*M+A4-A7-A6	A7+A6-(1/4)*M-A4	(1/4)*M	A6-A5	A10	(1/2)*M+A5-A1-A9	(1/4)*M	(1/4)*M
(3/4)*M-A1-A9	A10+A6-(1/2)*M	A7+A6-(1/4)*M-A4	(3/4)*M+A4-A7-A6	(1/4)*M	(1/2)*M+A5-A6	(1/2)*M-A10	A1+A9-A5	(1/4)*M	(1/4)*M

Details:

It is a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 having *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of orders 8 and 6 at the upper-left corners. It contains a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 , 2×6 and 2×8 are of equal length and width in each case. The magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10, 8, 6 and 4 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 2 \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3}{2} \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 4.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4. See below two examples:

Example 5.11. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	10x10	pan	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80
70	10	6	11	1	1	13	3	11	-4	18	70	80	10	10	11	1	3	13	4	12	-2	18	80	
70	12	0	11	5	59	-45	15	-1	27	-13	70	80	12	0	11	9	66	-50	15	1	26	-10	80	
70	3	13	4	8	-10	24	16	-2	8	6	70	80	5	15	6	6	-7	23	16	0	8	8	80	
70	3	9	2	14	-22	36	-48	62	-4	18	70	80	5	7	4	16	-30	46	-53	69	-2	18	80	
70	16	-38	21	29	7	7	17	-3	7	7	70	80	15	-42	21	38	8	8	17	-1	8	8	80	
70	-2	52	-7	-15	7	7	39	-25	13	1	70	80	1	58	-5	-22	8	8	49	-33	15	1	80	
70	14	6	-5	55	-3	-25	7	7	-5	19	70	80	14	9	-2	61	-1	-33	8	8	-3	19	80	
70	0	8	19	-41	17	39	7	7	14	0	70	80	2	7	18	-45	17	49	8	8	14	2	80	
70	21	-6	3	11	7	1	19	0	7	7	70	80	20	-2	6	10	8	1	19	2	8	8	80	
	-7	20	11	3	7	13	-5	14	7	7	70		-4	18	10	6	8	15	-3	14	8	8	80	
©IJT	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	©IJT	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 70$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 56$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 42$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 28$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 80$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 64$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 48$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 32$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.12. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$(1/4)*M$	$2*A1-2*A5-2*A4+2*A3$	$(1/4)*M-A1+A5+A4-A3$	$A3+A1-(1/4)*M$	$M-2*A1+A5+A4-2*A3$	$(1/4)*M$	$A6$	$(1/2)*M-A6$	$(1/2)*M-A8$	$A8$
$(3/4)*M+2*A5+2*A4-2*A3-3*A1$	$A1$	$A2$	$M-A2-A5-A4$	$A5+A4-A1$	$3*A1-2*A5-2*A4+2*A3-(1/4)*M$	$(-3*M-A7)$	$(7/2)*M+A7$	$A11-A7-(13/4)*M$	$A7+(15/4)*M-A11$
$A3+(7/2)*M$	$(-(5/2)*M-A2-A5-A4)$	$A5+A4+(7/2)*M-A1$	$A1-(7/2)*M$	$A2+(7/2)*M$	$(-3*M-A3)$	$A5+(15/4)*M-A1$	$A1-A5-(13/4)*M$	$(15/4)*M-A6+A10-A1+A5$	$A6-A10-(13/4)*M+A1-A5$
$(1/2)*M-A3$	$A2+A5+A4-(1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*M+A1-A5-A4$	$M/2-A1$	$M/2-A2$	$A3$	$(1/4)*M+A1-A5$	$(1/4)*M-A1+A5$	$A7+A9+A1-A5-(1/4)*M$	$(3/4)*M-A1+A5-A7-A9$
$2*A3+3*A1-2*A5-2*A4-(15/4)*M$	$(-A1+4*M)$	$(-3*M-A2)$	$A2+A5+A4+3*M$	$A1-3*M-A5-A4$	$(17/4)*M-3*A1+2*A5+2*A4-2*A3$	$A7$	$(1/2)*M-A7$	$(1/2)*M-A9$	$A9$
$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-2*A1+2*A5+2*A4-2*A3$	$(1/4)*M+A1-A5-A4+A3$	$(3/4)*M-A3-A1$	$2*A1-A5-A4+2*A3-(1/2)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A6$	$A6$	$(1/2)*M-A10$	$A10$
$(1/2)*M-A6$	$(15/4)*M-A1+A7$	$A4$	$A5$	$A1-A7-(11/4)*M-A5-A4$	$A6$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A11$	$A11$
$A6$	$A1-A7-(13/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A4$	$(1/2)*M-A5$	$A5+A4+(13/4)*M+A7-A1$	$(1/2)*M-A6$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$A6+A8-(1/4)*M$	$(3/4)*M-A6-A8$
$A8$	$4*M-A11+A7-A1$	$A6-A10+A4$	$(1/2)*M-A7-A9+A5$	$A1-A5-A4+A9-(13/4)*M$	$A10$	$A11$	$(3/4)*M-A6-A8$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$
$(1/2)*M-A8$	$A11-A7+A1-(7/2)*M$	$A10+(1/2)*M-A4-A6$	$A7+A9-A5$	$(15/4)*M+A5+A4-A9-A1$	$(1/2)*M-A10$	$(1/2)*M-A11$	$A6+A8-(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$

Details:

It is a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 having *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of orders 8 and 6 at the upper-left corners. The magic square of order 6 is *single-digit bordered* with *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 in the inner part. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×8 are of equal length and width in each case. The magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10, 8, 6 and 4 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 2 \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3}{2} \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 4.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4. See below two examples:

Example 5.12. *Let's consider the following example:*

10x10	pan	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110		10x10	pan	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
110	11	-28	25	14	33	11	24	-2	-8	30	110		120	12	-28	26	13	37	12	24	0	-6	30	120
110	51	10	12	-7	29	-29	-159	181	-131	153	110		120	54	10	12	-3	29	-30	-171	195	-144	168	120
110	169	-161	183	-144	166	-147	176	-154	188	-166	110		120	183	-171	197	-158	180	-159	191	-167	203	-179	120
110	7	29	-7	12	10	15	0	22	38	-16	110		120	9	27	-5	14	12	15	1	23	37	-13	120
110	-183	166	-144	183	-161	205	27	-5	-11	33	110		120	-198	182	-156	195	-173	222	27	-3	-9	33	120
110	11	50	-3	8	-11	11	-2	24	-14	36	110		120	12	52	-2	11	-13	12	0	24	-12	36	120
110	-2	182	18	21	-177	24	11	11	-17	39	110		120	0	197	18	21	-188	24	12	12	-15	39	120
110	24	-160	4	1	199	-2	11	11	43	-21	110		120	24	-173	6	3	212	0	12	12	42	-18	120
110	30	154	6	-17	-139	36	39	-21	11	11	110		120	30	170	6	-15	-152	36	39	-18	12	12	120
	-8	-132	16	39	161	-14	-17	43	11	11	110			-6	-146	18	39	176	-12	-15	42	12	12	120
©IJT	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110		©IJT	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 110$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 88$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 66$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 44$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 96$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 72$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 48$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.13. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$(12/5)*m-3*A1-A3$	A1	$(3/5)*m$	A1	$A3+A1-A2$	A2	$m-A5-A2+A3$	$A5+A2-A3$	$m-A6$	A6
$3*A1-(7/5)*m+A3$	$m-A1$	$(2/5)*m$	$m-A1$	$m+A2-A3-A1$	$m-A2$	$A2-A4-A3+m$	$A4+A3-A2$	$(1/2)*m-A4+A9-A3+A2$	$(1/2)*m+A4-A9+A3-A2$
$(9/10)*m-A1$	$(3/2)*m-A3-A1$	$A3+A1+A1-(9/10)*m$	$(3/2)*m-A3-A1$	$2*A3-A2+3*A1-(3/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-A3-2*A1+A2$	$A3+A1-(2/5)*m$	$(7/5)*m-A3-A1$	$A5+A8+A1+A3-(7/5)*m$	$(12/5)*m-A1-A3-A5-A8$
$(1/10)*m+A1$	$A3+A1-(1/2)*m$	$(19/10)*m-A3-2*A1$	$A3+A1-(1/2)*m$	$(5/2)*m-2*A3-3*A1+A2$	$A3+2*A1-A2-(1/2)*m$	$(7/5)*m-A3-A1$	$A3+A1-(2/5)*m$	$(2/5)*m-A1+A7-A3+A4$	$(3/5)*m+A1-A7+A3-A4$
$(12/5)*m+A2-2*A3-3*A1$	$A3+A1-A2$	$(3/5)*m-A3+A2$	$A3+A1-A2$	A1	A3	A4	$m-A4$	$m-A7$	A7
$2*A3+3*A1-A2-(7/5)*m$	$m+A2-A3-A1$	$A3+(2/5)*m-A2$	$m-A3-A1+A2$	$m-A1$	$m-A3$	A5	$m-A5$	$m-A8$	A8
$A5+(19/10)*m-2*A3-3*A1+A2$	$A4+A3+A1-(1/2)*m-A2$	A1	$(3/5)*m-4*A1+4*A1$	$A1+(1/2)*m-A4$	$(1/2)*m+A3-A5$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$m-A9$	A9
$2*A3+3*A1-A2-A5-(9/10)*m$	$(3/2)*m+A2-A4-A3-A1$	$m-A1$	$(2/5)*m$	$(1/2)*m-A1+A4$	$A5+(1/2)*m-A3$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$A3+(1/2)*m-A2+A6-A5$	$A5-A6-A3+(1/2)*m+A2$
$(19/10)*m+A6-3*A1-A3$	$A1+A4-A9+A3-A2$	$m+A1-A5-A8$	$(8/5)*m-A7-A4$	$A7+A1-(1/2)*m$	$A8+A3-(1/2)*m$	A9	$A5-A6-A3+(1/2)*m+A2$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$
$3*A1+A3-A6-(9/10)*m$	$m+A9-A3+A2-A1-A4$	$A5+A8-A1$	$A7+A4-(3/5)*m$	$(-A7+(3/2)*m-A1)$	$(3/2)*m-A8-A3$	$m-A9$	$A3+(1/2)*m-A2+A6-A5$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$

Details:

It is a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 having *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of orders 8 at the upper-left corners. The magic square of order 6 is *astriped pandiagonal*. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and 2×8 are of equal length and width in each case. The magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10, 8 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := 5 \times m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 5 \times m$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 3 \times m$, where m is the width of magic rectangle of order 2×6 .

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the width of magic rectangles of order 2×6 should be multiple of 10. See below two examples:

Result 5.14. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$(1/4)*M$	A_6	$A_4+2*A_3+2*A_1+A_8+2*A_5-2*M$	$A_8+A_7+A_5-(1/2)*M$	$3*M-2*A_1-A_4-2*A_3-2*A_8-A_7-2*A_5$	$(1/2)*M-A_5$	$(1/2)*M-A_6$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A_9$	A_9
$(1/2)*M-A_6$	$(1/4)*M$	$3*M-2*A_5-2*A_1-2*A_8-2*A_3-2*A_4$	$A_5+A_1+A_8+A_3+A_4-(5/4)*M$	$A_3+A_1-(1/4)*M$	$A_5+A_8+A_4-(1/2)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	A_6	A_{12}	$(1/2)*M-A_{12}$
$(9/4)*M-A_4-2*A_3-A_1-A_8-2*A_5$	$A_1-(9/4)*M+2*A_5+2*A_8+2*A_3+2*A_4$	A_1	A_2	$(5/2)*M-A_5-A_2-A_8-2*A_3-A_4-2*A_1$	$A_1-(3/2)*M+A_5+A_8+2*A_3+A_4$	$(11/4)*M-A_1-2*A_5-2*A_8-2*A_3-2*A_4$	$A_4+2*A_3+A_1+A_8+2*A_5-(7/4)*M$	$(9/4)*M-A_1-2*A_5-2*A_8-A_4-2*A_3+A_{11}$	$A_1+2*A_5+2*A_8+A_4+2*A_3-A_{11}-(7/4)*M$
$(1/2)*M-A_7$	$(9/4)*M-A_1-A_3-A_4-2*A_5-2*A_8$	$(1/4)*M+A_5-A_2-A_1+A_8$	$(3/4)*M-A_5-A_8$	$2*A_1-(9/4)*M+2*A_5+2*A_8+2*A_3+A_4$	$(9/4)*M-A_1-2*A_5+A_2-2*A_8-2*A_3-A_4$	$A_1-(7/4)*M+2*A_5+2*A_8+A_3+A_4$	A_7	$(1/2)*M-A_{10}$	A_{10}
$A_4+2*A_3+A_1+2*A_8+A_7+2*A_5-(9/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A_3$	$2*A_1-2*M+A_5+A_2+A_8+2*A_3+A_4$	$2*M-A_5-A_1-A_8-2*A_3-A_4$	$M/2-A_1$	$M/2-A_2$	A_3	$(11/4)*M-A_4-2*A_3-A_1-2*A_8-A_7-2*A_5$	$A_1+A_{10}+2*A_5+2*A_8+A_4+2*A_3-(9/4)*M$	$(11/4)*M-A_4-2*A_3-A_1-A_{10}-2*A_5-2*A_8$
$(1/2)*M-A_8$	$(1/2)*M-A_4$	$(11/4)*M-2*A_1-2*A_5-2*A_8-2*A_3-A_4$	$A_1-(7/4)*M+2*A_5+2*A_8+2*A_3+A_4-A_2$	$(1/4)*M-A_5+A_2+A_1-A_8$	$A_5+A_8-(1/4)*M$	A_4	A_8	$(1/2)*M-A_{11}$	A_{11}
A_6	$(1/4)*M$	$2*A_5+2*A_1+2*A_8+2*A_3+2*A_4-(5/2)*M$	$(7/4)*M-A_5-A_1-A_8-A_3-A_4$	$(3/4)*M-A_3-A_1$	$M-A_5-A_8-A_4$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A_6$	$(1/2)*M-A_{12}$	A_{12}
$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A_6$	$(5/2)*M-A_4-2*A_3-2*A_1-A_8-2*A_5$	$M-A_8-A_7-A_5$	$2*A_1+A_4+2*A_3+2*A_8+A_7+2*A_5-(5/2)*M$	A_5	A_6	$(1/4)*M$	A_9	$(1/2)*M-A_9$
A_9	$(1/2)*M-A_{12}$	$2*A_1+2*A_5+2*A_8+A_4+2*A_3-A_{11}-2*M$	$A_8+A_5+A_{10}-(1/2)*M$	$3*M-2*A_1-A_{10}-2*A_5-2*A_8-A_4-2*A_3$	$(1/2)*M+A_{11}-A_5-A_8$	A_{12}	$(1/2)*M-A_9$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$
$(1/2)*M-A_9$	A_{12}	$(5/2)*M-A_4-2*A_3+A_{11}-2*A_1-2*A_5-2*A_8$	$M-A_{10}-A_8-A_5$	$2*A_1+A_{10}+2*A_5+2*A_8-(5/2)*M+A_4+2*A_3$	$A_5+A_8-A_{11}$	$(1/2)*M-A_{12}$	A_9	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$

Details:

It is a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 having *single-digit pandiagonal* magic squares of orders 6 and 8 at the upper-left corner with *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 in the inner part. The magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10, 8, 6 and 4 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 2 \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3}{2} \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 4.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4. See below two examples:

Example 5.14. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	10x10	pan	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
110	11	16	22	28	-13	7	6	11	3	19	110	100	10	16	30	30	-25	5	4	10	1	19	100
110	6	11	-10	16	13	25	11	16	22	0	110	100	4	10	-22	21	14	27	10	16	22	-2	100
110	0	32	11	12	3	18	-10	22	3	19	110	100	-9	41	11	12	-7	24	-21	29	-6	26	100
110	5	-5	21	0	29	-6	27	17	2	20	110	100	3	-14	20	-3	38	-15	34	17	0	20	100
110	35	9	19	4	11	10	13	-13	38	-16	110	100	44	7	27	-4	9	8	13	-24	47	-27	100
110	4	8	-7	28	1	22	14	18	1	21	110	100	2	6	-18	35	0	23	14	18	-1	21	100
110	16	11	32	6	9	-3	11	6	0	22	110	100	16	10	42	-1	6	-7	10	4	-2	22	100
110	11	6	0	-6	35	15	16	11	19	3	110	100	10	4	-10	-10	45	15	16	10	19	1	100
110	19	0	19	31	-16	10	22	3	11	11	110	100	19	-2	27	33	-28	8	22	1	10	10	100
	3	22	3	-9	38	12	0	19	11	11	110		1	22	-7	-13	48	12	-2	19	10	10	100
©IJT	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	©IJT	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 110$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 88$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 66$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 44$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 100$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 80$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 60$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 40$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.15. Let's consider the following *self-made magic square of order 10 with reduced entries*:

$(1/6)*S$	$A2+A4+10*S+A10+A11$	$A16+A14+A13+A2+A4+(11/3)*S+3*A11+A15+A10$	$(-(17/2)*S-A2-A4)$	$(-A16-A14-A13-A2-A4-5*S-3*A11-A15-A10)$	$(1/3)*S-A10$	$(1/2)*S-A11$	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/3)*S-A12$	$A12$
$(1/3)*S-A11$	$(-(59/6)*S-A2-A4-A10)$	$A1$	$A2$	$A3$	$(65/6)*S-A3+A10-A1+A4$	$(-4*A16-4*A13+(22/3)*S+4*(A16+A13-(11/6)*S))$	$A11$	$A17+A15+A16+A14+A13-(2/3)*S$	$S-A15-A17-A16-A14-A13$
$(13/6)*S-A16-A13$	$(29/6)*S-A1-3*A11-A14-A15$	$A4$	$A8+A6+2*A16+2*A14+2*A13-A3+A4+(29/6)*S+3*A11+2*A15+A10$	$A9-A6-A16-A14-A13-(5/6)*S-A15-A10$	$2*S/3-A8-A4-A9$	$A1-A4-(17/2)*S-A16-A13+A3$	$A16+A13-(11/6)*S$	$(1/3)*S-A13$	$A13$
$(1/3)*S$	$(9/2)*S+A14+A15+3*A11$	$A7-2*A13-A4+(37/6)*S-3*A11-2*A15-A8-A6-2*A16-A1-2*A14$	$A1-A7-A4-(26/3)*S-A9+A3$	$A5$	$A6-(25/6)*S-3*A11-A2-A5$	$A8+A9+2*A16+A14+2*A13-A3+A2+2*A4+(19/6)*S+3*A11+A15$	0	$(1/3)*S-A14$	$A14$
$(1/3)*S-A14-A15$	$A1-A7-(28/3)*S+A16+A14+A13+A15$	$A6$	$A9+A16+A14-A5+A13-A2-(21/2)*S+A15-A10$	$A7-A13-A3+A2+A4+(119/6)*S-A15+A10-A16-A1-A14$	$A3-(61/6)*S-A6-A4-A10$	$A5-A13+(67/6)*S-A15+A10-A9-A16-A14$	$A14+A15$	$(1/3)*S-A15$	$A15$
$(-3/2)*S$	$A7$	$A8$	$A2+A4+(53/6)*S-A14-A15+A5-A6$	$A6+A16+A1+2*A14-A7+A13-(10/3)*S+3*A11+2*A15+A10-A9$	$A9$	$(-A8-A16-A1-A14-A5-A13-A2-A4-(9/2)*S-3*A11-A15-A10)$	$(11/6)*S$	$(1/3)*S-A16$	$A16$
$A16+A14+A13+A15+A11-(2/3)*S$	$A2+A4+(65/6)*S-A16-A14-A13-A15+A10$	$2*A16+2*A14+2*A13+(31/6)*S+2*A15+3*A11-A7$	$A7-A4-A8+(13/2)*S-3*A16-2*A14-3*A13-2*A15-3*A11-A2-A1$	$A16+A13-(44/3)*S-A2-A4-A5-A10-3*A11$	$A2+A1+A4+A8+(23/6)*S+A5+3*A11$	$A16+A14+A13+A15-(1/3)*S$	$S-A16-A14-A13-A15-A11$	$(1/3)*S-A17$	$A17$
$(1/6)*S$	$(-A2-(29/3)*S-A4-A10-A11)$	$(-(10/3)*S-A4-A16-A14-A13-A15-A10-3*A11-A2)$	$A2+A4+(53/6)*S$	$A2+A4+(16/3)*S+A16+A14+A13+A15+A10+3*A11$	$A10$	$(-(1/6)*S+A11)$	$(1/6)*S$	$A12$	$(1/3)*S-A12$
$A12$	$11*S-A15+A2+A4+A10-A17-A16-A14-A13$	$A13+A2+A4+(11/2)*S+A14+A15+3*A11+A10$	$A14-A2-A4-(17/2)*S$	$(-5*S-A10-A2-A4-A16-2*A14-A13-A15-3*A11)$	$A16-A10-(3/2)*S$	$A17-(1/2)*S+A16+A14+A13+A15$	$(1/3)*S-A12$	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$
$(1/3)*S-A12$	$A17+A16+A14+A13-(32/3)*S+A15-A2-A4-A10$	$(-A13-A2-A4-(31/6)*S-A14-A15-3*A11-A10)$	$(53/6)*S+A2+A4-A14$	$A10+A2+A4+(16/3)*S+A16+2*A14+A13+A15+3*A11$	$(11/6)*S+A10-A16$	$(5/6)*S-A16-A14-A13-A15-A17$	$A12$	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$

Details:

It is a **cornered pandiagonal magic square of order 10** having **single-digit pandiagonal magic squares of orders 8** at the upper-left corner with **pandiagonal magic square of order 6** in the inner part. The magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**. The magic sums of orders 10, 8 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{3} \times S$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{4}{3} \times S$, where S is the magic sum of order 6.

In order to bring this **pandiagonal magic square of order 10** without **decimal entries**, the magic sum of order 6 should be multiple of 6. See below two examples:

Example 5.15. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	10x10	pan	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60		
50	5	367	317	-281	-357	-10	-6	5	-12	22	50	60	6	427	339	-332	-387	-8	-3	6	-10	22	60
50	-11	-341	11	12	13	335	0	21	105	-95	50	60	-9	-400	11	12	13	400	0	21	101	-89	60
50	16	22	14	459	-140	-31	-294	-6	-13	23	50	60	29	51	14	488	-145	-27	-345	-17	-11	23	60
50	10	247	-116	-286	15	-199	369	0	-14	24	50	60	12	274	-79	-338	15	-224	388	0	-12	24	60
50	-39	-188	16	-245	536	-342	253	49	-15	25	50	60	-37	-244	16	-308	655	-403	320	49	-13	25	60
50	-45	17	18	241	121	19	-386	55	-16	26	50	60	-54	17	18	294	101	19	-413	66	-14	26	60
50	99	273	87	-151	-515	248	88	-89	-17	27	50	60	95	338	56	-112	-603	271	86	-83	-15	27	60
50	5	-357	-307	291	367	20	16	5	22	-12	50	60	6	-415	-327	344	399	20	15	6	22	-10	60
50	22	251	346	-257	-381	-39	110	-12	5	5	50	60	22	317	379	-308	-411	-48	107	-10	6	6	60
	-12	-241	-336	267	391	49	-100	22	5	5	50		-10	-305	-367	320	423	60	-95	22	6	6	60
©IJT	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	©IJT	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 50$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 40$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 30$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 60$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 48$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 36$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.16. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

M-A3-A4	$A6 - (1/3)*M + A9 + A2 - A12 - A11 + A5 - A1 + A7$	$A12 + A11 + A3 - A5 + A4 + A1 - (1/3)*M - A9 - A2$	$A12 + A11 + A3 - A5 + A4 - (2/3)*M + 2*A1 + A8 - A7 - A9 - A2$	$(4/3)*M - A8 + A7 + A9 + A2 - A12 - A11 - A3 + A5 - A4 - 2*A1$	$(1/3)*M - A1 + A9$	$(5/3)*M + A1 - A5 - A2 - A6 - A7 - A9$	$A5 + A2 - (1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M - A13$	A13
$(2/3)*M - A6$	A1	$M/3 - A1 + A2$	$2*M/3 - A2$	A3	$A12 + A11 - A5 + A4 + A1 - (1/3)*M - A2$	$(4/3)*M + A2 - A12 - A11 - A3 + A5 - A4 - A1$	A6	$(1/3)*M + A9 + A7 + A2 - A12 - A11 + A10 - A3 + A5 - A4 - A1$	$(1/3)*M - A9 - A7 - A2 + A12 + A11 - A10 + A3$
$(2/3)*M - A7$	M-A1-A2	M/3	$A2 + A1 - M/3$	$(5/3)*M - 2*A3 + A2 - A12 - A11 + A5 - A4 - A1$	M/3	$A12 + A11 + 2*A3 - A5 + A4 - M + A1 - A2$	A7	$A1 + A11 + A3 + A4 - M$	$(5/3)*M - A3 - A4 - A1 - A11$
$(2/3)*M - A8$	A2	$M/3 + A1 - A2$	$2*M/3 - A1$	$A12 + A11 + A3 - A5 + A4 - (2/3)*M + A1 - A2$	$M + A2 - A12 - A11 + A5 - A4 - A1$	$2*M/3 - A3$	A8	$(2/3)*M - A14$	A14
A8	A4	$(1/3)*M - A4 + A7 + A9 - A1$	$(2/3)*M - A7 - A9 + A1$	$A9 + A2 - A12 - A11 - A3 + A5 - A4 + (2/3)*M - A1 + A7$	$A12 + A11 + A3 + A4 + A1 - A7 - (1/3)*M - A9 - A2$	$2*M/3 - A5$	$(2/3)*M - A8$	$A14 + (4/3)*M - 2*A9 - 2*A7$	$2*A9 + 2*A7 - A14 - (2/3)*M$
$(2/3)*M - A9$	$M - A4 - A7 - A9 + A1$	M/3	$A7 + A9 - A1 + A4 - (1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M - A9 - A2 + A12 + A11 + A3 - 2*A5 + A4 + A1 - A7$	M/3	$2*A5 + (1/3)*M + A9 + A2 - A12 - A11 - A3 - A4 - A1 + A7$	A9	$A7 + A9 + A2 - A11 + A5 - A1 - (1/3)*M$	$M - A2 + A11 - A5 + A1 - A7 - A9$
$A5 + A2 + A6 + A7 + A9 - 2*M + A4 + A3$	$A7 + A9 - A1$	$(1/3)*M + A4 - A7 - A9 + A1$	$2*M/3 - A4$	A5	$M + A9 + A2 - A12 - A11 - A3 - A4 - A1 + A7$	$A12 + A11 + A3 - A5 + A4 + A1 - A7 - A9 - A2$	$(8/3)*M - A5 - A2 - A6 - A7 - A9 - A4 - A3$	$A1 - A2 + A12 + A11 - A10 + A3 - A5 + A4 - (1/3)*M$	$A2 - A12 - A11 + A10 - A3 + A5 - A4 + M - A1$
M-A5-A2	$M - A6 - A2 + A12 + A11 - A5 + A1 - A7 - A9$	$M + A2 - A12 - A11 - A3 + A5 - A4 - A1 + A9$	$(4/3)*M - A8 + A7 + A9 + A2 - A12 - A11 - A3 + A5 - A4 - 2*A1$	$A12 + A11 + A3 - A5 + A4 - (2/3)*M + 2*A1 + A8 - A7 - A9 - A2$	$(1/3)*M + A1 - A9$	$A5 + A2 + A6 + A7 + A9 - M - A1$	$A3 + A4 - (1/3)*M$	$A13 - A2 - A3 + (4/3)*M - A5 - A4$	$A2 + A3 - (2/3)*M + A5 + A4 - A13$
$A13 + (2/3)*M - A3 - A4$	$(2/3)*M - A10$	$(2/3)*M - A11$	$2*A12 + 2*A11 + 2*A3 - 2*A5 + 2*A4 + 2*A1 - 2*A7 + A14 - (2/3)*M - 2*A9 - 2*A2$	$2*A9 + 2*A7 - A14 - 2*A1$	$(2/3)*M - A12$	$(2/3)*M + A2 - A12 - A11 + A10 - A3 + A5 - A4$	$A2 + A5 - A13$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$
$A3 + A4 - A13$	A10	A11	$2*A9 + 2*A2 - 2*A12 - 2*A11 - 2*A3 + 2*A5 - 2*A4 + (4/3)*M - 2*A1 + 2*A7 - A14$	$A14 + (2/3)*M + 2*A1 - 2*A9 - 2*A7$	A12	$A12 + A11 - A10 + A3 - A5 + A4 - A2$	$A13 - A2 + (2/3)*M - A5$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$

Details:

It is a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 having *single-digit pandiagonal* magic squares of orders 8 at the upper-left corner with *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 formed by four equal sums *semi-magic* squares of order 3 in the inner part. The magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10, 8 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10}{3} \times M$, $S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8}{3} \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 2 \times M$, where M is the *semi-magic* sum of order 3.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples:

Example 5.16. *Let's consider the following example:*

10x10	pan	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	10x10	pan	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180
160	11	15	45	43	-11	40	-36	21	-15	47	160	180	17	13	43	39	-3	42	-26	19	-11	47
160	6	11	19	18	17	63	-32	26	22	10	160	180	10	11	21	22	17	61	-24	26	24	12
160	3	23	16	9	-33	16	65	29	41	-9	160	180	7	29	18	7	-23	18	59	29	35	1
160	0	14	13	21	64	-31	15	32	-18	50	160	180	4	14	15	25	60	-25	19	32	-14	50
160	32	20	49	-21	0	39	9	0	-14	46	160	180	32	20	51	-17	4	37	13	4	-6	42
160	-3	-25	16	57	25	16	7	35	33	-1	160	180	1	-19	18	55	27	18	9	35	31	5
160	68	53	-17	12	23	-7	32	-36	42	-10	160	180	56	53	-15	16	23	-1	32	-20	40	-4
160	11	17	-13	-11	43	-8	68	21	37	-5	160	180	17	23	-7	-3	39	-6	62	19	45	-9
160	42	-6	-9	82	56	-12	-15	-10	16	16	160	180	46	-2	-5	78	56	-8	-11	-10	18	18
160	-10	38	41	-50	-24	44	47	42	16	16	160	180	-10	38	41	-42	-20	44	47	46	18	18
©IJT	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	©IJT	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 160$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 128$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 96$ and $T_{3 \times 3} := 48$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 180$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 144$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 108$ and $T_{3 \times 3} := 54$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.17. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$(1/2)^*m$	$A2+2^*A1-A10-A8+A6-(2/5)^*m$	$m-A5$	$(12/5)^*m-A2-A1-A3-A4$	$A3+A4+A1-m$	$A5+A10+A8-2^*A1$	$m-A6$	$(1/2)^*m$	$m-A7$	$A7$
$A3+A10+A8-(1/2)^*m-A6$	$(12/5)^*m-A2-2^*A1-A3$	$A1$	$(3/5)^*m$	$A2$	$m+A1-A10-A8$	$A3+A10+A8-m$	$(3/2)^*m-A3-A10-A8+A6$	$A10+A11+A8-m$	$2^*m-A10-A11-A8$
$(1/2)^*m+A5-A1$	$2^*A1-(7/5)^*m+A3+A2$	$m-A1$	$(2/5)^*m$	$m-A2$	$A10+A8-A1$	$2^*m-A3-A10-A8$	$(1/2)^*m-A5+A1$	$m-A8$	$A8$
$A4$	$(9/10)^*m-A1$	$(3/2)^*m-A3-A2$	$A3+A2+A1-(9/10)^*m$	$(3/2)^*m-A3-A1$	$A3-(1/2)^*m+2^*A1-A10-A8+A2$	$(1/2)^*m-A2-A1+A10+A8$	$m-A4$	$A9$	$m-A9$
$m-A4$	$(1/10)^*m+A1$	$A3+A2-(1/2)^*m$	$(19/10)^*m-A3-A2-A1$	$A3+A1-(1/2)^*m$	$(3/2)^*m-A3-A2-2^*A1+A10+A8$	$A2+A1-A10-A8+(1/2)^*m$	$A4$	$m-A9$	$A9$
$(3/2)^*m-A5+A1-A10-A8$	$(7/5)^*m-2^*A1-A3+A10+A8-A2$	$m+A1-A10-A8$	$A10+A8-(2/5)^*m$	$A2+m-A10-A8$	$A1$	$A3$	$A5-A1+A10+A8-(1/2)^*m$	$m-A10$	$A10$
$(1/2)^*m+A6-A3$	$A3+A2+2^*A1-(2/5)^*m-A10-A8$	$A10+A8-A1$	$(7/5)^*m-A10-A8$	$A10+A8-A2$	$m-A1$	$m-A3$	$(1/2)^*m+A3-A6$	$m-A11$	$A11$
$(1/2)^*m$	$(7/5)^*m-A2-2^*A1+A10+A8-A6$	$A5$	$A2+A1+A3-(7/5)^*m+A4$	$2^*m-A3-A4-A1$	$m+2^*A1-A5-A10-A8$	$A6$	$(1/2)^*m$	$A7$	$m-A7$
$A7$	$(1/10)^*m-A10-A11-A8+2^*A1+A3+A2$	$(1/2)^*m-A1+A8$	$(12/5)^*m-A3-A1-A9-A2$	$A1+A3+A9-m$	$(1/2)^*m+A10-A1$	$(1/2)^*m+A11-A3$	$m-A7$	$(1/2)^*m$	$(1/2)^*m$
$m-A7$	$(9/10)^*m+A10+A11+A8-2^*A1-A3-A2$	$(1/2)^*m+A1-A8$	$A3+A1+A9+A2-(7/5)^*m$	$2^*m-A1-A3-A9$	$(1/2)^*m-A10+A1$	$(1/2)^*m-A11+A3$	$A7$	$(1/2)^*m$	$(1/2)^*m$

Details:

It is a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 having *single-digit pandiagonal* magic squares of orders 8 at the upper-left corner with *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 formed by three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 in the inner part . The magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10, 8 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := 5 \times m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4 \times m$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 3 \times m$, where m is the width of magic rectangle of order 2×6 .

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the width of magic rectangles of order 2×6 should be multiple of 10. See below two examples:

5.4 Single-Digit Bordered Pandiagonal Magic Squares

Result 5.18. *Let's consider the following self-made magic square of order 10 with reduced entries:*

$(1/4)*M$	$M-A11-A14$	$M-A15-A12-A13$	$A11$	$A12$	$A13$	$A14$	$A15$	0	$(1/4)*M$
$(3/4)*M-A2-A4-A3$	$A3+A11-M+A14+A2+A4$	$A12-A11+A9+(5/4)*M-A14-A2-A4-A1-A3$	$A5-A7+A8-A6+A13-A9-(1/4)*M+A2+A1$	$(-A5+A7-A8+A6-A12-A13+M-A2)$	$A2$	$A3$	$A4$	$M-A2-A3-A4$	$A3-(1/4)*M+A2+A4$
$A15+A13-A9$	$A1$	$(3/4)*M-A12-A9$	$A7+A3-A8+A6-A13+A11+A9-(3/4)*M+A14+A4-A5$	$A5-A7-A3+A8-A6+A12+A13-A11+M-A14-A4-A1$	$A9+(1/4)*M-A2+A4-A13$	$A13-A9+(3/4)*M-A4-A3$	$A9+(1/4)*M-A13$	$A3+A13-A9-(1/4)*M+A2$	$(1/2)*M+A9-A15-A13$
$A3-(3/4)*M+A14+A2+A4$	$A7-A8+A6-A13+A9+(3/4)*M-A2-A1-A5$	$A5-A7+A8-A6+A12+A13-(1/2)*M+A2$	$(3/2)*M-A14-A2-A4-A3-A11$	$A3-A12+A11-A9-(3/4)*M+A14+A2+A4+A1$	$M/2-A4$	$A2+A3+A4-M/2$	$M/2-A2$	$M/2-A3$	$(5/4)*M-A14-A2-A4-A3$
$A9$	$A5-A7-A3+A8-A6+A13-A11-A9+(5/4)*M-A14-A4$	$A7+A3-A8+A6-A12-A13+A11-(1/2)*M+A14+A4+A1-A5$	$M/2-A1$	$(-1/4)*M+A12+A9$	$(1/4)*M+A13-A9$	$(3/4)*M-A3-A13-A2+A9$	$A13-A9+(1/4)*M+A2-A4$	$A3-A13+A9-(1/4)*M+A4$	$(1/2)*M-A9$
$(1/2)*M-A5+A3+A6-A13-A10+A4$	$A5-A6+A11-(3/4)*M+A10+A14$	$A12+A13-A11+M-A14-A4-A5-A3$	$A5$	$A3+A6+(3/4)*M-A12-A13-A10+A4-A5$	$(1/4)*M+A5-A3-A6+A10-A4$	$(-A5+A3+A6+A4-A8)$	$A7$	$(3/4)*M-A10+A8-A7$	$A5-A3-A6+A13+A10-A4$
$M-A10-A14$	$A6$	$A3+(3/4)*M-A12-A13-A10+A4$	$A11-(3/4)*M+A10+A14$	$A12+A13-A11+M-A14-A4-A3-A6$	$A8$	$(3/4)*M-A10$	$(1/4)*M-A7+A5-A3-A6+A10-A4+A8$	$A7-A5+A3+A6+A4-2*A8$	$A10+A14-(1/2)*M$
$A5-A3-A6-A15+(1/2)*M+A10-A4$	$M/2-A5$	$A5-(1/4)*M-A3-A6+A12+A13+A10-A4$	$A6-A11+(5/4)*M-A10-A14-A5$	$A5+A3-A12-A13+A11-(1/2)*M+A14+A4$	$M/2-A7$	$A7-(1/4)*M+A10-A8$	$(1/4)*M-A5+A3+A6-A10+A4$	$A8+A5+(1/2)*M-A3-A6-A4$	$A3+A6+A15-A10+A4-A5$
$A10$	$(5/4)*M-A10-A14-A11$	$A3+A6-A12-A13+A11-(1/2)*M+A14+A4$	$M/2-A6$	$A12+A13+A10-A4-A3-(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M+A7-A5+A3+A6-A10+A4-A8$	$2*A8+A5+(1/2)*M-A3-A6-A4-A7$	$M/2-A8$	$(-1/4)*M+A10$	$(1/2)*M-A10$
$(1/4)*M$	$A11+A14-(1/2)*M$	$A15+A12+A13-(1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A11$	$(1/2)*M-A12$	$(1/2)*M-A13$	$(1/2)*M-A14$	$(1/2)*M-A15$	$(1/2)*M$	$(1/4)*M$

Details:

It is a single-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square of order 10 embedded with a pandiagonal magic square of order 8. It contains four equal sums pandiagonal magic square of order 4. The magic squares of orders 4, 8 and 10 are pandiagonal. The magic sums of orders 10, 8 and 4 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := 2 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 4.

In order to bring this pandiagonal magic square of order 10 without decimal entries, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4. See below two examples:

Example 5.18. *Let's consider the following example:*

10x10	pan	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	11	-24	-63	31	33	35	37	39	0	11	110
110	-12	69	-9	21	-37	13	15	17	-1	34	110
110	47	11	-27	59	1	7	9	3	25	-25	110
110	49	1	59	-47	31	5	23	9	7	-27	110
110	27	-37	21	11	49	19	-3	15	13	-5	110
110	-8	62	-7	19	-30	6	9	23	6	30	110
110	-22	21	-32	64	-9	25	4	8	7	44	110
110	-22	3	52	-40	29	-1	16	16	13	44	110
110	29	-42	31	1	54	14	15	-3	18	-7	110
	11	46	85	-9	-11	-13	-15	-17	22	11	110
©IJT	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110

10x10	pan	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	12	-20	-59	31	33	35	37	39	0	12	120
120	-9	65	-4	20	-33	13	15	17	3	33	120
120	47	11	-24	56	5	8	12	4	24	-23	120
120	46	4	57	-41	28	7	21	11	9	-22	120
120	27	-32	19	13	48	20	0	16	12	-3	120
120	-6	59	-3	19	-27	7	9	23	9	30	120
120	-18	21	-29	61	-5	25	7	9	7	42	120
120	-20	5	51	-35	27	1	15	17	15	44	120
120	29	-37	29	3	53	15	17	-1	17	-5	120
	12	44	83	-7	-9	-11	-13	-15	24	12	120
©IJT	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 110$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 88$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 44$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 96$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 48$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.19. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$m/2$	$A_6+A_7-A_{10}$	$2^*m-A_6-A_7-A_9$	$2^*m-A_6-A_7-A_8$	A_6	A_7	A_8	A_9	A_{10}	$m/2$
$(3/2)^*m+A_{10}-A_6-A_7+A_4-A_1-A_3$	$A_1+A_3-A_4$	$A_3+A_{10}+A_1-(3/2)^*m+A_5$	2^*m	$(3/2)^*m-2^*A_1-2^*A_3-A_{10}+A_4-A_5$	$A_1-A_2+A_3-A_{10}-A_4+(3/2)^*m-A_5$	$A_3+2^*A_{10}+A_1-3^*m+2^*A_5+A_2$	$(3/2)^*m-A_5+A_6+A_7-A_3-A_{10}-A_1$	$2^*m+A_4-A_1-A_3-A_6-A_7$	$A_6+A_7-(1/2)^*m-A_4+A_1+A_3-A_{10}$
$m-A_5+A_6+A_7+A_9-A_3-A_{10}-A_1$	$m-A_1-A_3+A_4$	$(5/2)^*m-A_3-A_{10}-A_1-A_5$	$(-m)$	$2^*A_1+2^*A_3+A_{10}-A_4-(1/2)^*m+A_5$	$A_2-A_3+A_{10}-A_1+A_4-(1/2)^*m+A_5$	$4^*m-2^*A_5-A_2-A_1-A_3-2^*A_{10}$	$A_3+A_{10}+A_1-(1/2)^*m+A_5-A_6-A_7$	$A_1+A_3+A_6+A_7-m-A_4$	$A_3+A_{10}+A_1+A_5-A_6-A_7-A_9$
$2^*A_6+2^*A_7+A_8-(5/2)^*m-2^*A_4+2^*A_1+A_3$	$A_4-A_1-A_6-A_7$	$2^*A_3+A_{10}+A_1+(1/2)^*m+A_5-A_6-A_7$	$A_6+A_7-A_3$	$(3/2)^*m-A_3-A_{10}-A_5+A_6+A_7-A_4$	$A_3+A_{10}+A_4+(1/2)^*m+A_5-2^*A_6-2^*A_7$	A_3	$A_2-A_3+A_{10}-(3/2)^*m+A_5+A_6+A_7$	$3^*m-2^*A_5+A_6+A_7-A_4-A_2-A_3-2^*A_{10}$	$(7/2)^*m-2^*A_6-2^*A_7-A_8+2^*A_4-2^*A_1-A_3$
$A_3+A_{10}+2^*A_1-2^*m+A_5+A_7-A_4$	$m+A_1+A_6+A_7-A_4$	$(1/2)^*m-2^*A_3-A_{10}-A_1-A_5+A_6+A_7$	$A_3-A_6-A_7+m$	$A_3+A_{10}-(1/2)^*m+A_5-A_6-A_7+A_4$	$(1/2)^*m-A_5+2^*A_6+2^*A_7-A_3-A_{10}-A_4$	$m-A_3$	$A_3-A_{10}+(5/2)^*m-A_5-A_6-A_7-A_2$	$A_2+A_3+2^*A_{10}-2^*m+2^*A_5-A_6-A_7+A_4$	$3^*m-A_3-A_{10}-2^*A_1-A_5-A_7+A_4$
$(3/2)^*m+2^*A_4-A_1-A_6-2^*A_7$	$A_{10}-A_1+(1/2)^*m+A_5-A_6-A_7+A_2$	$2^*m+A_4-A_2-A_1-A_6-A_7$	$A_1-A_{10}-A_4-(1/2)^*m-A_5+2^*A_6+2^*A_7$	A_1	$2^*m-A_1-A_6-A_7$	$A_{10}+(1/2)^*m+A_5-A_6-A_7+A_4-A_1$	$3^*A_6+3^*A_7-A_3-2^*A_{10}-A_4-m-2^*A_5$	$2^*A_1+A_3+A_{10}+(1/2)^*m+A_5-A_6-A_7$	$A_6+2^*A_7-2^*A_4+A_1-(1/2)^*m$
$3^*m-A_6-A_7-A_8+A_4-A_5-A_1-A_{10}$	$A_1-A_2-A_{10}+(1/2)^*m-A_5+A_6+A_7$	$A_1+A_6+A_7-m-A_4+A_2$	$(3/2)^*m-A_1+A_{10}+A_4+A_5-2^*A_6-2^*A_7$	$m-A_1$	$A_1+A_6+A_7-m$	$(1/2)^*m+A_1-A_{10}-A_5+A_6+A_7-A_4$	$2^*m+A_3+2^*A_{10}+A_4+2^*A_5-3^*A_6-3^*A_7$	$(1/2)^*m-2^*A_1-A_3-A_{10}-A_5+A_6+A_7$	$A_6+A_7+A_8-A_4+A_5+A_1+A_{10}-2^*m$
$(3/2)^*m-A_9-A_4$	$A_{10}+(1/2)^*m+A_5-A_6-A_7$	$A_6+A_7-A_4$	$A_4+(3/2)^*m-A_5-A_2-A_{10}$	A_2	$A_3+2^*A_{10}+A_1+m+2^*A_5-2^*A_6-2^*A_7$	$2^*A_6+2^*A_7-(1/2)^*m-A_4-A_{10}-A_1-A_5-A_3$	A_4	$(3/2)^*m-A_5-A_{10}$	$A_9+A_4-(1/2)^*m$
A_5	$(1/2)^*m-A_5+A_6+A_7-A_{10}$	$m-A_6-A_7+A_4$	$A_2+A_{10}-A_4-(1/2)^*m+A_5$	$m-A_2$	$2^*A_6+2^*A_7-A_1-A_3-2^*A_{10}-2^*A_5$	$(3/2)^*m+A_3-2^*A_6-2^*A_7+A_4+A_{10}+A_1+A_5$	$m-A_4$	$A_{10}-(1/2)^*m+A_5$	$m-A_5$
$m/2$	$m+A_{10}-A_6-A_7$	$A_6+A_7+A_9-m$	$A_6+A_7+A_8-m$	$m-A_6$	$m-A_7$	$m-A_8$	$m-A_9$	$m-A_{10}$	$m/2$

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 embedded with a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 8. It contains eight equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 . The magic squares of orders 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10 and 8 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := 5 \times m$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := 4 \times m$, where m is the width of magic rectangle of order $m \times 2m$.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the width of magic rectangle of order $m \times 2m$ should be multiple of 2. See below two examples:

Example 5.19. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190
190	19	17	-14	-11	26	29	32	35	38	19	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190
190	32	8	32	76	-40	-10	50	23	13	6	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190
190	39	30	6	-38	78	48	-12	15	25	-1	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190
190	46	-46	70	38	14	7	17	56	-4	-8	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190
190	33	84	-32	0	24	31	21	-18	42	5	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190
190	2	28	16	21	11	10	34	-32	64	36	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190
190	-25	10	22	17	27	28	4	70	-26	63	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190
190	2	25	35	2	14	78	-18	20	-4	36	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190
190	23	13	3	36	24	-40	56	18	42	15	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190
	19	21	52	49	12	9	6	3	0	19	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190
©IJT	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190

10x10	pan	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
210	21	17	-6	-3	26	29	32	35	38	21	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
210	38	8	26	84	-34	-4	38	29	21	4	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
210	43	34	16	-42	76	46	4	13	21	-1	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
210	36	-46	72	38	20	9	17	50	8	6	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
210	25	88	-30	4	22	33	25	-8	34	17	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
210	8	30	24	19	11	18	36	-36	66	34	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
210	-13	12	18	23	31	24	6	78	-24	55	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
210	8	27	35	8	14	82	-20	20	2	34	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
210	23	15	7	34	28	-40	62	22	40	19	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
	21	25	48	45	16	13	10	7	4	21	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210
©IJT	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 190$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := 152$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 210$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := 168$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.20. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

M/4	M-A12-A13-A8	A8	A9	A10	M-A10-A9-A11	A11	A12	A13	M/4
$(5/4)*M - A1 + A6 + A13 + A12 + A8$	$A1 - (3/2)*M - A6$	$(1/2)*M - A5$	$A5 + A4 + 2*M + A6 - A12 - A8 - A3$	$A3 - A5 + (1/4)*A2 - A4 + A1 - (37/8)*M - A6 + A12 + A8$	$(29/8)*M - (1/4)*A2 - A1 - A6$	A6	$(1/2)*M - A12 - A8 + A5$	$(3/2)*M - A1 + A6 + A12 + A8$	$A1 - (3/4)*M - A6 - A13 - A12 - A8$
$(9/4)*M + A6 - A8 - A1$	A5	$2*M + A6 - A1$	$(-3/2)*M + A3 - A5 - A4 - A6 + A12 + A8$	$(41/8)*M - A3 + A5 - (1/4)*A2 + A4 - A1 + A6 - A12 - A8$	$A6 + (1/4)*A2 + A1 - (25/8)*M$	$(1/2)*M - A6$	$A1 - A6 + A12 + A8 - 2*M$	$M - A12 - A8 - A5$	$(-7/4)*M - A6 + A8 + A1$
$(1/4)*A2 + 2*A1 - A6 + A7 - A12 - A8 + A11 - (51/8)*M$	$(29/8)*M + A3 - A5 - (1/4)*A2 - A1 - A6 - A7 - A4 + 2*A12 + 2*A8 - A9 - A11$	$A5 - (25/8)*M + (1/4)*A2 + A1 + A6 + A7 + A4 - 2*A12 - 2*A8 + A9 + A11 - A3$	A1	A2	A3	$M - (A1 + A2 + A3)$	$(41/8)*M - A7 + A6 - (1/4)*A2 - A1$	$A7 - A6 + (1/4)*A2 + A1 - (37/8)*M$	$(55/8)*M - (1/4)*A2 - 2*A1 + A6 - A7 + A12 + A8 - A11$
$(11/8)*M - A10 - A7 - (5/4)*A2 - A4 - 3*A6 + A12 + A8 - A9 - A11$	$(5/2)*M - 2*A12 - 2*A8 - A3 + A2 + A5 + 2*A4 + A7 + 3*A6 + A9 + A11$	$A3 - A2 - 2*A4 - 2*M - 3*A6 + 2*A12 + 2*A8 - A5 - A7 - A9 - A11$	A4	$M - A1 - A2 - A4$	$A1 - A3 + A4$	$A2 + A3 - A4$	$M + A6 + A7 + A4 + A2$	$(-A6 - (1/2)*M - A7 - A4 - A2)$	$A10 + A7 + (5/4)*A2 + A4 + 3*A6 - A12 - A8 + A9 + A11 - (7/8)*M$
$(51/8)*M + A6 + A12 + A8 - (1/4)*A2 + A10 - A7 - 2*A1$	$(1/4)*A2 - (37/8)*M + A1$	$(41/8)*M - (1/4)*A2 - A1$	$M/2 - A3$	$A1 + A2 + A3 - M/2$	$M/2 - A1$	$M/2 - A2$	$A1 - 2*A6 - (41/8)*M - A5 - (3/4)*A2 - A4$	$(45/8)*M + A5 + (3/4)*A2 + A4 - A1 + 2*A6$	$2*A1 - A6 - A12 - A8 + (1/4)*A2 - A10 + A7 - (47/8)*M$
$A7 + (5/4)*A2 + A4 + 3*A6 - (3/8)*M - A12 - A8 + A9$	$(-1/2)*M - A2 - A4 - 2*A6$	$M + A2 + A4 + 2*A6$	$(1/2)*M - A1 + A3 - A4$	$(1/2)*M - A2 - A3 + A4$	$M/2 - A4$	$A1 + A2 + A4 - (1/2)*M$	A5	$(1/2)*M - A5$	$(7/8)*M - A7 - (5/4)*A2 - A4 - 3*A6 + A12 + A8 - A9$
$A1 - A6 - A12 - (5/4)*M$	$A12 + A8 - A5$	$A1 - M - A6 - A12 - A8$	$A7 - (25/8)*M + (1/4)*A2 + A1$	$(1/2)*M - A7$	$(1/2)*M + A2 + A5 + 2*A6 + A7 + A4 - A12 - A8 + A9 + A11$	$A12 + A8 - A9 - A1 - A11 - A5 + (25/8)*M - 2*A6 - A7 - (5/4)*A2 - A4$	$2*M + A6 - A1$	A5	$(7/4)*M - A1 + A6 + A12$
$A1 - (5/4)*M - A6 - A13$	$(5/2)*M + A6 - A12 - A8 - A1$	$A12 + A8 + A5 - (1/2)*M$	$(29/8)*M - A7 - (1/4)*A2 - A1$	A7	$A12 + A8 - A9 - A11 - A2 - A5 - 2*A6 - A7 - A4$	$A1 + A5 - (21/8)*M + 2*A6 + A7 + (5/4)*A2 + A4 - A12 - A8 + A9 + A11$	$(1/2)*M - A5$	$A1 - (3/2)*M - A6$	$(7/4)*M - A1 + A6 + A13$
M/4	$A12 + A13 + A8 - (1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*M - A8$	$(1/2)*M - A9$	$(1/2)*M - A10$	$A10 + A9 + A11 - (1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*M - A11$	$(1/2)*M - A12$	$(1/2)*M - A13$	M/4

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 embedded with a *double-digit pandiagonal* magic square of order 8. It contains a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 in the middle. The magic squares of orders 4, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10, 8 and 4 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := 2 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 4.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 8. See below two examples:

Example 5.20. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	12	-72	31	34	37	-63	40	43	46	12	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	194	-86	2	72	-184	135	25	-28	160	-170	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	91	22	110	-48	208	-111	-1	-36	-48	-67	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	-312	156	-132	11	12	16	9	229	-205	336	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	-108	205	-181	19	6	14	9	132	-108	132	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	389	-208	232	8	15	13	12	-335	359	-365	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	79	-105	129	10	15	5	18	22	2	-55	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	-117	52	-136	-108	-4	155	5	110	22	141	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	-120	60	72	132	28	-131	19	2	-86	144	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
	12	96	-7	-10	-13	87	-16	-19	-22	12	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
©IJT	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

10x10	pan	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
100	10	-80	31	34	37	-71	40	43	46	10	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
100	184	-74	-2	56	-147	106	25	-32	148	-164	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
100	73	22	94	-36	167	-86	-5	-20	-56	-53	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
100	-261	127	-107	11	12	16	1	188	-168	281	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
100	-119	185	-165	19	-2	14	9	124	-104	139	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
100	338	-171	191	4	19	9	8	-294	314	-318	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
100	82	-101	121	6	11	1	22	22	-2	-62	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
100	-107	52	-128	-83	-8	151	-20	94	22	127	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
100	-110	40	76	103	28	-131	40	-2	-74	130	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	10	100	-11	-14	-17	91	-20	-23	-26	10	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
©IJT	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 96$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 48$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 100$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 80$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 40$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 4, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.21. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$(1/6)*S$	$A18+A14+A5+A1-(2/3)*S-A21-A13$	A18	$A13-A1-A18-A14-A12-A15-A5-A4-A17+2*S-A20$	A19	$A12+A15+A4+A17+(1/3)*S-A18-A19$	A20	$-(1/3)*S$	A21	$(1/6)*S$
$A13-(1/6)*S+A21$	$(4/3)*S-A1-A18-A14-A5$	A1	A2	$A18+A14+A5-A4-(1/3)*S-A2-A3$	A3	A4	$(1/3)*S-A13$	A13	$(1/2)*S-A21-A13$
$A14-(1/2)*S$	A5	A6	A7	$2*A17+A4+A16+A14+A15-A8+A11+A12-S$	$(3/2)*S-2*A17+A3-A16-A5-2*A14-A15+A8-A7-A6-A11$	$A14-A12+(1/2)*S-A3-A4$	$(1/3)*S-A14$	A14	$(5/6)*S-A14$
$A15+A4+A20-(1/6)*S-A13$	$A12-(2/3)*S+A18+A14+A17-A6-A2$	$A3-A6+A10-A7+(1/6)*S$	$S-A17-A3-A11-A10-A12$	$A11-A18-2*A14-A15-A16-A5-A4-A17+2*S+A6-A1-A9$	$A9+A5+A14+A8-A11+A1-A12-(1/3)*S$	$A17+A4+A6+A16+A15-A8+A11+A7+A2+A12-(7/6)*S$	$(1/3)*S-A15$	A15	$A13-A15-A4+(1/2)*S-A20$
$A15+A16+A4+A17+(1/3)*S-A19-A18$	$A2-A18-2*A14-A15-A16-A5-2*A17+2*S+A6-A10-A12$	A8	A9	$2*A17+A3+A1+A18+2*A14+A15+A16+A5+A4-(7/3)*S-A6+A10+A12$	$2*S/3-A3-A8-A1$	$2*S/3-A4-A2-A9$	$(1/3)*S-A16$	A16	$A18-A15-A16-A4-A17+A19$
$A18+A19-A15-A4-(1/3)*S$	A10	$2*A17-A3+A16+A5+2*A14+A15-A8+A7-(5/6)*S$	$A6-A9-A14-A8+A11+A12+(1/6)*S$	$A8-A11-A10-A12+(5/3)*S-2*A17-A4-A16-A5-A14-A15$	A11	$A3+A4-A7+A8-A6+A9-A11$	$(1/3)*S-A17$	A17	$A15+A4+(2/3)*S-A18-A19$
$(7/6)*S-A20-A14-A15-A16-A4-A17$	$A1+A18+2*A14+A15+A16+A5+A17-(5/3)*S$	$(5/3)*S-2*A17-A16-A5-2*A14-A15-A10-A1$	$A17+A3-A6+A14+A8+A10-A7-(1/6)*S-A2$	$A4+A9-A11-A18-A14-A17+S+A2-A12$	$2*A17-A3+A6+A16-A9+A14+A15-A8+A11+A7+A12-(5/6)*S$	$S-A17-A4-A16-A14-A15$	$A13+A14+A15+A16+A17-(2/3)*S$	$S-A13-A14-A15-A16-A17$	$A14+A15+A16+A4+A17+A20-(5/6)*S$
$(2/3)*S$	$(7/6)*S+A13-A1-A18-A14-A5$	$(5/6)*S-A18$	$A1+A18+A14+A15+A5+A17-(3/2)*S+A12$	$A18-A15-A17-A4$	$(1/3)*S-A12$	$A4-A13+(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$	$-(1/3)*S$
$(1/3)*S-A21$	$A1+A18+A14+A5-(5/6)*S-A13$	$A18-(1/2)*S$	$(11/6)*S-A12-A1-A18-A14-A15-A5-A17$	$A4-A18+A15+A17+(1/3)*S$	A12	$(1/6)*S+A13-A4$	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$	A21
$(1/6)*S$	$A13-A18-A14-A5-A1+S+A21$	$(1/3)*S-A18$	$A1+A18+A14+A12+A15+A5+A4+A17+A20-(5/3)*S-A13$	$(1/3)*S-A19$	$A18+A19-A12-A15-A4-A17$	$(1/3)*S-A20$	$(2/3)*S$	$(1/3)*S-A21$	$(1/6)*S$

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 embedded with a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 8. It contains a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner. The magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 are of equal width and length. The magic sums of orders 10, 8 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{3} \times S$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := \frac{4}{3} \times S$, where S is the magic sum of order 6.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 6 should be multiple of 6. See below two examples:

Example 5.21. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	10x10	pan	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	
60	6	0	28	-101	29	43	30	-12	31	6	60	70	7	-4	28	-89	29	45	30	-14	31	7	70
60	48	-30	11	12	16	13	14	-11	23	-36	60	70	47	-22	11	12	14	13	14	-9	23	-33	70
60	6	15	16	17	132	-137	-7	-12	24	6	60	70	3	15	16	17	126	-128	-4	-10	24	11	70
60	40	49	6	-67	-104	32	120	-13	25	-28	60	70	39	45	7	-61	-92	30	113	-11	25	-25	70
60	47	-138	18	19	176	-18	-21	-14	26	-35	60	70	49	-126	18	19	162	-14	-17	-12	26	-35	70
60	6	20	124	4	-143	21	10	-15	27	6	60	70	4	20	119	5	-133	21	10	-13	27	10	70
60	-104	120	-139	51	-41	125	-80	101	-89	116	60	70	-97	110	-129	50	-35	120	-74	97	-83	111	70
60	24	-13	2	98	-38	-10	-3	6	6	-12	60	70	28	-6	7	89	-38	-8	-2	7	7	-14	70
60	-19	25	10	-86	50	22	15	6	6	31	60	70	-17	20	7	-75	52	22	16	7	7	31	70
	6	12	-16	113	-17	-31	-18	24	-19	6	60		7	18	-14	103	-15	-31	-16	28	-17	7	70
©IJT	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	©IJT	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 60$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 48$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 36$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 70$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 56$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 42$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.22. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$(1/3)*M$	$(8/3)*M-A8-A9-A10-A11-A12-A13$	A8	A9	A10	A11	A12	0	A13	$(1/3)*M$
$A6-A3+A11-A1-A2-A4+A10+A9+A12-(1/3)*M+A13$	$A1-A6+A3+A2+A4-(4/3)*M+A8$	$A6-A3-A2-A4+(5/3)*M+A5-A8-A1$	$2*M/3-A5$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A2+A3-M/3$	$2*M/3-A3$	$(2/3)*M-A6+A3-A11+A1+A2+A4-A10-A9-A12$	$A6-A3+A11-A1-A2-A4+A10+A9+A12$	$A3-A11+A1+A2+A4-A10-A9-A12+M-A13-A6$
$M-A7-A10+A1-A8$	$(1/3)*M+A7+A10-A5-A1$	$(1/3)*M+2*A1-A7-A10$	$M/3+A5-A1$	$A6-A4+M-A8$	$(1/3)*M+A8-A6-A3$	$A3+A4-M/3$	$A7+A10+A8-A1-(2/3)*M$	$A1-A10+(4/3)*M-A7-A8$	$A7+A10+A8-A1-(1/3)*M$
$2*A3+2*A2+2*A4+A10-A9-(8/3)*M+A7+2*A8-2*A6$	$2*M+A6-A3-A2-A4-A10-A7+A5-A8$	$A3+A2+A4+A10+A7-A5+A8-M-A1-A6$	A1	$A2+A4+A8-(2/3)*M-A6$	$A6-A2+M-A8$	$2*M/3-A4$	$A6-2*A3-A11-A2-A4+(11/3)*M-A7-2*A10-2*A8+A1$	$2*A3+A11+A2+A4-3*M+A7+2*A10+2*A8-A1-A6$	$2*A6-2*A3-2*A2-2*A4-A10+A9+(10/3)*M-A7-2*A8$
A7	A2	$M-A2-A3$	A3	$A6-A3-A2-A4+2*M-A8-A1$	$A1-A6+A3+A2+A4-A5+A8-M$	A5	$A3+A11+A2+A4+A10+A8-(5/3)*M-A1$	$A1-A3-A11-A2-A4+(7/3)*M-A10-A8$	$(2/3)*M-A7$
$A1-A11+A6-A3-A2-A4-A10+(7/3)*M-A7-A8$	$A4-(1/3)*M+A8-A6$	$A6+A3+(1/3)*M-A8$	$M-A3-A4$	$(1/3)*M-A7-A10+A5+A1$	$(1/3)*M+A7+A10-2*A1$	$M/3-A5+A1$	$(2/3)*M-A6$	A6	$A11-A6+A3+A2+A4-A10+A7+A8-(5/3)*M-A1$
$M-A1-A12$	$A6-A2-A4+(4/3)*M-A8$	$A2+A8-(1/3)*M-A6$	A4	$A3+A2+A4+A10-(4/3)*M+A7-A5+A8-A6$	$(5/3)*M+A1+A6-A3-A2-A4-A10-A7+A5-A8$	$2*M/3-A1$	$A6+A11-A2-A4+A10+A9+A12-(2/3)*M$	$(4/3)*M-A6-A11+A2+A4-A10-A9-A12$	$A1+A12-(1/3)*M$
$(2/3)*M$	$A11-(5/3)*M+A10+A8+A9+A12$	M-A8	$A6+A11-A2-A4+(1/3)*M+A10-A1$	$3*M-A7-2*A10+A1-A3-A11-A2-A4-A8$	$A3+A2+A4+A10-(5/3)*M+A7+A8-A1$	$M-A6-A11+A1+A2+A4-A10-A9-A12$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	0
$(2/3)*M-A13$	$(7/3)*M-A10-A8-A9-A12-A11$	$A8-(1/3)*M$	$A2+A4+(1/3)*M-A10+A1-A6-A11$	$A3+A11+A2+A4-(7/3)*M+2*A10+A8+A7-A1$	$A1+(7/3)*M-A3-A2-A4-A10-A7-A8$	$A6+A11-A1-A2-A4+A10+A9+A12-(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	A13
$(1/3)*M$	$A8+A9+A10+A11+A12+A13-2*M$	$(2/3)*M-A8$	$(2/3)*M-A9$	$(2/3)*M-A10$	$(2/3)*M-A11$	$(2/3)*M-A12$	$(2/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A13$	$(1/3)*M$

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 embedded with a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 8. It contains a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner. It is composed of 4 equal sum *semi-magic* squares of order 3. The magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 are of equal width and length. The magic sums of orders 10, 8, 6 and 3 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10}{3} \times M$, $T_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8}{3} \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 2 \times M$, where M is the *semi-magic* sum of order 3.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples:

Example 5.22. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	10x10	pan	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	
80	8	-59	18	19	20	21	22	0	23	8	80	90	9	-51	18	19	20	21	22	0	23	9	90
80	63	20	3	1	4	17	3	-32	48	-47	80	90	62	16	8	3	6	16	5	-30	48	-44	90
80	-20	19	-7	12	8	-3	19	28	-12	36	80	90	-17	20	-6	13	11	-2	18	26	-8	35	90
80	36	-15	28	11	12	10	2	-51	67	-20	80	90	28	-9	25	11	10	13	4	-40	58	-10	90
80	17	12	-1	13	-4	13	15	47	-31	-1	80	90	17	12	2	13	2	10	15	42	-24	1	90
80	-32	8	19	-3	-3	23	4	0	16	48	80	90	-25	7	20	0	-2	24	5	2	16	43	90
80	-9	4	6	14	31	-12	5	56	-40	25	80	90	-6	8	5	14	27	-7	7	54	-36	24	90
80	16	60	6	28	-52	43	-37	8	8	0	80	90	18	55	9	29	-43	38	-34	9	9	0	90
80	-7	-44	10	-12	68	-27	53	8	8	23	80	90	-5	-37	9	-11	61	-20	52	9	9	23	90
	8	75	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	16	-7	8	80		9	69	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	18	-5	9	90
©IJT	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	©IJT	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 80$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 64$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 48$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 90$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 72$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 54$ respectively. The **semi-magic** sums of order 3 are 24 and 27 respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.23. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

M/4	$A_9 + A_7 - (1/4)*M$	$2*A_5 - A_4 + (5/4)*M + 2*A_6 - A_{12} - 2*A_1 - 2*A_3 - A_8$	$M - A_{11} - A_7 - A_5$	A_{10}	$2*A_3 - A_5 + A_4 - (1/2)*M - A_{10} - 2*A_6 + A_8 + 2*A_1$	A_{11}	A_{12}	$(1/2)*M - A_9$	M/4
$(3/4)*M - A_9 - A_7$	$(1/4)*M$	$2*A_1 - 2*A_6 - 2*A_5 + 2*A_3$	$(1/4)*M - A_1 + A_6 + A_5 - A_3$	$A_3 + A_1 - (1/4)*M$	$M - 2*A_1 + A_6 + A_5 - 2*A_3$	$(1/4)*M$	A_7	$(1/2)*M - A_7$	$A_9 + A_7 - (1/4)*M$
$2*A_3 + A_8 - 2*A_5 + A_4 - 2*A_6 + A_{12} + 3*A_1 - M$	$(3/4)*M + 2*A_6 + 2*A_5 - 2*A_3 - 3*A_1$	A_1	A_2	$M - A_2 - A_6 - A_5$	$A_6 + A_5 - A_1$	$3*A_1 - 2*A_6 - 2*A_5 + 2*A_3 - (1/4)*M$	$(5/4)*M - 3*A_1 + 2*A_6 + 2*A_5 - 2*A_3 - A_4 - A_8$	$3*A_1 - 2*A_6 - 2*A_5 - (3/4)*M + 2*A_3 + A_4 + A_8$	$(3/2)*M - 2*A_3 - A_8 + 2*A_5 - A_4 + 2*A_6 - A_{12} - 3*A_1$
$(1/2)*M - 2*A_1 + A_6 + 2*A_5 - 2*A_3 - A_4 + A_7 + A_{11}$	$3*A_1 + 3*A_3 + A_4 - 2*A_6 - 2*A_5 - (3/4)*M$	$(7/4)*M - 3*A_1 - A_2 + A_6 + A_5 - 2*A_3 - A_4$	$2*A_1 - A_6 - A_5 + 2*A_3 + A_4 - (3/4)*M$	$(3/4)*M + 2*A_6 + 2*A_5 - 2*A_3 - A_4 - 2*A_1$	$3*A_1 + A_2 - 2*A_6 - 2*A_5 + 2*A_3 + A_4 - (3/4)*M$	$(5/4)*M + 2*A_6 + 2*A_5 - 3*A_1 - 3*A_3 - A_4$	$2*A_1 - A_6 - 2*A_5 + 2*A_3 + A_4 - (1/2)*M$	$M - 2*A_1 + A_6 + 2*A_5 - 2*A_3 - A_4$	$2*A_1 - A_6 - 2*A_5 + 2*A_3 + A_4 - A_7 - A_{11}$
$(3/4)*M - A_{10} - A_1$	$(1/2)*M - A_3$	$A_2 + A_6 + A_5 - (1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*M + A_1 - A_6 - A_5$	$M/2 - A_1$	$M/2 - A_2$	A_3	$(1/4)*M + A_1 - A_6$	$(1/4)*M - A_1 + A_6$	$A_{10} + A_1 - (1/4)*M$
$A_{10} + A_6 - A_8$	$(1/2)*M - A_4$	$2*A_1 - 2*A_6 - 2*A_5 + 2*A_3 + A_4 - (1/4)*M$	$(5/4)*M + 2*A_6 + 2*A_5 - 2*A_3 - A_4 - A_2 - 3*A_1$	$3*A_1 + A_2 - A_6 - A_5 + 2*A_3 + A_4 - (5/4)*M$	$(5/4)*M + A_6 + A_5 - 2*A_3 - A_4 - 2*A_1$	A_4	A_8	$(1/2)*M - A_8$	$(1/2)*M - A_{10} - A_6 + A_8$
$(1/2)*M - A_{11}$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M - 2*A_1 + 2*A_6 + 2*A_5 - 2*A_3$	$(1/4)*M + A_1 - A_6 - A_5 + A_3$	$(3/4)*M - A_3 - A_1$	$2*A_1 - A_6 - A_5 + 2*A_3 - (1/2)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M - A_7$	A_7	A_{11}
$(1/2)*M - A_{12}$	$(1/2)*M - A_7$	$2*A_3 + A_4 + 2*A_1 + A_8 - 2*A_6 - 2*A_5 - (1/2)*M$	A_5	A_6	$(3/2)*M + A_6 + A_5 - 2*A_3 - A_4 - 2*A_1 - A_8$	A_7	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	A_{12}
A_9	A_7	$M + 2*A_6 + 2*A_5 - 2*A_3 - A_4 - 2*A_1 - A_8$	$(1/2)*M - A_5$	$(1/2)*M - A_6$	$2*A_1 - A_6 - A_5 + 2*A_3 + A_4 + A_8 - M$	$(1/2)*M - A_7$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M - A_9$
M/4	$(3/4)*M - A_9 - A_7$	$2*A_3 + A_8 - 2*A_5 + A_4 - 2*A_6 + A_{12} + 2*A_1 - (3/4)*M$	$A_7 + A_5 + A_{11} - (1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*M - A_{10}$	$A_5 - A_4 + A_{10} + 2*A_6 + M - 2*A_1 - 2*A_3 - A_8$	$(1/2)*M - A_{11}$	$(1/2)*M - A_{12}$	A_9	M/4

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 embedded with a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 8. It contains a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner having *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 in the middle. The magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 are of equal width and length. The magic sums of orders 10, 8, 6 and 4 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 2 \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3}{2} \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 4.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4. See below two examples:

Example 5.23. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	10x10	pan	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	
70	7	29	-5	-25	20	-1	21	22	-5	7	70	90	9	27	5	-17	20	-5	21	22	-1	9	90
70	-15	7	-14	14	17	11	7	17	-3	29	70	90	-9	9	-14	16	15	19	9	17	1	27	90
70	23	24	11	12	-15	20	-10	6	8	-9	70	90	15	30	11	12	-7	20	-12	16	2	3	90
70	36	3	-5	10	21	2	11	2	12	-22	70	90	40	-3	9	4	27	-4	21	-2	20	-22	90
70	-10	1	29	-6	3	2	13	2	12	24	70	90	-4	5	25	-2	7	6	13	4	14	22	90
70	18	0	-7	12	19	4	14	18	-4	-4	70	90	18	4	-9	22	9	14	14	18	0	0	90
70	-7	7	28	0	-3	3	7	-3	17	21	70	90	-3	9	32	2	3	-1	9	1	17	21	90
70	-8	-3	4	15	16	-7	17	7	7	22	70	90	-4	1	0	15	16	5	17	9	9	22	90
70	19	17	10	-1	-2	21	-3	7	7	-5	70	90	19	17	18	3	2	13	1	9	9	-1	90
	7	-15	19	39	-6	15	-7	-8	19	7	70		9	-9	13	35	-2	23	-3	-4	19	9	90
©IJT	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	©IJT	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 70$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 56$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 42$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 28$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 90$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 72$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 54$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 36$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.24. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$m/2$	$(11/10)*m+A3-A2+2*A1-A9-A8-A7$	$A6$	$A7$	$A4+A5-(3/5)*m$	$(3/2)*m-A1-A5$	$A8$	$A2-A1+2*m-A4-A6-A3$	$A9$	$m/2$
$A2+A1+A9+A8+A7-2*m$	$(12/5)*m-3*A1-A3$	$A1$	$(3/5)*m$	$A1$	$A3+A1-A2$	$A2$	$(5/2)*m-A2-A1-A7-A8$	$A2-(3/2)*m+A1+A7+A8$	$3*m-A2-A1-A9-A8-A7$
$(3/2)*m-A6-A1$	$3*A1-(7/5)*m+A3$	$m-A1$	$(2/5)*m$	$m-A1$	$m+A2-A3-A1$	$m-A2$	$A2-A4-A3+m$	$A4+A3-A2$	$A6+A1-(1/2)*m$
$(12/5)*m-2*A1-A3-A7$	$(9/10)*m-A1$	$(3/2)*m-A3-A1$	$A3+A1+A1-(9/10)*m$	$(3/2)*m-A3-A1$	$2*A3-A2+3*A1-(3/2)*m$	$(3/2)*m-A3-2*A1+A2$	$A3+A1-(2/5)*m$	$(7/5)*m-A3-A1$	$2*A1+A3+A7-(7/5)*m$
$A1+A3-A4-A5+(3/5)*m$	$(1/10)*m+A1$	$A3+A1-(1/2)*m$	$(19/10)*m-A3-2*A1$	$A3+A1-(1/2)*m$	$(5/2)*m-2*A3-3*A1+A2$	$A3+2*A1-A2-(1/2)*m$	$(7/5)*m-A3-A1$	$A3+A1-(2/5)*m$	$(2/5)*m-A1-A3+A4+A5$
$A5$	$(12/5)*m+A2-2*A3-3*A1$	$A3+A1-A2$	$(3/5)*m-A3+A2$	$A3+A1-A2$	$A1$	$A3$	$A4$	$m-A4$	$m-A5$
$(3/2)*m-A3-A8$	$2*A3+3*A1-A2-(7/5)*m$	$m+A2-A3-A1$	$A3+(2/5)*m-A2$	$m-A3-A1+A2$	$m-A1$	$m-A3$	$A3-(3/2)*m+A1+A7+A8$	$(5/2)*m-A3-A1-A7-A8$	$A3+A8-(1/2)*m$
$A3-A2+A1+A4+A6-m$	$A2+(2/5)*m-2*A1+A7+A8-A3$	$A4+A3+A1-(1/2)*m-A2$	$A1$	$(3/5)*m-4*A1+4*A1$	$A1+(1/2)*m-A4$	$2*m-A1-A7-A8$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$A2-A1+2*m-A4-A6-A3$
$m-A9$	$A3+2*A1-A2+(3/5)*m-A7-A8$	$(3/2)*m+A2-A4-A3-A1$	$m-A1$	$(2/5)*m$	$(1/2)*m-A1+A4$	$A1+A7+A8-m$	$(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m$	$A9$
$m/2$	$A7-(1/10)*m-A3+A2-2*A1+A9+A8$	$m-A6$	$m-A7$	$(8/5)*m-A4-A5$	$A1+A5-(1/2)*m$	$m-A8$	$A3-A2+A1+A4+A6-m$	$m-A9$	$m/2$

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 embedded with a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 8 having *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner. It is formed by three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 . The magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10, 8 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := 5 \times m$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 5 \times m$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 3 \times m$, where m is the width of magic rectangle of order $m \times 3m$

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the width of magic rectangle of order $m \times 3m$ should be multiple of 10. See below two examples:

Example 5.24. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	10x10	pan	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
150	15	-37	25	28	23	13	31	3	34	15	150	150	200	20	-26	25	28	17	28	31	23	34	20	200	
150	56	26	10	18	10	13	13	-7	37	-26	150	150	200	36	50	10	24	10	13	13	18	22	4	200	
150	10	4	20	12	20	17	17	8	22	20	150	150	200	25	-10	30	16	30	27	27	18	22	15	200	
150	8	17	19	9	19	4	22	14	16	22	150	150	200	32	26	34	0	34	-11	37	10	30	8	200	
150	3	13	11	21	11	26	8	16	14	27	150	150	200	9	14	6	40	6	51	3	30	10	31	200	
150	22	23	13	15	13	10	16	19	11	8	150	150	200	22	47	13	21	13	10	16	19	21	18	200	
150	-2	7	17	15	17	20	14	40	-10	32	150	150	200	13	-7	27	19	27	30	24	25	15	27	200	
150	27	48	17	10	18	6	-9	15	15	3	150	150	200	17	52	12	10	24	11	11	20	20	23	200	
150	-4	-18	13	20	12	24	39	15	15	34	150	150	200	6	-12	28	30	16	29	29	20	20	34	200	
	15	67	5	2	7	17	-1	27	-4	15	150	150		20	66	15	12	23	12	9	17	6	20	200	
©IJT	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	©IJT	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 150$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 120$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 90$ and $m \times 3m := 30 \times 90$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 200$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 160$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 120$ and $m \times 3m := 40 \times 120$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.25. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$(1/4)*M$	$(3/4)*M-A6-A12$	$(-A1-(7/4)*M)$	$A6+A7-A10-A5+(1/4)*M$	$A9$	$A5+(11/4)*M+A1-A7-A11-A9$	$A10$	$A11$	$A12$	$(1/4)*M$
$A6+A12-A1$	$A1$	$M-A1-A3$	$A3+A1-A2$	$A2-A1$	$(1/2)*M-A5$	$A5$	$(1/4)*M-A6+A1$	$(1/4)*M+A6-A1$	$(1/2)*M+A1-A6-A12$
$A1+2*M$	$A3$	0	$A2$	$M-A2-A3$	$(1/4)*M+A4$	$(1/4)*M-A4$	$A11-A1-(7/4)*M$	$(9/4)*M-A11+A1$	$(-3/2)*M-A1$
$A1-A6-A7+A10+A5$	$(1/2)*M-A1+A2-A3$	$A1+(1/2)*M-A2$	$(1/2)*M-A1$	$(- (1/2)*M+A1+A3)$	$(5/2)*M+A2-A11-A8$	$(-2*M-A2+A11+A8)$	$A7$	$(1/2)*M-A7$	$(1/2)*M-A1+A6+A7-A10-A5$
$(3/4)*M-A9$	$(1/2)*M-A2$	$A2-(1/2)*M+A3$	$(1/2)*M-A3$	$(1/2)*M$	$A5+A11+A8-(9/4)*M-A2-A4$	$(11/4)*M+A2+A4-A5-A11-A8$	$A5-A7+(1/4)*M-A4$	$A7+(1/4)*M+A4-A5$	$A9-(1/4)*M$
$A7+A11+A9-A5-(9/4)*M-A1$	$A1+A5-(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A4$	$A8+A11-A1-(7/4)*M-A2$	$A4+(5/2)*M+A2-A11-A5-A8$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$A8$	$(1/2)*M-A8$	$A5+(11/4)*M+A1-A7-A11-A9$
$(1/2)*M-A10$	$(3/4)*M-A1-A5$	$A4$	$(9/4)*M+A2-A8-A11+A1$	$A5-2*M+A8-A4-A2+A11$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$A4+A6-A5+(11/4)*M-A11-A8$	$A5+A11+A8-(9/4)*M-A4-A6$	$A10$
$(1/2)*M-A11$	$A6$	$(5/2)*M+A1-A11$	$(3/4)*M-A1-A7$	$A7+A4-A5$	$(1/2)*M-A8$	$A5+A11+A8-(9/4)*M-A4-A6$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$A11$
$(1/2)*M-A12$	$(1/2)*M-A6$	$A11-2*M-A1$	$A7+A1-(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M+A5-A4-A7$	$A8$	$A4+A6-A5+(11/4)*M-A11-A8$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$A12$
$(1/4)*M$	$A6+A12-(1/4)*M$	$(9/4)*M+A1$	$(1/4)*M-A6-A7+A10+A5$	$(1/2)*M-A9$	$A7+A11+A9-A5-(9/4)*M-A1$	$(1/2)*M-A10$	$(1/2)*M-A11$	$(1/2)*M-A12$	$(1/4)*M$

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 embedded with a *cornered pandiagonal* magic square of orders 8 and 6.. It contains a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal width and length in each case. The magic sums of orders 10, 8, 6 and 4 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 2 \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3}{2} \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 4.

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4. See below two examples:

Example 5.25. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	12	-32	-94	6	34	62	37	40	43	12	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	58	10	22	13	3	2	22	-3	27	-34	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	106	16	0	13	19	31	-7	-54	78	-82	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	16	11	21	14	2	62	-38	28	-4	8	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	2	11	5	8	24	-47	71	-13	37	22	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	-38	20	5	-36	59	12	12	31	-7	62	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	-13	4	19	60	-35	12	12	83	-59	37	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	-16	25	90	-2	25	-7	-59	12	12	40	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	-19	-1	-66	26	-1	31	83	12	12	43	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
	12	56	118	18	-10	-38	-13	-16	-19	12	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
©IJT	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
10x10	pan	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	11	-35	-87	5	34	51	37	40	43	11	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	58	10	18	13	3	0	22	-4	26	-36	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	98	16	0	13	15	30	-8	-47	69	-76	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	16	9	19	12	4	52	-30	28	-6	6	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	-1	9	7	6	22	-38	60	-14	36	23	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	-29	21	3	-29	49	11	11	31	-9	51	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	-15	1	19	51	-27	11	11	72	-50	37	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	-18	25	80	-5	25	-9	-50	11	11	40	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	-21	-3	-58	27	-3	31	72	11	11	43	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
	11	57	109	17	-12	-29	-15	-18	-21	11	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
©IJT	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 96$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 72$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 48$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 110$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 88$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 66$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 44$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.26. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$(1/6)*S$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$A13+A11+(1/6)*S-A4-A17$	$(5/6)*S+A4-A19-A18-A16-A13-A11$	A19	$(1/3)*S-A15$	$(1/6)*S$
$(1/3)*S-A15$	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S+A4-A19-A16+A9$	$2*A4-(16/3)*S-2*A19-A16+3*A9-A14$	$A12+(1/3)*S-A10-A18$	$A4+A10+A17-A12-A13-A11+(1/6)*S$	$(31/6)*S-3*A4+3*A19+A18+2*A16+A13+A11-A17-3*A9+A14$	$(1/2)*S-A4-A9$	$(1/6)*S$	A15
$(1/6)*S-A4+A19$	$(1/3)*S-A9$	$A19+A16-A4$	A1	A2	A3	$S-A19-A16-A2-A1-A3$	A4	A9	$(1/6)*S+A4-A19$
$A4-A19-A12-A13-A14-A11+(5/6)*S$	$(31/6)*S+3*A19+A16+A13+A11-3*A9+A12+2*A14-3*A4-A17$	$2*A4+A17-2*A19-A16-A12-A13-A14-A11+S-A1$	$8*A4+4*A10+4*A17-8*A19+A18+12*A9-A2-4*A16-4*A12-4*A13-4*A14-3*A11-(145/6)*S$	$2*A4+A6-A3-2*A19+A18+A9+A8+A7-A2-A12-2*A14+(1/3)*S-A1$	$3*A19-A9+A16+A12+A13+2*A14+A11-(1/2)*S+A1-3*A4-A6-A17$	$8*A19-A18-12*A9-A8-A7+A2+4*A16+4*A12+4*A13+4*A14+3*A11+(149/6)*S-8*A4-4*A10-4*A17$	$A3+A19-A18+A2+A12+A14-(1/2)*S+A1-A4$	$3*A4+A17-3*A19+3*A9-A16-A12-A13-2*A14-A11-(29/6)*S$	$A19+A12+A13+A14+A11-(1/2)*S-A4$
A11	$A10+(1/3)*S-A12-A11$	$(71/3)*S-10*A4+10*A19+5*A16+5*A13+5*A11-12*A9+5*A12+5*A14-4*A10-5*A17$	$9*A19-2*A18-13*A9-A8-A7+A2+3*A16+5*A12+4*A13+6*A14+3*A11+25*S-10*A4-4*A10-4*A17$	$A4-A6+A3-A18-A8+A2-A11+(1/6)*S+A1$	A5	$11*A4+4*A10+A6+6*A17-11*A19+A18+13*A9+A8-A2-5*A16-5*A12-6*A13-6*A14-4*A11-(47/2)*S-A1-A5$	$8*A4+4*A10-A3+3*A17-8*A19+2*A18+12*A9+A8+A7-A2-3*A16-5*A12-3*A13-5*A14-3*A11-(73/3)*S$	$(-A10+A12+A11)$	$(1/3)*S-A11$
A12	$(1/3)*S-A10$	$9*A4+4*A10-A6+4*A17-9*A19+12*A9-4*A16-4*A12-4*A13-5*A14-4*A11-(143/6)*S+A1$	$2*A4+A6+A17-(1/6)*S-A19+A18-A13+A9+A8-A12-A14-A1$	$7*A4+4*A10+4*A17-8*A19+A18+12*A9+A8-A2-3*A16-4*A12-4*A13-5*A14-3*A11-24*S-A5$	$A6-A3-4*A17+8*A19-12*A9+3*A16+4*A12+4*A13+5*A14+4*A11+(49/2)*S-A1-8*A4-4*A10$	$A3-A17+2*A19-A18-A9-A8+A2+A16+A12+A13+A14-(1/6)*S+A1-2*A4-A6$	$A5-8*A4-4*A10-4*A17+8*A19-A18-12*A9-A8+3*A16+4*A12+4*A13+5*A14+3*A11+(74/3)*S$	A10	$(1/3)*S-A12$
A13	$2*A4+A17-2*A19+3*A9-A16-A13-A14-(16/3)*S$	A6	A7	$A5-A6+(1/6)*S-A4+A19+A13-A17-A9+A14-A8+A1$	$A4-A19+A9-A14+(1/6)*S$	A8	$A17-A7-A13+(2/3)*S-A1-A5$	$2*A19-3*A9+A16+A13+A14+(17/3)*S-$	$(1/3)*S-A13$
A14	$A4-A19+A9-A14+(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S-A16+A14$	$A16+A13-A14+(1/3)*S-A6-A17$	$A6-3*A17+9*A19-A18-12*A9+3*A16+3*A13+6*A14+(73/3)*S-A7+5*A12+4*A11-A1-9*A4-4*A10$	$10*A4+4*A10+5*A17-(139/6)*S-10*A19-4*A16-5*A13-5*A11+12*A9-5*A12-6*A14-A5$	$A5-A4+A18-A17+2*A19+A16+A13+A14-(7/6)*S+A7+A11+A1$	$(1/2)*S-A19-A14$	$A19-A9+A14+(1/6)*S-A4$	$(1/3)*S-A14$
A15	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S-A4+A19+A16-A9$	$(17/3)*S+2*A19+A16-3*A9+A14-2*A4$	$A10+A18-A12$	$A12+A13+A11+(1/6)*S-A4-A10-A17$	$3*A4-3*A19-A18-2*A16-A13-A11+A17+3*A9-A14-(29/6)*S$	$A4+A9-(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/3)*S-A15$
$(1/6)*S$	$(1/3)*S-A15$	$(1/3)*S-A16$	$(1/3)*S-A17$	$(1/3)*S-A18$	$A4+A17-A13-A11+(1/6)*S$	$A19+A18+A16+A13+A11-(1/2)*S-A4$	$(1/3)*S-A19$	A15	$(1/6)*S$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered pandiagonal** magic square of order 10 and 8 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 6. The magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**. The magic sums of orders 10, 8 and 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{3} \times S$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := \frac{4}{3} \times S$, where S is the magic sum of order 6.

In order to bring this **pandiagonal** magic square of order 10 without **decimal** entries, the magic sum of order 6 should be multiple of 6. See below two examples:

Example 5.26. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110
110	11	53	56	59	62	20	-196	65	-31	11	110
110	-31	11	-55	-443	-34	-4	624	-22	11	53	110
110	56	-13	101	11	14	17	-97	20	35	-34	110
110	-172	600	-214	-2010	-70	281	1993	86	-578	194	110
110	41	-25	2335	2020	-88	23	-2259	-1965	47	-19	110
110	44	-16	-2187	26	-2004	2113	104	2014	38	-22	110
110	47	-431	26	29	35	-49	32	-7	453	-25	110
110	50	-49	5	-10	2179	-2319	293	-82	71	-28	110
110	53	11	77	465	56	26	-602	44	11	-31	110
	11	-31	-34	-37	-40	2	218	-43	53	11	110
©IJT	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110

10x10	pan	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
120	12	53	56	59	62	21	-191	65	-29	12	120
120	-29	12	-54	-475	-32	-3	655	-19	12	53	120
120	57	-11	101	11	14	17	-91	20	35	-33	120
120	-167	631	-208	-2155	-68	278	2142	83	-607	191	120
120	41	-23	2477	2170	-87	23	-2400	-2111	47	-17	120
120	44	-14	-2330	25	-2148	2260	103	2162	38	-20	120
120	47	-463	26	29	36	-48	32	-3	487	-23	120
120	50	-48	6	-8	2325	-2458	286	-79	72	-26	120
120	53	12	78	499	56	27	-631	43	12	-29	120
	12	-29	-32	-35	-38	3	215	-41	53	12	120
©IJT	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 110$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 88$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 66$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 96$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 72$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.27. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$(1/3)*M$	$(4/3)*M+A4-A1-A10-A12-A14$	$(2/3)*M+A4-A13-A1$	$A10$	$(2/3)*M-A11-2*A4+2*A1$	$A11$	$A12$	$A13$	$A14$	$(1/3)*M$
$A10+A12+2*A14-A4+A1+A9-(4/3)*M$	$M-A14-A9$	$A5-A12+(2/3)*M-A8$	$A6+A12+A14-(4/3)*M+A8+A9$	$A12+A14+A7-(5/3)*M+A8+A9+A1$	$(7/3)*M-A8-A1-A12-A7-A14-A9$	$A4-A6-A12-A14+2*M-A8-A9-A1$	$(2/3)*M-A5+A8-A10$	$A10+A12+A14-M-A4+A1+A9$	$2*M+A4-A1-A9-A10-A12-2*A14$
$A12+A14-(4/3)*M-A4+A13+A1+A8+A9$	$(2/3)*M-A5$	$A1$	$M/3-A1+A2$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A3$	$M/3-A3+A4$	$2*M/3-A4$	$A5$	$2*M+A4-A13-A1-A8-A9-A12-A14$
$(5/3)*M-A1-A10-A14-A9$	$(2/3)*M-A6$	$M-A1-A2$	$M/3$	$A2+A1-M/3$	$M-A3-A4$	$M/3$	$A4+A3-M/3$	$A6$	$A10+A14+A9+A1-M$
$(8/3)*M+A11+2*A4-2*A1-2*A8-2*A9-2*A12-2*A14$	$(2/3)*M-A7$	$A2$	$M/3+A1-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$A4$	$M/3+A3-A4$	$2*M/3-A3$	$A7$	$2*A12+2*A14-A11-2*A4+2*A1+2*A8+2*A9-2*M$
$2*A1-A11$	$A7$	$A14-A3+A9$	$A4+A3-A12-2*A14+2*M-A8-2*A9-A1$	$A12+A14-M+A8+A9+A1-A4$	$(5/3)*M-A8-A9-A12-A14$	$A10+2*A12+2*A14-2*M-A4+A1+2*A9+A8-A2$	$(4/3)*M+A2-A10-A12-A14+A4-A1-A9$	$(2/3)*M-A7$	$(2/3)*M+A11-2*A1$
$A8$	$A6+A12+A14-M+A8+A9-A4$	$A3+A12-(2/3)*M+A8+A1-A4$	$M/3$	$A4-A3-A12+(4/3)*M-A8-A1$	$A2-A10+A4-A1+A8$	$M/3$	$A10+(2/3)*M-A4+A1-A8-A2$	$A4-A6-A12-A14+(5/3)*M-A8-A9$	$(2/3)*M-A8$
$M-A1-A13$	$A10+A14-M+A1+A9+A5-A8$	$A4-A12-A14+(5/3)*M-A8-A9-A1$	$A12+2*A14-(4/3)*M+A8+2*A9+A1-A4-A3$	$(2/3)*M-A14+A3-A9$	$A10+A12+A14-(2/3)*M-A4+A1+A9-A2$	$A2-A10-2*A12-2*A14+(8/3)*M+A4-A1-2*A9-A8$	$A12+A14-M+A8+A9$	$(5/3)*M-A1-A9-A5+A8-A10-A14$	$A13+A1-(1/3)*M$
$A9$	$(5/3)*M-A10-A12-A14+A4-A1-A9$	$A12+A8-A5$	$2*M-A8-A9-A6-A12-A14$	$(7/3)*M-A8-A1-A12-A7-A14-A9$	$A12+A14+A7-(5/3)*M+A8+A9+A1$	$A6+A12+A14-(4/3)*M+A1+A8+A9-A4$	$A5+A10-A8$	$A14+A9-(1/3)*M$	$(2/3)*M-A9$
$(1/3)*M$	$A1+A10+A12+A14-(2/3)*M-A4$	$A13+A1-A4$	$(2/3)*M-A10$	$A11+2*A4-2*A1$	$(2/3)*M-A11$	$(2/3)*M-A12$	$(2/3)*M-A13$	$(2/3)*M-A14$	$(1/3)*M$

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered pandiagonal** magic square of order 10 and 8 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 6. It contains 4 equal sums magic squares of order 3. The magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**. The magic sums of orders 10, 8, 6 and 3 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10}{3} \times M$, $T_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8}{3} \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 2 \times M$ where M is the magic sum of order 3.

In order to bring this **pandiagonal** magic square of order 10 without **decimal** entries, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples:

Example 5.27. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	10x10	pan	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	
80	8	-31	-4	20	-11	21	22	23	24	8	80	90	9	-27	-2	20	-9	21	22	23	24	9	90
80	74	-19	-9	67	71	-55	-48	-1	58	-58	80	90	70	-16	-7	63	66	-48	-42	1	55	-52	90
80	71	1	11	9	4	13	9	2	15	-55	80	90	67	3	11	10	6	13	10	4	15	-49	90
80	-34	0	1	8	15	-3	8	19	16	50	80	90	-29	2	4	9	14	0	9	18	16	47	90
80	-75	-1	12	7	5	14	7	3	17	91	80	90	-67	1	12	8	7	14	8	5	17	85	90
80	1	17	30	-62	56	-43	105	-38	-1	15	80	90	1	17	30	-56	53	-38	99	-34	1	17	90
80	18	61	34	8	-18	13	8	3	-45	-2	80	90	18	58	32	9	-14	13	9	5	-40	0	90
80	-10	47	-40	78	-14	54	-89	59	-31	26	80	90	-7	44	-35	74	-12	52	-81	56	-26	25	90
80	19	-42	25	-51	-55	71	64	17	35	-3	80	90	19	-37	25	-45	-48	66	60	17	34	-1	90
	8	47	20	-4	27	-5	-6	-7	-8	8	80		9	45	20	-2	27	-3	-4	-5	-6	9	90
©IJT	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	©IJT	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 80$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 64$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 48$ and $T_{3 \times 3} := 24$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 90$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 72$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 54$ and $T_{3 \times 3} := 27$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.28. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

$m/2$	$m-A_{11}$	$(12/5)*m-A_2-A_{40}-A_{10}-A_7$	A_7	$(3/5)*m-A_8+A_2$	A_8	A_{40}	A_{10}	A_{11}	$m/2$
A_{11}	$m/2$	$A_{40}+A_7-(7/5)*m+A_2+A_6$	$(3/2)*m+A_1-A_5-A_{40}-A_7$	$(12/5)*m-A_2-A_1-A_3-A_4$	$A_3+A_4+A_1-m$	$(1/2)*m-A_1+A_5$	$m-A_6$	$m/2$	$m-A_{11}$
$A_{40}+A_{10}+A_7+(1/2)*m-2*A_1-A_3$	$2*A_1-A_{40}-A_7+(1/2)*m+A_3-A_6$	$(12/5)*m-A_2-2*A_1-A_3$	A_1	$(3/5)*m$	A_2	$A_{40}+A_7-A_1$	$2*A_1+A_3-A_{40}-A_7$	$(1/2)*m-2*A_1+A_{40}+A_7-A_3+A_6$	$A_3-A_{40}-A_{10}-A_7+(1/2)*m+2*A_1$
$A_1+(1/2)*m-A_7$	$A_5+A_{40}+A_7-2*A_1$	$2*A_1-(7/5)*m+A_3+A_2$	$m-A_1$	$(2/5)*m$	$m-A_2$	$m+A_1-A_{40}-A_7$	$m-2*A_1+A_{40}+A_7-A_3$	$m+2*A_1-A_5-A_{40}-A_7$	$A_7-A_1+(1/2)*m$
$A_8+A_1+A_3-m$	A_4	$(9/10)*m-A_1$	$(3/2)*m-A_3-A_2$	$A_3+A_2+A_1-(9/10)*m$	$(3/2)*m-A_3-A_1$	$A_3-(3/2)*m+A_{40}+A_7+A_2$	$(3/2)*m-A_2+A_1-A_{40}-A_7$	$m-A_4$	$2*m-A_8-A_1-A_3$
$2*m-A_8-A_1-A_3$	$m-A_4$	$(1/10)*m+A_1$	$A_3+A_2-(1/2)*m$	$(19/10)*m-A_3-A_2-A_1$	$A_3+A_1-(1/2)*m$	$(5/2)*m-A_3-A_2-A_{40}-A_7$	$A_2-A_1+A_{40}+A_7-(1/2)*m$	A_4	$A_8+A_1+A_3-m$
$(1/2)*m+A_1-A_{40}$	$m-A_5$	$(12/5)*m-A_{40}-A_7-A_2-A_3$	$A_{40}+A_7-A_1$	$(3/5)*m+2*A_1-A_{40}-A_7$	$A_2-2*A_1+A_{40}+A_7$	A_1	A_3	A_5	$(1/2)*m-A_1+A_{40}$
$A_3-A_{10}+(1/2)*m$	$(1/2)*m+A_6-A_3$	$A_3+A_2-(7/5)*m+A_{40}+A_7$	$m+A_1-A_{40}-A_7$	$(2/5)*m-2*A_1+A_{40}+A_7$	$m-A_2+2*A_1-A_{40}-A_7$	$m-A_1$	$m-A_3$	$(1/2)*m+A_3-A_6$	$(1/2)*m-A_3+A_{10}$
$m-A_{11}$	$m/2$	$(12/5)*m-A_{40}-A_7-A_2-A_6$	$A_5+A_{40}+A_7-(1/2)*m-A_1$	$A_2+A_1+A_3-(7/5)*m+A_4$	$2*m-A_3-A_4-A_1$	$(1/2)*m+A_1-A_5$	A_6	$m/2$	A_{11}
$m/2$	A_{11}	$A_{40}+A_{10}+A_7+A_2-(7/5)*m$	$m-A_7$	$(2/5)*m+A_8-A_2$	$m-A_8$	$m-A_{40}$	$m-A_{10}$	$m-A_{11}$	$m/2$

Details:

It is a *single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 and 8 embedded with a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6. It contains 3 equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×6 . The magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are *pandiagonal*. The magic sums of orders 10, 8, 6 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := 5 \times m$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 4 \times m$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := 3 \times m$ where m is the width of magic rectangle of order $m \times 3m$

In order to bring this *pandiagonal* magic square of order 10 without *decimal* entries, the width of magic rectangle of order $m \times 3m$ should be multiple of 10. See below two examples:

Example 5.28. *Let's consider the following example:*

10x10	pan	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	10x10	pan	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
200	20	0	18	28	6	31	0	37	40	20	200	250	25	10	42	28	12	31	0	37	40	25	250
200	40	20	10	20	38	5	32	15	20	0	200	250	40	25	-4	35	62	-5	37	25	25	10	250
200	49	3	47	10	24	13	18	8	37	-9	200	250	54	8	71	10	30	13	18	8	42	-4	250
200	2	30	-7	30	16	27	22	32	10	38	200	250	7	30	-21	40	20	37	32	42	20	43	250
200	17	19	26	31	3	34	-3	29	21	23	200	250	7	19	35	46	-6	49	-18	44	31	43	250
200	23	21	14	9	37	6	43	11	19	17	200	250	43	31	15	4	56	1	68	6	19	7	250
200	30	18	39	18	16	21	10	16	22	10	200	250	35	28	63	18	22	21	10	16	22	15	250
200	-1	29	1	22	24	19	30	24	11	41	200	250	4	34	-13	32	28	29	40	34	16	46	250
200	0	20	30	20	2	35	8	25	20	40	200	250	10	25	54	15	-12	55	13	25	25	40	250
	20	40	22	12	34	9	40	3	0	20	200		25	40	8	22	38	19	50	13	10	25	250
©IJT	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	©IJT	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 200$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 160$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 120$ and $m \times 3m := 40 \times 120$ and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 250$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 200$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 150$ and $m \times 3m := 50 \times 150$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.29. Let's consider the following *self-made* magic square of order 10 with *reduced entries*:

M/4	$(1/2)*M-A12$	$(1/2)*M-A11$	$(5/2)*M-A10-2*A3-2*A1-A8-A5-A4$	$2*A3+2*A1-(3/2)*M+A8+A5+A4-A9$	A9	A10	A11	A12	M/4
A12	$(1/4)*M$	A6	$A4+2*A3+2*A1+A8+2*A5-2*M$	$A8+A7+A5-(1/2)*M$	$3*M-2*A1-A4-2*A3-2*A8-A7-2*A5$	$(1/2)*M-A5$	$(1/2)*M-A6$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A12$
A11	$(1/2)*M-A6$	$(1/4)*M$	$3*M-2*A5-2*A1-2*A8-2*A3-2*A4$	$A5+A1+A8+A3+A4-(5/4)*M$	$A3+A1-(1/4)*M$	$A5+A8+A4-(1/2)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	A6	$(1/2)*M-A11$
$A1-(7/4)*M+A10+2*A3+A8+A5+A4$	$(9/4)*M-A4-2*A3-A1-A8-2*A5$	$A1-(9/4)*M+2*A5+2*A8+2*A3+2*A4$	A1	A2	$(5/2)*M-A5-A2-A8-2*A3-A4-2*A1$	$A1-(3/2)*M+A5+A8+2*A3+A4$	$(11/4)*M-A1-2*A5-2*A8-2*A3-2*A4$	$A4+2*A3+A1+A8+2*A5-(7/4)*M$	$(9/4)*M-A1-A10-2*A3-A8-A5-A4$
$(5/2)*M-2*A8-2*A5-2*A3-2*A1-A4+A9$	$(1/2)*M-A7$	$(9/4)*M-A1-A3-A4-2*A5-2*A8$	$(1/4)*M+A5-A2-A1+A8$	$(3/4)*M-A5-A8$	$2*A1-(9/4)*M+2*A5+2*A8+2*A3+A4$	$(9/4)*M-A1-2*A5+A2-2*A8-2*A3-A4$	$A1+A3+A4-(7/4)*M+2*A5+2*A8$	A7	$2*A8+2*A5+2*A3+2*A1+A4-A9-2*M$
$(1/4)*M+A1-A9$	$A4+2*A3+A1+2*A8+A7+2*A5-(9/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A3$	$2*A1-2*M+A5+A2+A8+2*A3+A4$	$2*M-A5-A1-A8-2*A3-A4$	M/2-A1	M/2-A2	A3	$(11/4)*M-A4-2*A3-A1-2*A8-A7-2*A5$	$(1/4)*M-A1+A9$
A8+A5-A10	$(1/2)*M-A8$	$(1/2)*M-A4$	$(11/4)*M-2*A1-2*A5-2*A8-2*A3-A4$	$A1-(7/4)*M+2*A5+2*A8+2*A3+A4-A2$	$(1/4)*M-A5+A2+A1-A8$	$A5+A8-(1/4)*M$	A4	A8	$(1/2)*M-A8-A5+A10$
$(1/2)*M-A11$	A6	$(1/4)*M$	$2*A5+2*A1+2*A8+2*A3+2*A4-(5/2)*M$	$(7/4)*M-A5-A1-A8-A3-A4$	$(3/4)*M-A3-A1$	M-A5-A8-A4	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A6$	A11
$(1/2)*M-A12$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A6$	$(5/2)*M-A4-2*A3-2*A1-A8-2*A5$	M-A8-A7-A5	$2*A1+A4+2*A3+2*A8+A7+2*A5-(5/2)*M$	A5	A6	$(1/4)*M$	A12
M/4	A12	A11	$A10+2*A3+2*A1+A8+A5+A4-2*M$	$2*M-2*A3-2*A1-A8-A5-A4+A9$	$(1/2)*M-A9$	$(1/2)*M-A10$	$(1/2)*M-A11$	$(1/2)*M-A12$	M/4

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered pandiagonal** magic square of order 10, 8 and 6 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4. The magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**. The magic sums of orders 10, 8, 6 and 4 are given as $L_{10 \times 10} := \frac{5}{2} \times M$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 2 \times M$ and $S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3}{2} \times M$ where M is the magic sum of order 4.

In order to bring this **pandiagonal** magic square of order 10 without **decimal** entries, the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4. See below two examples:

Example 5.29. Let's consider the following example:

10x10	pan	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	10x10	pan	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	
110	11	-22	-19	-59	30	35	38	41	44	11	110	120	12	-20	-17	-49	24	35	38	41	44	12	120
110	44	11	26	66	62	-83	-1	-4	11	-22	110	120	44	12	26	58	60	-71	1	-2	12	-20	120
110	41	-4	11	-74	48	17	53	11	26	-19	110	120	41	-2	12	-62	43	16	51	12	26	-17	120
110	81	-44	96	11	14	-35	54	-74	66	-59	110	120	74	-35	87	11	14	-25	48	-63	59	-50	120
110	-41	-7	-59	41	-22	87	-62	81	29	63	110	120	-31	-5	-50	42	-19	78	-53	74	29	55	120
110	-13	105	5	57	-32	11	8	17	-83	35	110	120	-12	96	7	49	-24	13	10	17	-72	36	120
110	17	-10	2	-65	84	-19	44	20	32	5	110	120	17	-8	4	-54	77	-18	43	20	32	7	120
110	-19	26	11	96	-26	5	-31	11	-4	41	110	120	-17	26	12	86	-19	8	-27	12	-2	41	120
110	-22	11	-4	-44	-40	105	23	26	11	44	110	120	-20	12	-2	-34	-36	95	23	26	12	44	120
	11	44	41	81	-8	-13	-16	-19	-22	11	110		12	44	41	73	0	-11	-14	-17	-20	12	120
©IJT	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	©IJT	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

The magic sums for the first example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 110$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 88$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 66$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 44$, and for the second example are $L_{10 \times 10} := 120$, $T_{8 \times 8} := 96$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 72$ and $T_{4 \times 4} := 48$ respectively.

In both the examples the magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8 and 10 are **pandiagonal**.

Remark 1. We observe that the quantity of pandiagonal magic squares of order 10 is much more than the main magic and semi-magic squares. This due to the fact Section 2 and Section 3 don't work with **striped** magic squares of order 6. While this idea is included in the Section 4 on **algebraic pandiagonal** magic squares of order 10. In the revised version complete this idea.

6 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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